

PRE-NORMATIVE RESEARCH ON HYDROGEN RELEASES ASSESSMENT

D1.1

H₂ supply chains' unit processes

The project NHyRA has received funding from the Clean Hydrogen Partnership under Grant Agreement No 101137770. This Partnership receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation program, Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research.

Co-funded by
the European Union

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Project Acronym	NHyRA
Project Title	PRE-NORMATIVE RESEARCH ON HYDROGEN RELEASES ASSESSMENT
Type	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Call Identifier	HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2023-05-03
Topic	Pre-Normative Research on the determination of hydrogen releases from the hydrogen value chain
Project Coordinator	Matteo Robino (SNAM)
Project Duration	January 1, 2024 – December 31, 2026
Deliverable No.	D1.1
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP1 - H ₂ releases inventory
Task	T 1.1 - Definition of the H ₂ supply chains and unit processes
Lead beneficiary	Fondazione Bruno Kessler
Contributing beneficiaries	UNIBO, FBK, SNAM, ENEA, SURREY, DLR, ENGIE, BH, LINDE, EQN
Due date of deliverable	30/06/24
Actual submission date	01/08/24

VERSIONS

Revision Version	Date	Changes	Changes made by Partner
0.1	15 July 2024	First release	FBK; All contributing beneficiaries
0.2	23 July 2024	Reviews	FBK; All contributing beneficiaries

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Where explicit references are not provided, it is assumed that the data are derived from the direct experience of the consortium partners. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the NHyrA consortium shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Hydrogen is a key element in Europe's goal for a zero-emission energy system by 2050. It can decarbonize sectors like energy, industry, heating, and mobility. Establishing a reliable hydrogen supply chain, which includes production, transportation, storage, and utilization, is essential. The expected increase in hydrogen use within the energy and other sectors as part of the green energy transition necessitates a thorough evaluation of its environmental impact. Hydrogen emissions, whether planned or unplanned due to leaks, failures, or accidents, could pose indirect environmental impact and safety risks if not properly addressed.

Quantifying hydrogen releases across the value chain is challenging due to insufficient standardized data, and approved methodologies for their collection, quality check and use. Addressing this gap is crucial for understanding if hydrogen has a climate impact. Most of the literature focuses on leaks during failures, but there's limited information on overall hydrogen emissions. The research community needs rigorous and standardized methods to quantify both small and large hydrogen emissions and develop validated measurement techniques. An open-access inventory and user-friendly tool are needed to track hydrogen emissions as its use expands serving as basis for decision-makers.

The NHyra project would like to support the scientific community and all the interested stakeholders to cover this gap by providing at the end of the project a comprehensive "H₂ emissions" inventory containing as much as possible validated data about H₂ emissions from the elements of the value chain. The NHyra project will validate new methodologies for laboratory and field measurements and will conduct tests on some elements of the hydrogen value chain. These activities will be prodromal for the evaluation of hydrogen emissions scenarios for today, 2030, and 2050, helping decision-makers prioritize mitigation actions. The NHyra project aims also to provide inputs to the relevant standardization bodies.

This report defines the hydrogen supply chain, detailing its components' typical operative conditions and recognizing the potential sources of hydrogen emissions. Data about the typical operative conditions of the investigated components were gathered from literature and NHyra Consortium experts' inputs for hydrogen production, conversion, transport, storage, and end-use.

The term "archetype" will be used rather than component in the rest of the document.

From a technical perspective, the most promising technologies involved in the hydrogen supply chain over a large-scale prototype state (TRL 6) have been evaluated finding the fundamental process blocks that are, in most of the case presents, defining specific operational parameters as pressure, temperature, flow rate, material composition and others. Lower TRL technologies were not evaluated due to lack of uniformed information.

Summing up, the deliverable report provides a detailed dataset on primary technologies in the hydrogen supply chain, identifying key hydrogen losses and emissions for current and future scenarios. This comprehensive analysis supports the evaluation of mitigate potential environmental impact of the hydrogen value chain.

1. INTRODUCTION

This report focuses on the description and analysis of the main technologies across the entire hydrogen supply chain. It examines the main technologies currently adopted and sufficiently developed to at least TRL 6-7, at full prototype scale or pre-commercial demonstration stages as defined by the European Union for the Horizon 2020 program and also used by the International Energy Agency (IEA)¹. The analysis considers technological advancements and the projected increase in market share of individual technologies based on European development scenarios for 2030 and 2050, in accordance with the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)².

The report begins with an overview of the NHyra project, outlining the challenges and objectives it aims to address. It then describes the hydrogen supply chain considered, categorizing the various technologies and sectors of application. The specific technologies of each step of the supply chain, referred to as archetypes, are explained in terms of their roles in subsequent work packages, with a focus on characterizing the value chains in both current and future scenarios (2030-2050). The methodology used to gather information on the various archetypes is introduced, detailing the characterization of key plant components and the operational parameters that could be considered relevant for quantifying hydrogen emissions throughout the supply chain. Following the discussion of Task 1.2, this document adopts a standardized categorization of hydrogen emissions, considered both intentional and unintended leakages, which will be referenced throughout the project. The categorization aligns with standards from the broader gas sector, facilitating similar evaluations for different gases. This decision agreed by NHyra Consortium adheres to the categories outlined in the "Assessment of methane emissions for gas Transmission and Distribution system operators"³, and it could be adopted in future standardization efforts in the hydrogen sector. The characteristic parameters and emissions will be used to detail all the technologies, defined as "archetypes", in the following sections of the report, covering "production," "conversion/reconversion," "storage," "transport," and "end-users." This structured approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the hydrogen supply chain.

1.1. NHyra Project and Task description

NHyra project focuses on the evaluation of how much hydrogen is emitted in the whole value chain, focusing on the anthropogenic hydrogen emissions in the atmosphere. The project will deliver an estimation of "H₂ emissions" in different supply chains. For this purpose, an inventory containing data about H₂ emissions will be published and periodically updated in accordance with the rules defined in Task 1.2 and it will serve as a reference for the scientific and industrial community. New or adequately adapted experimental, theoretical, and simulation methodologies will be validated to perform laboratory or in-field measurements to achieve this goal. Experimental tests will also be performed on the most critical elements of the H₂ value chains by the partners of the Consortium. An overview of the H₂ emissions' scenarios in the current, middle (2030) and long (2050) term will be developed to support decision-makers to identify and prioritize effective mitigation actions.

The task on which the deliverable is based on aims to describe the main routes in H₂ supply chains, i.e., production, compression, storage, liquefaction, conversion in other energy carriers and utilization, as a collection of basic unit processes linked together. FBK with all the involved partners has contributed to

the definition of archetypes, i.e., the equipment, customized machines and assemblies, that could be part of supply chains and from which H₂ emissions could derive. A not exhaustive list of examples includes: H₂ production units (e.g., electrolyzers, steam methane reforming plants), pipework in transmission and distribution systems (pipes, valves, traps, assets, etc.), compressors, above ground storage systems (i.e., compressed tanks), underground storage systems (e.g. salt caverns), compressed gas and LH₂ transports, refuelling stations, fuel cells based on their knowhow and experience. The activity of Task 1.1 is preparatory for the design of the H₂ emission inventory (Task 1.2), to guide the methodology for quantifying losses in WP2, to assist in the identification of the main field test assessments in WP3, and to estimate the value chain and systems' H₂ emissions (WP4 and WP5).

This first deliverable D 1.1 “H₂ supply chains’ unit processes” within Work Package 1 involves defining the hydrogen (H₂) supply chains and unit processes, including main operational parameters and outlining the main pathways within H₂ supply chains as a sequence of fundamental unit processes linked together. Table 1 summarizes all the technical and management/communication Work Packages of NHyra Project.

Table 1: Work Packages of NHyra.

Work package	Description	WP Leader	Timeline (months)
WP1	H ₂ releases inventory	UNIBO	1-36
WP2	Methodology development for H ₂ releases’ quantification	INIG	3-27
WP3	Methodology validation and field tests assessment	NPL	7-34
WP4	H ₂ releases from supply chains	ENGIE	12-34
WP5	Hydrogen release scenarios	FBK	12-36
WP6	Dissemination, communication & exploitation	GERG	1-36
WP7	Coordination and Project Management	SNAM	1-36

1.2. Overview of the hydrogen supply chain

In the 2012-2021 period, the global hydrogen production stood at approximately 94–118 Mton_{H₂}/year, with around 60% generated as a primary product and the remaining 40% as a by-product, particularly in the chemical industry and the steel sector^{4,5}.

The direct production of hydrogen is mostly made from fossil sources, accounting for 99.3% of the total, with 70% originating from Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) and the remaining portion from coal gasification (CG). Less than 1% of primary hydrogen is produced through electrolysis, today. Similarly, hydrogen produced as a by-product is also sourced from fossil fuels, with only 0.5% currently produced through electrolysis. So, the total hydrogen production from electrolysis stands for approx. 80-100 kton_{H₂}/year.

Hydrogen is mostly used in the petrochemical sector (45%), ammonia production (35%), methanol production (14%), and the iron and steel industry (0.5%), with green hydrogen poised as a clean alternative for these sectors. It is crucial to emphasize the future trends in hydrogen demand and consumption for the years 2030 and 2050 worldwide⁵.

For 2030, the expected global trends, compared to the current consumption, include:

- Oil Refining Sector: Anticipated growth of approximately 7% in hydrogen demand.
- Chemical Sector: A substantial increase of 31% in demand, particularly for ammonia and methanol production.
- Steel Sector: A doubling of demand driven by the transition from Blast Furnace-Basic Oxygen Furnace to Electric Arc Furnace-Direct Reduced Iron technology.
- High-Temperature Heat Demand: An estimated 9% increase in demand for high-temperature heat under existing policies.

Looking ahead to 2050 for Europe:

- A projected 14% share of hydrogen in the European energy mix.
- Expectation of an installed capacity of 500 GW for electrolyzers.
- Cumulative investments in favour of renewable hydrogen from now until 2050 are estimated to range between 180-470 B€.

These trends underscore the growing importance of hydrogen and, specifically, renewable energy sources as a key component of Europe's energy transition. The definition of renewable hydrogen is introduced in the delegate act related to the RFNBO of the RED II directive. Specific rules are established to produce renewable liquid and gaseous transport fuels of non-biological origin and the methodology for assessing GHG emissions savings from these fuels. The maximum GHG emission intensity threshold is set at 70% below a fossil fuel comparator of 94 gCO_{2,eq}/MJ equivalent to 3.38 tCO_{2,eq}/tH₂ or 102 gCO_{2,eq}/kWh_{H₂}⁶.

The research community is investigating if hydrogen emissions, whether intentional or unintentional due to leaks, failures, or accidents, can have an indirect impact on the environment. Indeed, it is supposed that hydrogen emissions into the atmosphere can affect the lifetime of other greenhouse gases, such as methane, ozone, and water vapor, thereby indirectly contributing to the increase of the Earth's temperature in the near-term. For example, a recent study by the English Department for Energy Security

& Net Zero defined the Global Warming Potential relative to carbon dioxide coefficient (GWP) for species whose emissions result in indirect radiative forcings considering the lifetime of the pulse gas in addition to the lifetimes of the radiatively active gases causing the indirect forcing. Has been estimated the 100-year GWP of hydrogen to be 11 ± 5^7 , 100% larger than previously published calculations, coherent with the studies of the Center for International Climate Research, Oslo, Norway that founded a GWP for hydrogen of 11.6 ± 2.8^8 . This underscores the importance of managing hydrogen emissions effectively to minimize their environmental impact as hydrogen becomes a more prominent part of the energy mix.

In order to quantify the amounts of hydrogen released to the atmosphere, it is fundamental to define first the complete hydrogen supply chain, also in terms of main hydrogen emissions, as of today and in future energy transitions.

The hydrogen supply chain can be analysed through a holistic approach, focusing on the main stages from production to end-use, without delving deeply into the technical specifics of each phase. This approach allows for an overview of the entire supply chain, providing insights into how hydrogen is produced, processed, stored, transported, and utilized. Figure 1 presents a breakdown of these five main life cycle stages.

Figure 1: Life cycle stages of the hydrogen value chain and archetypes considered.

- **Production:** Hydrogen can be produced using several methods such as steam methane reforming (SMR), electrolysis, thermochemical processes and others.
- **Conversion/reconversion:** After production, hydrogen may undergo conversion into a more easily transportable or storable form. This includes processes like liquefaction or binding hydrogen into chemical carriers such as ammonia or LOHCs. Reconversion refers to the process of extracting hydrogen from these carriers when it reaches its destination. The compression

stages required for the transportation & storage of compressed hydrogen have also been considered as conversion/reconversion processes.

- **Storage:** Storing hydrogen is challenging due to its high diffusivity and low density at ambient conditions. State of the art storage solutions can take various forms, including high-pressure tanks for gaseous hydrogen, cryogenic tanks for liquid hydrogen, or chemical storage in the form of hydrogen-rich compounds.
- **Transport:** Hydrogen can be transported in its gaseous or liquid form, or by chemical compound. Transport methods include pipelines, tankers etc. depending on the characteristics of transfer by road, rails or sea.
- **Final use:** The end-use of hydrogen covers a wide range of applications, including as feedstock in various industrial processes such as refining and chemical production, a fuel for transportation, for heating and electricity generation, and future further uses.

2. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this deliverable is to establish characteristic blocks, defined as archetypes, applicable across all possible supply chain configurations. These blocks have been defined in such a way that they enable the straightforward implementation of various supply chains, from production to end-uses. This approach allows the investigation of any scenario analysed in subsequent Work Packages (WP4), ensuring compatibility among the blocks without issues. Furthermore, it attempts to balance between specific characteristics or specifications of certain plant configurations, making possible to pinpoint macro-blocks that are frequently repeated across different specific plant configurations and value chains.

2.1. Operational Parameters

In defining the archetypes for each technology, it is crucial to consider the main parameters that might influence an hydrogen emission, including for example its amount and temporal pattern. These could be, for example, operative (i.e., referred to process conditions), and technological (i.e., depending on the specific configuration of the equipment through which an emission could occur). Where applicable and compatible with the application type, factors to consider include, for example:

- Operating pressure
- Operating temperature
- Specific volumes of hydrogen processed (flow rates or capacities)
- Hydrogen purity (for any required treatments)
- Equivalent operating hours
- Lifespan -> component degradation
- Dynamic procedures (as start-up and shut down etc...)

Any other parameters that could influence the magnitude of the release for specific archetypes have also been considered to ensure an accurate estimation for scenarios' analysis. These characteristics are essential for defining the distinctive parameters of the different archetypes that will be used to build different supply chains. Simultaneously, the main sources of hydrogen emissions are indicated. Due to current progress of the NHyRA project, only a qualitative assessment of the main expected emission in the defined archetypes is provided. Connected to the Task 1.1, Task 1.2 will define the structure of the dataset of the hydrogen emissions based on the input received. Specifically, the preliminary version of the dataset will include available information.

2.2. Categorization of H₂ Emissions

Three main categories of H₂ emissions are assumed. The categorization was selected in accordance with natural gas sector commonly accepted procedure as reported in the document entitled "*Assessment of methane emissions for gas Transmission and Distribution system operators*", published by MARCOGAZ³:

- Fugitives:
 - Leaks due to connections / loss of tightness: leaks typically due to gradual changes in conditions like leaks of flanges, seals, joints, valve seats, etc.
 - Permeation as through wall material or subsurface emissions from a storage reservoir to the atmosphere
- Vented:
 - Operations:
 - Purging / venting for works, process, commissioning, and decommissioning, including work, maintenance, and renewal.
 - Regular emissions of devices: pneumatic emission actuators, flow control valves, measurement equipment, compressors, seals
 - Starts & stops emissions from the start and stops of equipment
 - Overpressure events: releases of hydrogen due to unexpected overpressure conditions due to anomalies in the process, like those from safety valves, bursting disk.
 - Incidents:
 - Leaks due to unexpected changes in conditions, due to third party damage, construction defect/material failure, ground movement.
 - Operational errors
 - Other incidents
- Incomplete combustion: Unburned hydrogen in exhaust gases from combustion devices

For emissions associated with technologies not yet industrially treated or hard to define, general assumptions can be made:

- i) through risk evaluation methodologies like HAZOP, FMEA, and bow-tie analysis
- ii) by adhering to technical Directives such as PED, ATEX, NFPA 2
- iii) by applying relevant technical standards included in ISO, ANSI, EN, API, etc.

3. TYPICAL BOP ELEMENTS

Many of the archetypes include typical components essential for the internal movement, regulation, and treatment of hydrogen within the system. Even though this level of detail will not be selected for scenario analysis in WP4, it could be a guideline for the analysis of specific archetypes' mitigation strategies. To avoid unnecessary repetition in each technology where these components are present, we will analyse these recurring elements separately, a preliminary list of the main elements is reported in the next sections.

3.1. Balance of Plant Process Elements

The balance of plant includes all components related to the convey of hydrogen gases within the specific plant, such as pipes, flanges, and various types of valves described below.

3.1.1. Pipes

Pipes are crucial for transporting hydrogen gas within the plant. Selecting the appropriate material for these pipes is fundamental to prevent hydrogen embrittlement and ensure safe operation.

The main used materials are summarized Table 2 below, based on the ASME B31.12-2023 standards for hydrogen pipes⁷ and studies of material for liquified hydrogen transportation and storage⁹:

Table 2: Pipelines' material composition related to hydrogen compatibility.

Material	Description
Carbon Steel	ASTM A53 Grade B, ASTM A106 Grade B, and API 5L Grades X52, X42, and micro-alloyed X52 used for gaseous hydrogen
Aluminium-Based Alloys	Suitable for both gas and liquid hydrogen
Austenitic Stainless Steel	Alloys with greater than 8 wt% nickel in solution annealed condition are suitable for both gas and liquid hydrogen
Low-Alloy Carbon Steels	Suitable for gaseous hydrogen but not for liquid hydrogen due to cryogenic temperature embrittlement
Nickel-Based Alloys	Suitable for liquid hydrogen; usable in gaseous hydrogen depending on strength and alloy composition
Titanium-Based Alloys	Should not be used for gaseous hydrogen due to titanium hydride formation but are acceptable for liquid hydrogen

The main hydrogen emissions are fugitives' ones related to:

- **Permeation:** Hydrogen atoms can permeate through the pipe walls, especially at high pressures and temperatures. The rate of permeation depends on the material and wall thickness.
- **Leaks:** Can occur at connection points or due to material defects.

3.1.2. Flanges

Used for connecting sections of piping or attach pipes to other components, similar to pipes are usually made from stainless steel or carbon steel.

The main hydrogen emissions are fugitives' ones related to:

- **Leaks:** Mainly occur at the gasket interface due to improper sealing, thermal cycling, or mechanical stress.

3.1.3. Valves

Manual and control valves are usually present in mechanical industrial plants. Control valves enable flow stream operative conditions, including operative pressure and flow rate. Various types of valves can be installed in hydrogen systems including for example:

Safety Pressure Relief Valves and Thermal Pressure Relief Device (PRVs and TPRDs): multiple lines valves that automatically release pressure from the system when it exceeds a pre-set limit to prevent overpressure scenarios venting the gas or when temperature in gas fluid exceed pre-set temperature to avoid explosions.

- The main hydrogen emissions are vented ones related to overpressure events, where hydrogen is vented to the atmosphere.

Pressure Regulation Valves: Includes back pressure valves, control valves, and pressure reducing valves. They allow to maintain desired pressure levels within the system.

- The main hydrogen emissions are vented ones related to occasional venting during maintenance or pressure adjustments.

Flow control Valves: Modulate the flow of hydrogen to maintain a parameter at the desired set point.

- The main hydrogen losses are fugitives' ones related to valve seats or stem seals leaks.

Blow-Down Valves: Used to depressurize sections of the system for maintenance or in emergency scenarios.

- The main hydrogen emissions are vented ones related to hydrogen venting during blow-down operations.

For all the defined types of valves, fugitive emissions of hydrogen can occur at seals and connections

3.2. Hydrogen Treatment Unit

This section covers the primary hydrogen treatment units commonly used throughout the hydrogen supply chain. These units are essential after hydrogen production (e.g., from steam methane reforming or coal gasification) and before final usage, such as in hydrogen refuelling stations when the delivered hydrogen does not meet the ultrapure requirements for fuel cell vehicles.

Evaluating the purity requirements for different applications, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) introduced the ISO 14687-2:2012 standard in 2012, setting requirements for hydrogen quality specifically for Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFCs). In 2015, the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) released the SAE J2719-201511 standard, which aligns with the ISO requirements. With advancements in PEMFC technology, such as reduced platinum usage, thinner electrolyte membranes, and higher operating current densities, it became necessary to revisit the impurity limits in hydrogen. Consequently, in November 2019, the ISO technical committee for hydrogen energy (ISO/TC 197) released the ISO 14687:2019 standard, which combined and revised three previous standards (ISO 14687-1, ISO 14687-2, and ISO 14687-3). Following this, in March 2020 the SAE updated its standard to SAE J2719-202003, which considers the limits for impurities like water (H₂O), total hydrocarbons (HC), oxygen (O₂), and others, as reported in Table 3.

Table 3 quality standards for PEMFC applications

Component	ISO 14687-2:2012 SAE J2719-201511	ISO 14687:2019 SAE J2719:202003
H ₂ purity (% mole)	99.97%	99.97%
Tot non H ₂ gases	300 ppm	300 ppm
H ₂ O	5 ppm	5 ppm
Tot HC	2 ppm	-
Non-methane HC	-	2 ppm
CH ₄	-	100 pp
O ₂	5 ppm	5 ppm
He	300 ppm	300 ppm
N ₂ and Ar	100 pp	-
N ₂	-	300 ppm
Ar	-	300 ppm
CO ₂	2 ppm	2 ppm
CO	0.2 ppm	0.2 ppm
S	0.004 ppm	0.004 ppm
HCHO	0.01 ppm	0.2 ppm
HCOOH	0.2 ppm	0.2 ppm
NH ₃	0.1 ppm	0.1 ppm
Tot halide	0.05 ppm	0.05 ppm
Max pm	1 mg/kg	1 mg/kg

To meet these stringent hydrogen quality standards, especially for ultrapure hydrogen in PEM fuel cell applications, a series of purification processes are necessary. These purification methods can be broadly categorized into physical and chemical methods. Among the physical ones:

- Adsorption methods: Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA), Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA)
- Low-temperature separation methods: Cryogenic distillation and low-temperature adsorption.
- Membrane separation methods: Both inorganic and organic membranes.

The choice of an appropriate hydrogen purification method depends on the hydrogen supply mode and gas source. For large-scale hydrogen production ($\geq 10,000 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$)¹⁰ from centralized coal gasification or natural gas reforming, PSA purification is commonly used after transformation, desulfurization, and decarbonization. PSA is favored for its low operational costs and long service life. However, traditional PSA may struggle to achieve the required purity levels for fuel cell vehicles, particularly for stringent impurity limits (e.g., $\text{CO} \leq 0.2 \text{ ppm}$). Cryogenic distillation can also be used for large-scale production but typically produces hydrogen with 85–99% purity, which may not meet all application requirements.

For medium-scale production ($1000\text{--}10,000 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$)¹⁰, a combination of processes is often employed to enhance hydrogen recovery efficiency. For instance, an organic membrane combined with PSA is used for methanol purge gas, while multi-stage PSA processes are suitable for coke oven gas and refinery by-product gas.

In small-scale on-site production scenarios ($\leq 1000 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$)¹⁰, traditional PSA can be less suitable due to its large footprint and limited flexibility. Alternative methods like low-temperature adsorption, metal hydride, and metal membrane separations are better suited. Low-temperature adsorption can effectively remove multiple impurities, such as sulfides, HCHO, and HCOOH, but it requires high energy consumption and is complex, making it more suitable for specialized small-scale applications¹⁰.

These widely used technologies are detailed in the following, focusing on the main operational parameters and main hydrogen losses.

3.1.4. *Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA)*

Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is a widely used method for gas separation and purification. The PSA process exploits the different adsorption capacities of gases on solid adsorbents under varying pressure conditions. Common adsorbents used in PSA include zeolite molecular sieves, activated carbon, activated alumina, and silica gel. PSA operates around ambient temperature and a pressure range of 1-40 bar^{11,12}

The most common PSA system is multicolumn, ranging from 2 bed configurations up to tens of beds in parallel. Each column undergoes absorption at high pressures of the crude gasses from the beds, depressurization phases in which treated hydrogen exit the bed and pressurize the following one, purge of pure hydrogen to purify the absorption bed and a new pressurization of the bed to repeat the process¹¹.

In Figure 2, a general configuration of a 4 columns PSA process made of absorption beds, storage tanks and valves to regulate the different pressurization and depressurization phases is shown.

Figure 2: Flow diagram of a multiple step PSA process¹¹

Hydrogen losses in PSA primarily occur during the counter current purge process, where the adsorber is purged with a pure hydrogen gas stream to desorb impurities at a lower pressure. The effluent gas from this step contains the remaining impurities and is typically used as a thermal source. Commercial PSA systems generally achieve a hydrogen recovery rate of 75-99%, depending on the quality of the feed hydrogen^{10,11}.

3.1.5. Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA)

Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA) operates similarly to PSA but relies on temperature variations to regenerate the adsorbent. The process involves adsorbing impurities at a lower temperature and desorbing them at a higher temperature being able to handle gas mixtures with high concentrations of impurities such as carbon dioxide or water, which may degrade the adsorbent performance in other swing absorption methods. For this reason, typically cycles between ambient and elevated temperatures (up to 200°C) in the 1-10 bar range¹².

Hydrogen losses in TSA can occur during the heating phase when the adsorbed impurities are desorbed and vented along with some hydrogen. The extent of hydrogen loss depends on the efficiency of the heating cycle and the type of adsorbent used.

3.1.6. Cryogenic Distillation

Cryogenic distillation separates gases based on their boiling points by cooling the gas mixture to very low temperatures and selectively condensing components. It is commonly used for large-scale hydrogen production where high purity is required. Temperature range of -150°C to -196°C and 1-5 bar pressure range are typical. This process is mainly used to separate light hydrocarbons and CO from hydrogen, with preliminary treatments for CO₂ and H₂O separation. In modern processes this drying is done almost always

with adsorption, where the adsorber beds are thermally regenerated with heated gas. High hydrogen purities and good recovery rates (90-95%) can only be achieved if the outgoing gas has low pressures (0.07 MPa)¹³.

Figure 3 shows a general flowchart of a cryogenic condensation process with the main plant elements¹⁴.

Figure 3: Cryogenic condensation process¹³

Hydrogen losses in cryogenic distillation are minimal but can occur due to leaks in the cryogenic system or during the depressurization phases.

3.1.7. Membrane Separation

Membrane separation methods use selective barriers (membranes) to separate hydrogen from other gases. These membranes can be metallic, polymeric, or ceramic. Membrane processes are often integrated with other purification methods to enhance overall efficiency as PSA, polymeric and MOF (Metal Organic Framework) membranes operate in the 20-80°C¹⁵ temperature range, while metallic ones up to 500 °C. The pressure range is 5-20 bar¹⁶. Membrane separation systems generally have low hydrogen losses, as the process involves the selective permeation of hydrogen through the membrane. However, some losses can occur due to imperfections in the membrane or during the purge cycles.

Summarizing all the main hydrogen treatment methods presented above, the key parameters fundamental for the quantification of hydrogen releases are summarized in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Summar of Operating Conditions and Hydrogen Losses

Technology	Treated Hydrogen	Temperature Range	Pressure Range	Hydrogen Losses
PSA	>> 1000 Nm ³ /h	Ambient	1-40 bar	1-25% (primarily during purging, used as thermal source)
TSA	\\	Ambient to 200°C	1-5 bar	Variable (during heating cycle)
Cryogenic Distillation	≤1000 Nm ³ /h	-150°C to -200 °C	1-5 bar	Minimal (system leaks, depressurization)
Membrane Separation	≤1000 Nm ³ /h	20-500°C	1-30 bar	Low (imperfections, purge cycles)

3.1.8. Other pre-treatment units

Before the previously defined hydrogen treatment technologies, depending on the specific application, several pre-treatment elements can be adopted, such as desulfurization process through zinc oxide beds or activated carbon to remove sulphur compounds from hydrocarbon-based syngas -, particulate removal trough mechanical filters and drying process using desiccants such as silica gel, molecular sieves, or through cooling and condensation.

Due to the fact that the pre-treatment units are multiple and depend on the specific applications, they will not be treated in this specific chapter but in the archetypes in which they are required.

4. PRODUCTION

In 2022, global hydrogen production reached approximately 95 Mton_{H₂}, predominantly driven by fossil fuel-based technologies. Natural gas without carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) accounted for 62% of global production. Primarily in China, coal gasification contributed 21% of the total hydrogen production. By-product hydrogen, generated during processes like naphtha reforming in refineries and petrochemical industries and subsequently used in other refinery operations (e.g., hydrocracking, desulphurization), made up 16% of global production. Low-emission hydrogen production in 2022 was less than 1 Mt (0.7% of global production), remaining consistent with 2021 levels and largely sourced from fossil fuels with CCUS. Hydrogen production from water electrolysis remained relatively small, under 100 kton_{H₂} in 2022, but this represented a 35% growth compared to the previous year¹⁷.

Looking forward, low-emission technologies are projected to significantly increase hydrogen production, potentially reaching up to 20 Mt by 2030. This growth will be primarily driven by systems based on fossil fuels with CCUS and water electrolysis, with water electrolysis expected to contribute to 70% of this production^{4,18}.

In this work hydrogen production will be divided into four main categories, mainly defined by the energy source used as input for the production of hydrogen itself:

- **Hydrocarbons:** the most used production technologies from fossil fuels, that are steam methane reforming (SMR), coal gasification and heavy fuel cracking (byproduct) with and without considering the adoption of CCUS
- **Water electrolysis:** Alkaline (ALK), Proton Exchange membrane (PEM), anionic exchange membrane (AEM), Solid oxide (SOEC) electrolyzers.
- **Biomass & Biowaste Gasification:** similarly to coal gasification, organic materials (e.g. wood chips or agricultural residues) into synthetic gas (syngas) to produce hydrogen through natural resources.
- **Others:** Photo electrocatalytic hydrogen production, thermochemical water splitting using nuclear energy/concentrated light.

4.1. Hydrocarbons

In thermal processes, heat is used to break down hydrogen-containing organic materials, such as fossil fuels, into smaller molecules, thereby producing hydrogen and other byproducts. These processes include steam methane reforming (SMR), partial oxidation of methane (POM), coal gasification (CG), auto-thermal reforming of methane (ATR), natural gas pyrolysis (NGP), dry reforming of methane (DRM), and hydrogen production as a byproduct of heavy fuel cracking.

Due to the current market dominance of SMR, CG, and heavy fuel cracking, and the anticipated future dominance of water electrolysis-based technologies in hydrogen production, this section will focus on the these three main hydrogen production technologies from fossil fuels¹⁹.

4.1.1. Steam Methane Reforming

Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) is the most prevalent method for hydrogen production. The complete process involves the conversion of natural gas (primarily methane) into hydrogen and carbon monoxide, followed by a water-gas shift reaction to convert the carbon monoxide into carbon dioxide and additional hydrogen.

The process requires a temperature range from 700°C to 1000°C and a pressure between 3 and 25 bar, depending on the specific technology. To promote the conversion process and simplify hydrocarbon transformation, a catalytic bed is installed inside the reactor. Three main reactions take place during the process: Steam Methane Reforming, Dry Steam Reforming (reaction between methane and carbon dioxide to form carbon monoxide and hydrogen), and Water-Gas Shift (CO reacts with water to produce CO₂ and hydrogen). The widespread use of SMR is attributed to its well-established technology and relatively lower costs compared to other hydrogen production methods.

Among the technologies for hydrogen and syngas production, the tubular flame reactor is the most common. Inside this type of reactor, endothermic reaction activation is powered by radiation heat from combustion. The reactor consists of a combustion chamber crossed by reaction tubes filled with catalyst, where the reactions take place. Natural gas and air burn inside the combustion chamber to generate heat and provide the necessary energy through radiation phenomena. This technology is competitive for plant capacities up to about 250,000 Nm³ of H₂ produced per hour²⁰. Reactor configurations may vary depending on how burners and reaction tubes are arranged inside the reactor drum. Common configurations include the "bottom fire configuration" with co-current heat exchange, the "top fire configuration" with counter-current heat exchange, and the "side-fired configuration" where burners are mounted along the reactor length, as shown in Figure 4. Reactor temperature is set to around 870-920°C to maintain high methane conversion rates²⁰.

To withstand high temperatures and pressures, reactor pipes are made of alloy metals such as HP 25/35 Ni-Cr, which resist thermal stress (up to 1000°C) and mechanical stress (30 barg)²¹.

Figure 4: Adiabatic pre-reformer and fired tubular reformer for hydrogen production plant²⁰.

Inside the reactor, there are up to one thousand steel tubes ranging from 10 to 14 meters in length. Depending on the temperature and operating pressure, the tubes vary in diameter and thickness to optimize strength and cost, typically ranging from 100-180 mm in diameter and 8-20 mm in thickness. Reactor components are designed to have a minimum lifespan of about 100,000 hours before requiring replacement or repair due to degradation²².

The archetype considered for this technology will be defined by:

- **The Natural Gas treatment unit:** The natural gas is pretreated through hydrogenation that converts sulphur compounds to H₂S, which is then removed in a ZnO bed. During the hydrogenation of sulphur it's used a small amount of hydrogen, which is recycled from the product stream²³.
- **Methane conversion process:** Made of the catalytic steam reforming and high and low temperature water gas shifting reactions where more than 90% of CO is converted in CO₂ and H₂. The reformer is fuelled primarily by the PSA off-gas, but a small amount of natural gas (usually under 10 wt% of the total reformer fuel requirement) is used.
- **Hydrogen treatment unit:** May consist exclusively of PSA (Pressure Swing Adsorption) or PSA combined with CCUS (Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage).

Figure 5: Archetype of the SMR based hydrogen production plant.

Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) Detail

CCUS (Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage) technology is set to play a crucial role in reducing the environmental impact of fossil fuel-based hydrogen production. So, necessitates an examination of this specific plant element.

Refrigerated methyl diethanolamine (MDEA) is typically employed for pre-combustion CO₂ capture in reforming-based hydrogen production processes. In this system, CO₂ is removed from the syngas stream before it reaches the PSA unit through chemical absorption using a highly selective, hybrid amine²⁴.

The process can be summarized in:

- Absorption step in which particulate-free syngas from the shift reactors is passed through an amine tower where it is contacted counter-currently with a circulating stream of lean aqueous amine solution; the H₂ rich treated gas is sent then to PSA unit.
- Regeneration in which the rich amine from the absorber is sent to a stripper column where the amine is regenerated using a steam reboiler to remove the CO₂ through fractionation
- CO₂ compression step in which the regenerated CO₂ stream is compressed for further uses.

Due to the lack of complete state of the art studies, operational parameters from an assessment of FOSSIL-BASED HYDROGEN PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES from NETL¹⁹ has been considered , with specific study cases reflecting the commercial technologies within plant configurations. Precisely the MDEA whole process operates in the 20 - 50 °C temperature range, an inlet absorber pressure for the syngas in the 20-30 bar range, and an outlet pressure in the 1-2 bar range for the regenerated CO₂.

Figure 6: MDEA CO₂ capture process typical flow diagram¹⁹

Evaluating possible hydrogen emissions, the CO₂-rich solution (acid gas) also carries some impurities (i.e. CO, CH₄, N₂ and some residual H₂), for this reason it is expanded in a flash drum. As a result, the inert impurities are released in the gas phase and recycled back to the absorber feed, without major H₂ losses²⁴.

Considering the complete SMR archetype, the main technical parameters that will be considered for the description of the archetype are:

Table 5: Technical parameters for archetype description.

Parameters	Value
Temperature [°C]	700-1000
Pressure [bar]	3-25
H ₂ Production [ton _{H₂} /h]	10-30
Plant lifetime [<i>h_{eq}</i>]	Up to 100'000
Pipe Info	Alloy metals (ex. HP 25/35 Ni-Cr) diameter of 100-180 mm, thickness of 8-20 mm
CCUS technology	
Temperature [°C]	20-50
Pressure [bar]	20-30 (Syngas) 1-2 (CO ₂)

Evaluating the main hydrogen releases for the SMR general archetype, it is important to highlight that usually these types of plants are equipped with a warm flare. Thus, planned as well as emergency depressurizations and seal gases from all the auxiliary elements (e.g. Compressors) are routed to flare. It remains still unburnt H₂ in the flare and potential leakages from flanges and instrumentation. Even so, the main elements or specific events related to hydrogen release will be introduced:

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Leaks in Pipes, Flanges, or Other Equipment:** Occasional equipment failures, operational errors (faulty components, corrosion, improper maintenance, or accidental damage). Further details of the losses are detailed in the "Balance of Plant Process Elements" paragraph

Vented hydrogen releases are mainly related to:

- **Safety Valves:** Overpressure events related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area. The total released mass depends on the frequency and duration of discharge, these specific elements have been detailed in the "Valves" subparagraph of "Balance of Plant Process Elements".
- **Purging and Venting:** Related to Maintenance and operational procedures for all the hydrogen lines and storage.
- **H₂ treatment unit losses:** In systems with PSA, some dry hydrogen is used to dry the inactive desiccant bed, which is then used as thermal source for the burners or vented off to the atmosphere. The details of the specific procedure are contained in the "Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA)" paragraph.

Unburned hydrogen releases are mainly related to:

- **Off-gasses unburned:** in SMR plants off-gasses containing hydrogen residues are usually burned for thermal energy purposes, minimum quantities of hydrogen could remain unburned.

4.1.2. Coal Gasification

Coal-based hydrogen production has been applied over several decades before other fossil-based resources and, given current state of technology and worldwide coal reserves, coal is still an economical and technically practical option to produce hydrogen in large scale plants, especially when the cost of natural gas is high (IJHE 45 (2020) 26022-35). According to the IEA Future of Hydrogen report⁵, around 20 % of global hydrogen is produced from coal, with essentially no CCUS. Coal gasification process converts the solid coal into synthetic gas (syngas) in the presence of oxidizing agents, usually O₂ and/or steam at temperatures between 500 and 1400°C²⁵. The syngas, a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide from which hydrogen can be extracted, is sent through a shift reactor in order increase the hydrogen yield.

From NTEL studies, the median production rates of Coal Gasification based H₂ production plants stands in the 4-10 ton_{H₂}/h¹⁹.

The main elements of the coal gasification process are shown in the following flow chart in Figure 7 and described below:

Figure 7: Main elements of coal gasification process.

- **Coal Gasification Unit (C.G.):** the pretreated oxygen and steam are sent to the CG unit where solid (pulverized) coal is partially oxidized at high-temperature (up to 1800°C) and pressure to produce syngas mainly H₂, CO, mixed with steam and CO₂ according to the simplified reaction:

Small amounts of other gases and particles are also produced in the reaction.

- **Syngas Cleaning/Cooling:** The resulting syngas, mainly consisting of H₂, CO, CO₂, H₂O, and various impurities, needs to be cleaned to remove particulate matter and sulphur compounds, which may damage catalysts or other equipment downstream through an initial wet scrubbing phase²⁶. The syngas temperature must be cooled down due to the negative enthalpy reaction of the shift reaction ($\Delta H = -41$ kJ/mol).
- **Water-Gas Shift Reactor (WGS):** to increase the hydrogen production yield, the syngas generated in the CG is sent to the high and low temperature WGS reactor where the following reaction takes place:

- **H₂ treatment unit:** H₂ must be separated by CH₄, CO₂, and other impurities as H₂S. The syngas is subjected to the acid gas removal process where H₂S and CO₂ are removed from it with two stages. Finally Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is utilized, where differences in gas molecule adsorption

on surfaces under varying pressures is used to purify hydrogen, or through Membrane Separation, using selective membranes that allow only hydrogen molecules to pass through.

- **Plant Power Unit:** After the PSA unit, the purge syngas is sent to the combustor to produce power. Steam Rankine cycle, organic Rankine cycle and system turbine are used for the power production unit of coal gasification plants²⁷.

The main operational parameters and information required for the characterization of the state-of-the-art coal gasification process are:

Table 6: Main operational parameters for characterization of state-of-the-art coal gasification process.

Parameters	Description
H₂ Production [ton_{H₂]/h]}	4-10
Coal Gasification reactor: Coal reacts with O ₂ and Steam to produce the syngas	
Temperature [°C]	Up to 1800
Pressure [bar]	200-400
Clean/cooling: The reaction must be cooled down due to the negative enthalpy of formation ($\Delta H = -41$ kJ/mol). Depending on the plant this is achieved via metal tubes, water or the gas expansion.	
Shift reactor: The syngas undergoes the shift reaction in order to increase the hydrogen production yield	
Temperature [°C]	300-500
Pressure [bar]	10-100
H₂ Treatment Unit: The syngas is purified through processes such as Pressure Swing Adsorption or Membrane separation	
Plant lifetime [years]	40
H₂ Purity [%]	> 99

CCUS Detail

From the FOSSIL-BASED HYDROGEN PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES from NETL assessment¹⁹, the Acid Gas Removal (AGR) process in coal gasification is essential for removing hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) from syngas. Among the various AGR processes, Selexol and methyl diethanolamine (MDEA) are commonly used. The choice of process depends on the desired selectivity for H₂S and CO₂. H₂S is removed in the first stage and CO₂ in the second stage of absorption. Then the regeneration phases allow to separate the desired gasses.

The amount of H₂ recovered by the syngas, depending on the specific Selexol process and design, can achieve the 99.5% of recovery rate, so are not expected important hydrogen losses during this final treatment process.

Evaluating the main hydrogen releases/emissions of the coal gasification technology, only general losses have been introduced due to the lack of available information. It is important to highlight that, as for the

SMR technology, also these types of plant are usually equipped with a warm flare; thus, planned as well as emergency depressurization and seal gases from all the auxiliary elements (e.g. Compressors) are routed to flare or the purged gas is used as partial energy supply for the plant. It remains still unburnt H₂ in the flare and potential leakages from flanges and instrumentation. Even so, the main elements or specific events related to hydrogen release will be introduced:

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Leaks in Pipes, Flanges, or Other Equipment:** Occasional equipment failures, operational errors (faulty components, corrosion, improper maintenance, or accidental damage). Further details of the losses are detailed in the "Balance of Plant Process Elements" paragraph

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Safety Valves:** Overpressure events related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area. The total released mass depends on the frequency and duration of discharge, these specific elements have been detailed in the "Valves" subparagraph of "Balance of Plant Process Elements".
- **H₂ treatment unit losses:** In systems with PSA, some dry hydrogen is used to dry the inactive desiccant bed, which is then used as thermal source for the burners or vented off to the atmosphere. The details of the specific procedure are contained in the "Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA)" paragraph.
- **Purging and Venting:** Related to Maintenance and operational procedures for all the hydrogen lines and storage.

Unburned hydrogen releases are mainly related to:

- **Off-gasses unburned:** in CG plants off-gasses containing hydrogen residues are usually burned for thermal or electric energy purposes, minimum quantities of hydrogen could remain unburned.

4.1.3. Byproduct of heavy fuel cracking

Byproduct of heavy fuel cracking represents a cost-effective way to utilize waste materials for hydrogen production²⁸. It refers to the breakdown of heavier (long-chain) hydrocarbon molecules found in crude oil or residual fuel oils and leftover byproducts from industrial processes, such as gasification or petrochemical. The process usually involves high temperatures and catalysts to facilitate the conversion of byproducts and heavy hydrocarbons into hydrogen and other valuable products. The main elements of these processes are shown in the following flow chart and described below:

Figure 8: Main elements of byproduct of heavy fuel cracking plant.

- **Heavy Fuel Cracking Unit:** The cracking of heavy fuel oil through thermal or catalytic methods produces lighter hydrocarbons (gasoline, diesel) and a byproduct stream rich in hydrogen (contains hydrogen, hydrocarbons, and other gases).
- **Byproduct Gas Separation Unit:** The hydrogen-rich fraction is separated through techniques such as distillation and absorption. Hydrogen-rich gas goes to the purifying unit while other hydrocarbons can be recycled to cracking unit or used elsewhere.
- **H₂ Treatment Unit:** Depending on desired purity, additional steps like pressure swing adsorption (PSA) or membrane separation may be needed to remove remaining impurities, coupled with eventual acid gas removal unit as described for the previous hydrocarbon-based technologies (e.g., CO, CO₂, hydrocarbons).

The main operational parameters and information required for the characterization of the state of the art of the byproduct of hydrogen by heavy fuels cracking process are:

Table 7: Main operational parameters for characterization of hydrogen byproduct by heavy fuels cracking process.

Parameters	Description
Biomass Gasification reactor: The cracking of heavy fuel oil through thermal or catalytic methods produces a byproduct stream rich in hydrogen	
Temperature [°C]	400-800 (depending on the type of biomass)

Pressure [bar]	1-100
Clean/cooling: The reaction must be cooled down due to the negative enthalpy of formation ($\Delta H = -41$ kJ/mol). Depending on the plant this is achieved via metal tubes, water or the gas expansion.	
Gas separation unit: the hydrogen-rich fraction is separated through techniques such as distillation and absorption.	
Purifying Unit: The syngas is purified through processes such as Pressure Swing Adsorption or Membrane separation	
Plant lifetime [years]	40
H₂ Purity [%]	> 99

Evaluating the main hydrogen releases/emissions of the byproduct of hydrogen by heavy fuels cracking process have been introduced only general losses due to the lack of information available:

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Leaks in Pipes, Flanges, or Other Equipment:** Occasional equipment failures, operational errors (faulty components, corrosion, improper maintenance, or accidental damage). Further details of the losses are detailed in the "Balance of Plant Process Elements" paragraph.

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Safety Valves:** Safety valves release hydrogen to prevent overpressure in equipment. Related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area, fluid characteristics. Theoretical calculations for flowrate can be made using ISO 4126-1 and 4126-2 or IEC 60179-10 can be referenced for flowrate calculation.
- **H₂ treatment unit losses:** In systems with PSA, some dry hydrogen is used to dry the inactive desiccant bed, which is then used as thermal source for the burners or vented off to the atmosphere. The details of the specific procedure are contained in the "Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA)" paragraph.
- **Purging and Venting:** Related to Maintenance and operational procedures for all the hydrogen lines and storage.

4.2. Water electrolysis

Currently, hydrogen production through electrolysis accounts for less than 80 kilotons annually. This technology is crucial for the energy transition, as the European Union aims to install 6 GW of electrolyzers by 2030 and 500 GW by 2050. The Announced Pledges Scenario (APS) predicts that by 2050, 250 Mt of H₂ will be produced globally, with 51% from electrolysis²⁹. Utilizing electricity and water, hydrogen can be produced via electrolysis, with the electrolyte type dictating the electrolyzer's technical and economic parameters. The most established electrolyzers are Proton Exchange Membrane (PEMWE) and Alkaline (AWE) water electrolyzers. Promising technologies include:

- Alkaline Water Electrolyzers (AWE)
- Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers (PEMWE)
- Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers (AEMWE)
- Solid Oxide Electrolyzer (SOC)

Each technology features unique characteristics both at cell/stack level (the core component of the electrolyzer) and in balance of plant components and layout. Since the goal of this analysis is to identify the main losses occurring in each technology, we will focus on describing for each of the four technologies the key plant components where losses may occur:

4.2.1. Alkaline electrolyzers

AWE are the most developed electrolytic technology (TRL 9)³⁰, especially for stationary applications that use continuous electrical production. Leading manufacturers include Cummins, McPhy, NEL Hydrogen, and others. AWEs operate in an alkaline environment using, mainly, concentrated potassium hydroxide (KOH) as the electrolyte. The electrochemical reactions are:

- **Cathode Reaction:** $2H_2O + 2e^- \rightarrow 2OH^- + H_2$, where water molecules are reduced to hydrogen gas and hydroxide ions.
- **Anode Reaction:** $2OH^- \rightarrow H_2O + 2e^- + \frac{1}{2}O_2$, where hydroxide ions are oxidized to regenerate water and produce oxygen gas.
- **Overall Reaction:** $H_2O \rightarrow H_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2$, illustrating the net decomposition and regeneration of water molecules.

AWEs feature large electrode areas and robust diaphragms loaded with ZrO₂ to manage gas crossover and mixing. Thicker diaphragms and spacers reduce gas intermixing but increase ohmic resistance, lowering efficiencies³¹. Advanced designs incorporate zero-gap electrodes and thinner diaphragms, enhancing performance and reliability, with lifetimes reaching 100'000 equivalent operating hours (EOH) and operating pressures up to 30 bars³². They produce hydrogen with 95.5% to 99.9% purity, though they face challenges with high power dissipation.

In terms of performance, AWEs exhibit a current density in the order of 0.2-0.8 A/cm² with cell voltages ranging from 1.8 to 2.4 V, operating in a temperature range of 60 to 80 °C. State-of-the-art systems achieve electric specific plant consumptions in the 46-54 kWh_{el}/kg_{H₂} range³²⁻³⁴. De Nora, a

manufacturer of Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA), claims to achieve current densities of up to 1.5 A/cm² with voltages of 2 V using innovative catalysts and production processes⁵.

Figure 9: Generic PFD of an alkaline system.

As it can be seen from the generalized process flow diagram (PFD) of an AWE plant in Figure 9, operational specifics of AWEs include electrolyte recirculation through the stack, which introduces a pressure drop typically consuming less than 0.1% of stack power for pumping. However, in some configurations electrolyzers operate without pumping peripherals. The alkaline solution is separated from gases in gas-water separators located above the stack, allowing KOH/water to flow back into the stack, supporting efficient resource management. Effective water management is essential to regulate the filling level of each gas separator, with a mixing pipe installed between the anode and cathode separators to balance hydroxyl ion charges.

4.2.2. PEM electrolyzer

PEMWEs are commercially available but have reached a lower stage of industrialization than alkaline electrolyzers (TRL 8)³⁰. Major manufacturers include Plug Power, ITM Power, NEL Hydrogen, Siemens and Cummins.

The fundamental electrochemical reactions in these systems are:

- **Cathode Reaction:** $2H^+ + 2e^- \rightarrow H_2$, where is generated water.
- **Anode Reaction:** $H_2O \rightarrow 2H^+ + 2e^- + \frac{1}{2}O_2$, where hydrogen is oxidized to generate the H^+ ions that are the moving ions for PEM technology.
- **Overall Reaction:** $H_2O \rightarrow H_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2$, illustrating the net decomposition and regeneration of water molecules.

PEMWEs use a solid electrolyte, i.e. a polymer membrane, generally made of nafion with thicknesses ranging from 20 to 500 μm . Limited thicknesses and high conductivity allow PEM electrolyzers to operate at higher current density, and the solid electrolyte allows to obtain high differential pressures between

the anode and cathode sides, with the possibility of obtaining hydrogen already compressed, thus reducing the overall Capex. Some companies claim the possibility of reaching pressures of up to 350 bar, while values between atmospheric pressure and up to 30 bar are frequent. PEM electrolyzers operate at higher current densities than alkaline electrolyzers, reaching values over $2\text{--}3\text{ A/cm}^2$. The low cross-over rate of hydrogen through the electrolyte membrane allows for a wide operating range, about 10-100% of the nominal power. Maintaining moderate electric specific plant consumptions in the $49\text{--}56\text{ kWh}_{el}/\text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}$ range^{5,32,33}.

Figure 10: Generic PFD of a PEM system.

Regarding the main BOP components, as it can be seen from the generalized PEM system PFD in Figure 10, they typically require circulation pumps, heat exchangers, and pressure control valves (back pressure valves) at the anode (oxygen) side. At the cathode side, a gas separator, a de-oxygenation component to remove residual oxygen (typically not required for differential pressure), a gas dryer, and a final compressor step are necessary with the pressure control valves (back pressure) and monitoring.

They can operate at a differential pressure between anode and cathode (with cathode at higher pressure); for this reason, we will consider the cathode side pressure as the operating pressure for quantifying hydrogen losses.

Due to the absence of alkaline electrolyte, the separation stages and final purity of the hydrogen produced by PEM are better, requiring fewer exit treatments, though all components related to hydrogen treatment as previously described remain present.

4.2.3. AEM electrolyzers

AEMWE can combine the advantages of AWE and PEMWE³⁵. Like alkaline water electrolysis, electrodes in AEMWE operate in an alkaline environment, which allows non-noble, low-cost catalysts (differently from PEMWEs, which use expensive platinum-group metals (PGMs) such as platinum, iridium, as a catalyst). Similarly to the PEMWEs, AWEs use a membrane as electrolyte, limiting issues related to bubble effect and gas crossover, characteristic of traditional alkaline electrolyzers. As in the traditional alkaline water

electrolysers, water reduction takes place in the cathode, exploiting the same partial reactions at the two poles. The general plant configuration of an AEMWE system is similar to the PEMWE one, presented in the Figure 10.

4.2.4. Solid Oxide electrolyzers

In alternative to low temperatures electrolysis processes, SOEs work at high temperatures, 700-1000 °C. Thus, they can be coupled with high temperatures processes. The high temperature allows the use of relatively cheap nickel electrodes³⁶. Additionally, the electricity demand decreases and part of the energy for separation is provided through heat. SOEs is today only deployed at the kW-scale, although some current demonstration projects have already reached 1 MW sizes.

From a thermodynamic perspective, it is advantageous to operate with high temperature steam to lower the electricity consumption. For instance, with steam at 1000 K the ideal consumption is reduced to 2.4 kWh_{el}/Nm^3 , compared to 3 kWh_{el}/Nm^3 at room temperature³⁷. In this case, the steam feeding the SOE is assumed to be produced without using electricity, otherwise the gain is nearly cancelled.

Generally, state of the art systems, operate in the 700-850 °C temperature range, at atmospheric pressure reaching system electrical consumption in the 40-50 kWh_{el}/kg_{H_2} range³⁴.

The main elements of a SOE plant are different compared to the low temperature technologies, precisely:

- Recuperator (Low temperature heat exchanger): are required to produce saturated steam from feed water at low temperature (<200°C) using the hot steams leaving the stack. Additionally, low temperature recuperator can be used, and an electric boiler can be required to evaporate the pre-heated water.
- High temperature preheater: steam is superheated also with air to ensure the high inlet temperatures.
- Recycle section: A mix of steam and recycled hydrogen (up to 20%) is used to maintain reducing conditions. For the mixing of recycled hydrogen, an additional line is required, delivering hydrogen at the specific operating pressure trough a compression line.

Figure 11: Generic PFD of a SOEC system³⁸

For the definition of the relevant archetype, it has been decided to include only the main plant components, as the primary losses occur at the stack and the hydrogen treatment line. Specifically, the main plant components considered are:

- **Water Treatment unit (H₂O Tr):** Involves H₂O ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis (RO), and electro-deionization (EDI) to ensure high-quality water for the electrolysis process (very high purity are needed in low temperature systems, while high temperature systems have less stringent purity requirements).
- **Electrolysis Stack:** here the specific water electrolysis reaction occurs.
- **Hydrogen treatment unit (H₂ Treat):** Includes chillers, scrubber for particulates and KOH removal (for AWE), deoxygenation unit based on catalytic purification Pd based technologies, and dryer. To ensure higher purity rates for as for PEM FC utilization further purification steps are needed, these technologies have been already evaluated in the “Hydrogen Treatment Unit” paragraph.
- **Balance of Plant (BOP):** Features SCADA (with all electric units), water pumps, heat exchangers (including recuperators and evaporators in high temperature SOE), gas-water separators, back pressure valves, safety valves and hydrogen compressors to support the overall operation of the system.

The simplified scheme of the main elements reported above provides a clear overview of the components critical in minimizing losses and optimizing hydrogen production efficiency:

Figure 12: General Archetype for Electrolysis technology.

Depending on the application, a hydrogen compression unit may be required (e.g., in energy storage applications with compressed hydrogen stored in vessels or large seasonal underground storage facilities). However, the compression unit is generally outside the electrolyzer battery limits.

Summing up the key operational parameters of the evaluated technologies in this chapter in the Table 8 form different sectorial studies^{5,33,34,36,39}.

Table 8: key parameters of the main electrolysis technologies

Parameters	AWE	PEMWE	AEMWE	SOE
TRL	7-9	7-9	3-5	5-6
Nominal Capacity [MW]	>100 (at 2050)	>100 (at 2050)	<100	<100
Temperature [°C]	65 - 100	70 - 90	50-70	650 – 1000
Pressure [bar]	2 - 10	15 - 30	<35	<30
Lifetime [h_{eq}]	<90000	<40000	<10000	<40000
Operating range [%]	20 - 100	10 - 100	20-100	25-100
Start-up [min]	15	< 15	-	> 60
Energy Consumption [kWh/Nm³]	4.5-7	4.5-7.5	R&D	2.5-3.5

Focus on the Hydrogen treatment Unit.

The hydrogen treatment unit in various electrolysis-based plants, as previously described, is one of the components most prone to hydrogen releases due to the various processes required to achieve hydrogen that meets the necessary standards for different applications.

The hydrogen handling subsystem includes the hydrogen-water separator, hydrogen drying and purification units, and optionally a hydrogen compression unit. In the hydrogen-water separator, water and hydrogen separate by gravity, allowing for an initial drying step. A demister is also installed at the gas outlet of the separator. To improve the drying effect, some systems available on the market include the option to cool the water in the separator (e.g., by pumping coolant through a coil within the separator). Other systems install a plate-type heat exchanger to cool the hydrogen leaving the separator and a separation unit to remove the condensed water.

Final step of standard hydrogen treatment is the removal of oxygen traces. Deoxidation systems (known as ‘deoxo systems’) are used to remove oxygen impurities through catalytic oxidation, consuming a small portion of the hydrogen to form water with the oxygen traces.

When very high purity hydrogen is required (e.g., for use in fuel cells or as a reactant in the chemical industry), additional purification units are installed as PSA dryers, desiccant dryers called TSA, and coalescer filters as evaluated in the “Hydrogen Treatment Unit”. Finally, the purified hydrogen flows through a valve and exits the system.

Evaluating the main hydrogen releases from electrolysis systems, a report by Frazer-Nash⁴⁰ estimated hydrogen venting from electrolyzer processes to be between 3% and 9% of production, introducing the main related hydrogen releases phenomena:

- **Purging and Venting:** This occurs during start-up, shutdown, or deviations from normal operation. Intermittent operation of the electrolyzer can lead to greater volumes of vented hydrogen.
- **Hydrogen Cross-Over:** Small amounts of hydrogen may migrate across the electrolyzer membrane to the anode, where it is ultimately vented. Cross-over of oxygen is usually smaller than hydrogen cross-over because dioxygen is a larger molecule.
- **Regenerating Units for Hydrogen Purification:** Purging is required for units like Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA), desiccant dryers (TSA) of small size but some TSAs are designed with a zero or close to zero purging.

During start-up, air in the cathode side is vented to avoid explosive mixtures, and during shutdown, it is vented again to remove moisture and prevent the formation of hydrogen-oxygen mixture leading to security issues. Minimizing off-specification hydrogen production is preferable, as regular venting impacts the overall operating efficiency and increases the hydrogen emissions. Consultation with OEMs indicates that hydrogen venting during start-up and shutdown is around 0.1% of total hydrogen produced. Assuming start-up and shutdown sequences last between 5 and 10 minutes and occur 50 to 300 times a year, hydrogen release is estimated to be 0.05% - 0.6% of the total produced.

Venting of hydrogen impurity in the oxygen byproduct is another potential source of emissions. Losses of hydrogen with the vented oxygen stream should be assessed, particularly at low load conditions, considering the impact of membrane degradation. Purging with nitrogen may be required, particularly for cold start-ups, resulting in more hydrogen being discharged. Opportunities to recycle should be sought, such as capturing, storing, and recycling off-specification hydrogen and/or oxygen. Combustion in air or oxygen, or alternative conversion techniques, can also reduce hydrogen emissions. Flare systems could be considered for disposal of hydrogen, subject to suitable design and controls.

The hydrogen produced from electrolyzer systems undergoes a purification step to meet the hydrogen fuel quality standard ISO 14687:2019. Depending on the required purity standards, different types of hydrogen dryers are used, including PSA dryers, desiccant dryers, and coalescer filters.

Going in the detail with each identified hydrogen release event:

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Safety Valves:** Overpressure events related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area. The total released mass depends on the frequency and duration of discharge, these specific elements have been detailed in the “Valves” subparagraph of “Balance of Plant Process Elements”.
- **Purging of Cathode Line for Start-Up and Shutdown:** Hydrogen releases from purging the cathode line with nitrogen or deionized (DI) water during start-up and shutdown procedures, primarily for PEM and AEM electrolyzers. Purging usually lasts less than 5 minutes at low pressures (< 10 psi)⁴¹.
- **Contamination of Vented Oxygen Due to Crossover:** Hydrogen contamination in the vented oxygen stream due to crossover.

- **H₂ treatment unit losses:** In systems with PSA, some dry hydrogen is used to dry the inactive desiccant bed, which is then used as thermal source for the burners or vented off to the atmosphere. The details of the specific procedure are contained in the “Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA)” paragraph.
- **H₂ Drying and Deoxygenating Losses in Demister:** Losses can occur in the final demister or coalescer system if ultrapure hydrogen is not required.
- **Hydrogen Venting at Start-Up and Shutdown:** Hydrogen is vented during start-up and shutdown procedures to eliminate traces of inert used for the purging procedure. Effective start-up and shutdown protocols can minimize these emissions.

Fugitives’ emissions are mainly related to:

- **Leaks in Pipes, Flanges, or Other Equipment:** Occasional releases or occasional equipment failures, operational errors (faulty components, corrosion, improper maintenance, or accidental damage). Further details of the losses are detailed in the “Balance of Plant Process Elements” paragraph.

4.3. Biomass Gasification

Hydrogen production from biomass gasification⁴² is considered a promising pathway for producing clean hydrogen, aligning with global efforts to transition to sustainable energy sources, since biomass represents a renewable and carbon-neutral feedstock. Biomass gasification process converts organic materials (*e.g.* wood chips or agricultural residues) into synthetic gas (syngas) in the presence of oxidizing agents, usually O₂ and steam. The syngas is sent through a shift reactor in order to increase the hydrogen yield. The main elements of the biomass gasification process are shown in the flow chart of Figure 13 and described below, considering the main processes of a biomass gasification plant⁴³:

Figure 13: Main elements of biomass classification process.

- **Feedstock Treatment Unit:** Biomass, including wood chips, agricultural residues, or other organic materials, is collected and pre-treated to remove impurities. This preparation can include drying, grinding, and other processes to optimize the materials for gasification.
- **Biomass Gasifier:** The prepared biomass is fed into a gasifier, where it is exposed to high temperatures (typically 700-1000°C) in the presence of a controlled amount of oxygen or steam. Instead of burning, the biomass undergoes a series of endothermic reactions where syngas is produced. These reactions include:
 - a) *Pyrolysis* (biomass decomposes into volatile gases, tar, and char).
 - b) *Oxidation* (volatile gases react with small amounts of oxygen to produce heat and convert into simpler molecules like CO and H₂).
 - c) *Reduction* (The remaining char reacts with steam (H₂O) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) to produce additional CO and H₂).
- **Syngas Cleaning/Cooling:** The resulting syngas, mainly consisting of H₂, CO, CO₂, H₂O, and various impurities, needs to be cleaned to remove particulate matter, sulphur compounds, chlorides, and other contaminants that can damage catalysts or other equipment downstream. The syngas temperature must be cooled down due to the negative enthalpy reaction of the shift reaction ($\Delta H = -41$ kJ/mol).
- **Water-gas Shift Reactor (S. R.):** to increase the hydrogen production yield, the syngas generated in the BG is processed further in a reactor where the water-gas shift reaction occurs:

$$\text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2.$$
- **H₂ treatment unit:** H₂ must be separated by CH₄, CO₂, and other impurities as H₂S. The syngas is subjected to the acid gas removal process where H₂S and CO₂ are removed from it with two stages.

Finally Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is utilized, where differences in gas molecule adsorption on surfaces under varying pressures is used to purify hydrogen, or through Membrane Separation, using selective membranes that allow only hydrogen molecules to pass through.

- **Plant Power Unit (optional):** After the PSA unit, the purge syngas is sent to the combustor to produce power. Steam Rankine cycle, organic Rankine cycle and system turbine are used for the power production unit of coal gasification plants²⁷.

The main operational parameters and information required for the characterization of the state of the art biomass gasification process are:

Table 9: Main operational parameters for the characterization of biomass gasification process.

Parameters	Description
Biomass Gasification reactor: Biomass reacts with O ₂ and Steam to produce the syngas	
Temperature [°C]	400-800 (depending on the type of biomass)
Pressure [bar]	1-100
Clean/cooling: The reaction must be cooled down due to the negative enthalpy of formation ($\Delta H = -41$ kJ/mol). Depending on the plant this is achieved via metal tubes, water or the gas expansion.	
Shift reactor: The syngas undergoes the shift reaction in order to increase the hydrogen production yield.	
Temperature [°C]	300-500
Pressure [bar]	10-100
Purifying Unit: The syngas is purified through processes such as Pressure Swing Adsorption or Membrane separation	
Plant lifetime [years]	20-40s
H ₂ Purity [%]	> 99

In evaluating the main hydrogen emissions of the biomass gasification process, only general losses have been introduced due to the lack of available information, the losses could be assumed similar to the ones of the coal gasification process:

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Leaks in Pipes, Flanges, or Other Equipment:** Occasional equipment failures, operational errors (faulty components, corrosion, improper maintenance, or accidental damage). Further details of the losses are detailed in the "Balance of Plant Process Elements" paragraph

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Safety Valves:** Overpressure events related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area. The total released mass depends on the frequency and duration of discharge, these specific elements have been detailed in the "Valves" subparagraph of "Balance of Plant Process Elements".

- **H₂ treatment unit losses:** In systems with PSA, some dry hydrogen is used to dry the inactive desiccant bed, which is then used as thermal source for the burners or vented off to the atmosphere. The details of the specific procedure are contained in the “Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA)” paragraph.
- **Purging and Venting:** Related to Maintenance and operational procedures for all the hydrogen lines and storage.

Unburned hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Off-gasses unburned:** in BG plants off-gasses containing hydrogen residues could be burned for thermal or electric energy purposes, minimum quantities of hydrogen could remain unburned.

4.4. Others

This category considers innovative ways to produce hydrogen. These technologies are considered as a possible different solution to support the hydrogen energy transition. Although they have a low TRL, it is fundamental to insert them for a complete analysis of the hydrogen supply chain.

4.4.1. Photo electrocatalysis

Solar energy is one of the abundant renewable energy sources for producing hydrogen from water. Particularly, photo electrocatalysis (PEC) has received increased attention due to the fact of using sun light to produce green hydrogen, even though it is in an early technological development stage⁴⁴. By doing so, the PEC is one of the potential strategies to mimic the photosynthesis artificially and to overcome high-power demands required for electrolysis, usually covered by fossil energy carriers. Also, PEC can be applied not only to water splitting, but also in applications such as pollutant detoxification, CO₂ reduction reaction, N₂ reduction reaction, alcohol oxidation or H₂O₂ production⁴⁵.

The technical photo electrocatalytic setup includes semi-conductor solar cell(s) as photoelectrodes, two electrodes separated by a membrane, which in turn are embedded in an electrolyte. The synthesis route is characterized by two semi-reactions: at the cathode hydrogen evolution reaction occurs, while at the anode oxygen evolution reaction occurs. As the electrolyte is basically predetermined⁴⁶, researchers focus on improving the photocathode with its catalyst and/or the electrode setups, as the fast charge recombination aggravates higher solar-to-hydrogen efficiencies ranging from 2.2% to 19.2%^{44,46}. The research mainly focused on the (photo)electrode design, whereas the systemic reactor design was less analysed due to the low TRL.

Figure 14: Photo electrocatalysis cell

For the definition of the archetype's elements do not consider the effective balance of plant (BOP) due to the LOW TRL of the technology, anyway a generalized plant layout will be defined:

- **Anode:** Electrode at which oxygen evolution reaction occurs
- **Cathode:** Electrode at which hydrogen evolution reaction occurs
- **Solar cell:** Absorption of photons to generate electron-hole pairs.
- **Membrane:** Separation layer for both electrodes
- **Electrolyte:** Medium

Table 10: Main operational parameters for the characterization of photo electrocatalysis process^{44,46,47}

Parameter	Value
Temperature [°C]	5-40
Water utilization and condition	Liquid or vapor at ambient temperature and pressure
H ₂ Output	Humidified at ambient temperature
Solar to hydrogen efficiency [%]	2.2-19.3

4.4.2. Thermochemical water splitting

Thermochemical water splitting (TCWS) is being researched since the 1960s and basically attempts to separate oxygen from the water molecules to gain hydrogen by using thermal energy. The most favoured synthesis route is the single-step cycle by splitting water directly into oxygen and hydrogen from a process engineering point of view. Two major challenges exist for successful single-cycle water splitting:

- i) temperatures >2000 °C are required
- ii) high affinity of oxygen and hydrogen to recombine to water.

Hence, it is difficult to implement larger production scales of single-cycle water splitting strategies^{48,49}. Consequently, the research focused on developing multi-cycle processes that use several cycles reducing the demand for thermal energy and on different precursors to simplify the separation of hydrogen. In the last decades a multitude of potential synthesis routes were investigated. An overview is given in Safari and Dincer⁴⁸. In general, the technical readiness level of all TCWS applications is low and mostly at a lab and few at pilot scale facilities tested.

Since the TCWS has a high energy demand, nuclear power and concentrated solar power are considered as potential electricity and thermal energy sources, which have less CO₂-emissions during operation than fossil-based sources. Potential precursors are based on sulphur and sulphur acid-cycle (i.e. sulphur iodine, hybrid sulphur cycle, sulphur trioxide), Cu-Cl and Mg-Cl cycle, metal oxides (e.g. ZnO, CeO₂, Fe₃O₄)⁴⁹.

The simplified process flow chart shows the general scheme of pure and hybrid thermochemical cycle in Figure 15.

Figure 15: General scheme of pure and hybrid thermochemical cycles⁴⁸

Are reported in the Table 11, some operational parameters for different approaches for thermochemical water splitting based on different studies⁵⁰⁻⁵²

Table 11: Main operational parameters for thermochemical water splitting processes bases on different energy sources

Parameter	Value range	
Energy Source	Nuclear	Solar
Temperature [°C]	550-850	1327-1727
H ₂ Output [tonH ₂ /day]	7-800	6

As PEC and TCWS technology matures, the Balance of Plant (BOP) components will play a critical role in the overall system efficiency and stability. Considering that both technologies mainly exploit solar irradiance, key BOP components could include:

- **Thermal or irradiance energy management system:** For the TCWS the thermal energy system has to be equipped with a high temperature heat exchanger to feed the thermochemical cycle. For the PEC the energy is directly absorbed by semiconducting materials⁵³.
- **Cooling System:** Manages the heat generated during the processes to maintain system stability and efficiency.
- **TCWS or PEC element:** main element in which the hydrogen production is occurring
- **Hydrogen Storage and Handling:** Safely stores the produced hydrogen and manages its delivery for further use or transport.

Hydrogen releases and losses are critical considerations in PEC & TCWS systems. Key potential release points could include:

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Leaks in Pipes, Flanges, or Other Equipment:** Occasional equipment failures, operational errors (faulty components, corrosion, improper maintenance, or accidental damage). Further details of the losses are detailed in the "Balance of Plant Process Elements" paragraph

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Safety Valves:** Overpressure events related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area. The total released mass depends on the frequency and duration of discharge, these specific elements have been detailed in the "Valves" subparagraph of "Balance of Plant Process Elements".
- **Purging and Venting:** Related to Maintenance and operational procedures for all the hydrogen lines and storage.

5. CONVERSION & RECONVERSION

After its production, hydrogen often undergoes conversion into a different physical or chemical form that is more suitable for transport or storage. These conversion processes include compression, liquefaction, or incorporation into chemical carriers such as ammonia, e-methanol or new forms of Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs). Reconversion refers to the extraction or release of hydrogen from these carriers once it reaches its destination or after a storage phase. This section covers all the intermediate steps between hydrogen production and its end-use, necessary for the storage and transportation of it in various forms.

In this category, we will examine the necessary transformation and loading/unloading procedures for each specific transport vector, from the loading bays for compressed/liquefied hydrogen to the reconversion plants required for ammonia, methanol synthesis and cracking, and more. The main hydrogen conversion and reconversion technologies to be evaluated include:

- **Compression of Hydrogen for Compressed Hydrogen Storage and Transport:** This archetype considers the compression stations needed to load and unload storage and transport compressed H₂ tanks. These systems are commonly referred to as compression and loading bays. Depending on the requirements of specific tanks, this compression and loading bays will have different operational pressures and configurations.
- **Liquefaction and Regasification of Hydrogen:** Hydrogen liquefaction involves cooling gaseous hydrogen to cryogenic temperatures to convert it into a liquid form. This process is energy-intensive but provides a high-density storage solution. Regasification is the process of converting liquid hydrogen back into gaseous form, typically at the point of use or distribution.
- **Ammonia Synthesis and Cracking:** Ammonia (NH₃) synthesis involves combining hydrogen with nitrogen under high pressure and temperature using the Haber-Bosch process. Ammonia is a widely used hydrogen carrier due to its high energy density and established infrastructure. Cracking ammonia involves breaking it down back into hydrogen and nitrogen, usually through thermal or catalytic processes.
- **E-Methanol Synthesis and Cracking:** E-methanol is synthesized by combining hydrogen with carbon dioxide in a catalytic process. Methanol serves as a convenient liquid carrier for hydrogen. Cracking methanol involves converting it back into hydrogen and carbon dioxide, typically using catalytic methods.
- **LOHC Hydrogenation and Dehydrogenation:** Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs) involve binding hydrogen to a liquid carrier molecule. Hydrogenation is the process of attaching hydrogen to the carrier, while dehydrogenation is the release of hydrogen from the carrier. This method offers safe and efficient hydrogen storage and transport solutions.

By thoroughly examining these technologies and their specific operational parameters, it's possible to understand their roles and impacts within the hydrogen supply chain.

5.1. H₂ Compression

Even if it is not exactly a conversion, hydrogen pressurization is a critical aspect of the hydrogen value chain, particularly in terms of the transportation and storage of compressed hydrogen, which is currently the most used technique. This solution proves to be particularly cost-effective for medium to short distances and moderate quantities of hydrogen. As will be evaluated in detail in the “**Errore. L'origine r iferimento non è stata trovata.**” chapter.

The types of compressors used in hydrogen pressurization are various and can be categorized into mechanical and non-mechanical devices. Among the mechanical devices, we find piston-driven compressors, diaphragm compressors, ionic liquid compressors, and centrifugal compressors. Non-mechanical devices include electrochemical compressors^{54,55}.

Among the various types, "positive displacement" devices are particularly used for hydrogen compression. Reciprocating piston compressors are the most widely used and can produce high-pressure hydrogen, especially when a multi-stage configuration is employed. Commercially available solutions have demonstrated achieving high discharge pressures up to 850 bara and flow rates up to 10'000 Nm³/h. These are typically used in refineries and chemical plants to compress industrial-grade hydrogen to high pressures⁵⁴. Hydrogen's lightness significantly impacts compressor design, as requiring high head impeller types, more stages, or higher impeller tip speeds to achieve similar pressure ratios as natural gas for centrifugal compressors. High-strength steels and titanium alloys are typically used to withstand high tip velocities but are susceptible to hydrogen embrittlement, leading to redesign efforts in compressor technology. Recent innovations allow for more impellers in a series, and research focuses on electrochemical compressors, although these are less likely to be used in high-capacity transmission systems.

The considered compressors type for this specific hydrogen application are:

- **Piston Compressors:** These are widely used due to their ability to achieve high pressures and to their robustness. Piston compressors can handle varying levels of hydrogen flow and pressure, making them versatile for different needs.
- **Centrifugal Compressors:** Typically used for large-scale hydrogen applications, these compressors are suited for high-flow, low-to-medium pressure scenarios. They are less common in loading stations but can be used in specific applications requiring large volumes of hydrogen.
- **Diaphragm Compressors:** These compressors are known for their high purity compression, as the hydrogen does not encounter the moving parts. They are ideal for compressing hydrogen to high pressures without contamination.

The configurations of compressors in a hydrogen loading bay or for a hydrogen refuelling station can vary based on the station's design and capacity requirements, precisely:

- **Single Medium-Pressure Compressor:** This configuration is used in smaller stations or those with lower throughput. It compresses hydrogen to medium pressures (500 bar), which are then further managed by the storage and dispensing system.

- **Dual Compressors (Medium and High Pressure):** In this setup, one compressor is used to compress hydrogen to a medium pressure, which is then fed into a second compressor to achieve the high pressure required for vehicle refuelling or high-pressure trailers (typically 200/350 bar up 700 bar). This configuration ensures a more efficient and reliable compression process, balancing the load between two compressors.
- **Multiple Compressors in Parallel:** For high-capacity loading bays, multiple compressors can be used in parallel to handle large volumes of hydrogen. This setup provides redundancy and ensures continuous operation even if one compressor is offline for maintenance.
- **Cascade Compression Systems:** In this configuration, hydrogen is compressed in stages using multiple compressors. Each stage progressively increases the pressure, which can be more efficient and reduce the strain on individual compressors.

These compressor types and configurations ensure that hydrogen is delivered at the correct pressures required for safe and efficient vehicle refuelling, adapting to the specific demands and capacities of different hydrogen mobility stations.

The archetype considered for this analysis includes the main elements of an average hydrogen compression facility, schematized in Figure 16:

Figure 16: General compression/loading bay layout.

- **Low Pressure Compressor (LP):** for low-pressure hydrogen production, below 30 bar.
- **Buffer Tank (BT):** typically, a few cubic meters of hydrogen to compensate for pressure variations and other needs.
- **High-Pressure Compressor (HP):** generally configured in multi-stage and parallel lines of compressors, this element will consider also the internal coolers units between stages to remain below the 135°C hydrogen temperature limits for safety⁵⁶, filters/separators and all the required valves system.
- **High pressure storage (cascades):** in the 70-95 MPa range.
- **Precooling unit:** fundamental to pre-cool the compressed hydrogen between -20 & -40 °C to respect the 85 °C operating temperature limits for tanks hydrogen storage system.

- **Dispenser or Loading Bay:** where compressed hydrogen is loaded into storage units or transport modules for delivery. Made of safety and regulation valves, flow meter, brake-away device that allow the disconnection of the hose from the loading bay and final hose and nozzle.
- **Balance of Plant (BOP):** Control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings can be considered sources of leakages or losses during normal operation or due to some process events (i.e. Depressurization after shut-down, PSV opening for pressure protection, etc.)

The most relevant elements for the hydrogen releases/losses evaluation are the compressor element and the final dispenser/loading bay block, so will be further detailed and will be defined as sub-archetype.

5.1.1. Compression unit

In this paragraph are evaluated both low pressure (LP) and high pressure (HP) compression units. The main difference is that the HP compression lines, can be made of different stages of compression in parallel and/or series configurations. This characteristic should be considered when evaluating the losses in this archetype.

The main plant components for a state-of-the-art compression station have been detailed in Figure 17, including the two compression steps and the interstage BOP, characterized by filters, coolers, valves and separators.

Figure 17: Detailed representation of compression unit (MP and/or HP).

For the sub-archetype definition, since the main sources of leakages/losses are concentrated in the compressor cylinder and its connections, the archetype focuses mainly on the cylinder system. Different configurations may be applicable depending on the cylinder arrangement. For low pressure (LP) compression stage, only the reciprocating compressors will be evaluated. Conversely, for the high pressure (HP) compression stage up to 550 bar reciprocating, centrifugal and diaphragm compressors will be evaluated.

Reciprocating Compressors

Reciprocating compressors, particularly oil-free models, are widely used in hydrogen applications due to their suitability for high-pressure and moderate-flow scenarios. These compressors can achieve pressures ranging from 350 to 550 bar at flow rates up to 1000 kg H₂/h, and they can also be used as low-pressure booster compressors operating under 30 bar^{54,57}.

The basic mechanism involves a piston-cylinder system with inlet and outlet valves, where compression energy is provided by a crankshaft connected to a piston via a connecting rod, converting rotary motion into linear motion.

The sub-archetype for reciprocating compressors, covering both high-pressure (HP) and low-pressure (LP) applications, is represented as follows:

Figure 18: Focus on the Reciprocating compressor.

The main elements defined for the reciprocating compressor are:

- **Cylinder body:** The cylinder body houses the piston and is where the compression of hydrogen gas takes place. The cylinder body is typically constructed from high-strength materials to ensure durability and efficiency in the compression process.
- **Suction valve unloading system:** This system controls the intake of hydrogen gas into the cylinder.
- **Piston:** the piston's reciprocating motion compresses the gas during the compression stroke
- **Main road packing system:** This system seals the area around the piston rod to prevent hydrogen leaks. Consists of multiple rings or seals that provide a tight seal around the rod
- **Crankshaft & connecting rod:** The crankshaft converts the rotary motion of the drive unit into the linear motion required to move the piston. The connecting rod links the crankshaft to the piston, transferring the rotational energy into a reciprocating motion.
- **BOP:** Includes control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings, seal gas system, cooling system and lubrication system

For the low-pressure compression stage the main operational parameters fundamental for the hydrogen releases estimation are:

Table 12: Low-pressure compression stage operational parameters.

Parameters	Small Size	Medium Size	Large Size
Cylinder Q.ty	1-6	2-8	2-10
Inlet Pressure [bar]	1-5	1-5	1-5
Outlet Pressure [bar]	10-30	10-30	10-30
Inlet Temperature [°C]	20-50	20-50	20-50
Outlet Temperature [°C]	100-150	100-150	100-150
Piston rod diameter [mm]	<65	65-100	100-165
Cylinder technology	Dry/Lube	Dry/Lube	Dry/Lube

For High-Pressure Compressor (HP), reciprocating compressor with delivery pressure from 350 to 550 bar have been considered.

For the sub-archetype definition, since the main sources of leakages/losses are concentrated in the compressor cylinder and relevant connections, the archetype focuses mainly on the cylinder system. Different configurations may be applicable depending on the cylinder arrangement. The main operational parameters fundamental for the hydrogen releases estimation are:

Table 13: High-pressure compression stage operational parameters.

Parameters	Small Size	Medium Size	Large Size
Cylinder Q.ty	1-6	2-8	2-10
Inlet Pressure [bar]	20-30	20-30	20-30
Outlet Pressure [bar]	Up to 550	Up to 350	Up to 350
Inlet Temperature [°C]	20-50	20-50	20-50
Outlet Temperature [°C]	100-150	100-150	100-150
Piston rod diameter [mm]	<65	65-100	100-165
Cylinder technology	Dry/Lube	Dry/Lube	Dry/Lube

The main hydrogen release elements/events related to the reciprocating compressors compression step can be categorized following the previously defined H₂ emission categorization:

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Main Rod Packing – First and second Piston Rod Sealing Gas Vent:** Leakages during normal operation from the first and second piston rod sealing. They are related to compressor operating conditions, size, sealing arrangement, cylinder type, and sealing wear status. These vents are

typically routed to flare system. If the suction pressure is low (e.g., < 2.5 bar), the first sealing vent can be routed to compressor suction or a dedicated low-pressure system, in which case a second gas vent is present. The vented gas may contain a mix of process gas and nitrogen if rod packing sealing is buffered with nitrogen.

- **Distance Piece Vent:** Venting from the separation volume between the cylinder and frame to low pressure (typically atmospheric pressure). It is related to compressor size, rod packing sealing arrangement, and sealing wear status. If nitrogen purging is present, the vented gas is mainly nitrogen otherwise is the mainly processing gas.
- **Suction Valve Unloader Pneumatic Actuator Rod Packing Sealing:** Leakages from the valve unloader actuator rod sealing. They are related to Actuator quantity, size, cylinder operating conditions. It can be routed to atmosphere in safe location. It normally contains process gas only but in case of actuator rod packing sealing buffering with nitrogen it contains mainly nitrogen with traces of process gas.

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Balance of Plant (BOP):** Control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings can be considered sources of leakages or losses during normal operation or due to some process events (i.e. Depressurization after shut-down, PSV opening for pressure protection, etc.). Related to various parameters depending on the specific component

Centrifugal compressors

Centrifugal compressors are dynamic compressors widely used in applications requiring high throughput and moderate compression ratios. They compress process gas using a rotating impeller with radial blades. Due to the low molecular weight of hydrogen (H_2), centrifugal compressors need impeller tip-speeds about three times higher for H_2 than those used for natural gas. Recent advancements have led to the development of titanium alloy-based impellers capable of operating with 100% H_2 at high tip speeds of approximately 700 m/s, enabling a pressure ratio per stage of 1.26:1^{54,55}.

The sub-archetype for high pressure centrifugal compressors can be represented as:

Figure 19: Centrifugal compressor state of the art.

The key elements considered for the state-of-the-art centrifugal compressors are:

- **Casing, head flange system:** The casing houses the rotating components and maintains the structural integrity of the compressor. The head flange system ensures a secure connection and minimizes leakage.
- **Statoric part:** The stator contains stationary components that guide the flow of gas through the compressor as the diffuser element and the volute.
- **Rotoric part:** The rotor includes the impeller and other rotating elements that provide the energy necessary for compressing the hydrogen gas. The impeller's radial blades accelerate the gas, increasing its pressure.
- **Suction and discharge section:** These sections manage the inflow and outflow of hydrogen gas, maintaining appropriate pressure and flow rates within the system.
- **Balance of Plant (BOP):** Control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings, seal gas system, cooling system and lubrication system

The main Centrifugal compressor based high compression stage parameters for the hydrogen releases evaluation are reported in Table 14:

Table 14: High-pressure compression stage operational parameters.

Parameters	Small Size	Medium Size	Large Size
Size (casing internal diameter) (mm)	400-900	900-1200	1200-2000
Pressure Rating [bar]	350	220	130
Service	Ammonia Fertilizer	Refinery (Recycle)	Refinery / H ₂ Production
Speed [rpm]	10000-20000	6000-10000	3000-6000

The main hydrogen emissions related to the centrifugal compressor's compression step are:

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Head Flange Leakage:** Leaks from connections, typically routed to the plant flare system. Continuous H₂ leakage due to compressor gaskets in the head flange/casing connection, influenced by compressor operating pressure.

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Compressor Shutdown with Vent:** Venting of plant volume during unexpected shutdowns (trip with vent for compressor/plant component failure) or normal shutdowns requiring depressurization. Typically routed to the plant flare system.
- **Seal Gas Filter Cartridge Maintenance:** During filter maintenance (cartridge replacement), the gas volume is vented to the atmosphere.

Fugitive/Vent emissions:

- **Primary Vent:** Continuous H₂ leakage from the inboard dry gas seal cartridge, typically routed to the plant flare system.
- **Secondary Vent:** Continuous H₂ leakage from the outboard dry gas seal cartridge, typically routed to the atmosphere during normal operation.
- **Control Valves, Safety Valves, Venting/Blow-Down Valves, Manual Valves, Fittings:** These components can leak or lose hydrogen during normal operation or process events (e.g., depressurization after shutdown, PSV opening for pressure protection).

Diaphragm compressors

Diaphragm compressors are ideal for handling high purity gases as the process gas is completely isolated from the hydraulic oil and/or piston. The motion in a diaphragm compressor is transmitted from a piston driven by a crankshaft to a hydraulic fluid, which then moves a thin metal membrane called a diaphragm. Materials commonly used for the diaphragm plates include stainless steel, stainless chrome nickel steel, copper-beryllium alloys, and duplex steel.

Due to their design, diaphragm compressors effectively minimize hydrogen leakages since the hydrogen circuit is entirely separated from the oil circuit. However, their durability is a concern due to the mechanical stresses that occur during operation. These compressors are particularly suitable for applications requiring low flow rates, capable of handling up to 700 Nm³/h of hydrogen at a maximum pressure of 1000 bar^{54,55}.

The sub-archetype for high pressure diaphragm compressors can be represented as:

Figure 20: Focus on the Diaphragm compressor.

The key elements considered for the state-of-the-art diaphragm compressors are:

- **Compression Diaphragm:** The diaphragm serves as the barrier separating the hydraulic fluid from the process gas. It flexes to compress the gas within the cylinder. Typically made from durable materials like stainless steel, stainless chrome nickel steel, copper-beryllium alloys, or duplex steel, ensuring resistance to high pressures and mechanical stresses.
- **Piston and Hydraulic System:** Driven by a crankshaft, the piston creates pressure in the hydraulic fluid, which in turn flexes the diaphragm. The hydraulic fluid transmits the motion from the piston to the diaphragm. Typically, an oil that ensures smooth operation and helps dissipate heat.

- **Cylinder Body:** Houses the diaphragm and provides the structural integrity needed to withstand high-pressure operations.
- **Crankshaft and Connecting Rod:** Converts rotary motion from a motor into the reciprocating motion of the piston.
- **Balance of Plant (BOP):** Control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings, seal gas system, cooling system and lubrication system

The main diaphragm compressor based high compression stage parameters for the hydrogen releases evaluation are reported in Table 15:

Table 15: High-pressure compression stage operational parameters.

Parameters	Small Size	Large Size
Cylinder Q.ty	1-2	4-6
Inlet Pressure [bar]	20-30	20-30
Outlet Pressure [bar]	Up to 900	Up to 900
Inlet Temperature [°C]	20-50	20-50
Outlet Temperature [°C]	100-150	100-150

For diaphragm compressors hydrogen is not in direct contact with moving parts as the piston, so the losses are limited, precisely:

- **Compression Diaphragm:** It is typically hermetically sealed, there is not gas leakage expected in normal operating conditions. The more advanced solutions provide a diaphragm construction that can detect through pressure measurement a possible diaphragm damage so preventing any major gas leakage outside of the compressor
- **Balance of Plan (BOP):** Control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings can be considered sources of leakages or losses during normal operation or due to some process events (i.e. Depressurization after shut-down, PSV opening for pressure protection, etc.)

5.1.2. Hydrogen Dispenser

A hydrogen dispenser is a crucial component of a hydrogen refuelling station or a loading bay for compressed hydrogen tanks refill. It functions similarly to a traditional gasoline pump, but it is specifically engineered to handle hydrogen gas at various pressures. The dispenser ensures that hydrogen is delivered at the correct pressure and temperature, providing a seamless and safe refuelling experience for users.

Types of Dispensers could be:

- **Medium-Pressure Dispensers:** Typically operate at pressures below 350 bar. Used for refuelling up to Type III tanks.
- **High-Pressure Dispensers:** Typically operate at pressures around 700 bar. Used for refuelling up to Type IV-V tanks.

For the characterization of the dispenser sub-archetype, key Components are:

- **Safety Shut-off Valves:** Provides an emergency shutoff mechanism to prevent over-pressurization and potential hazards.
- **Flow Meter:** Measures the flow rate of hydrogen being dispensed into the vehicle's tank.
- **Regulation Valve:** Controls the flow rate and pressure of hydrogen being dispensed.
- **Heat Exchanger:** Used to manage the temperature of hydrogen during dispensing, preventing excessive temperature changes that can occur due to the rapid expansion of hydrogen gas.
- **Hydrogen Filter:** Removes impurities and contaminants from the hydrogen gas before it is dispensed into the tank.
- **Break-Away Device:** A safety feature that allows the hose to disconnect from the dispenser in the event of a vehicle driving away with the nozzle still attached.
- **Hose:** Flexible tubing that connects the dispenser to the tank's refuelling port.
- **Nozzle:** The end component of the dispenser that connects to the hydrogen tank inlet. Equipped with safety interlocks to ensure a secure connection and prevent hydrogen leaks during refuelling.

The previously defined elements have been considered for the definition of the specific sub-archetype presented in Figure 21:

Figure 21: Detailed representation of dispenser

Dispenser units of the hydrogen tank's loading bays or refuelling station involve several potential points of hydrogen emissions, each with distinct characteristics and mitigation strategies. Below is a detailed breakdown of these release points, categorized by the sub-part.

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Purging Line:** After each loading session, to disconnect the nozzle from the tank, it is necessary to relieve the pressure inside the dispensing line, this venting occurs after each fuelling.
- **Safety Devices (Pressure Relief Device - PRD):** In case of overpressure in the distribution line, the overpressure is evacuated by a PRD. These devices are not represented on schematics as their positions vary among different suppliers.

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Any Equipment Installed on the Dispenser (Flow Meter, Regulation Valve, HEX, Filter, Break-Away, Hose, Nozzle):** Fugitive releases can occur due to leakages at the interfaces between the piping and the installed equipment. These releases are controlled and mitigated through leak tests during regular inspection and maintenance plans.
- **Break-Away:** In the event of a rupture of the break-away, hydrogen can be released at very high pressure (up to 700 bar) for a very short duration (under one second).

5.2. NH₃ synthesis/cracking

Hydrogen production for ammonia currently stands at 200 Mton/year per year, which is crucial for the production of fertilizers. Nowadays, it is also gaining ground as an energy carrier, thanks to the already developed international shipping chain, reaching a demand of 600 Mton/year of ammonia by 2050, 55% of which will be green ammonia (from renewable hydrogen and CCUS CO₂)¹⁸.

For this work, NH₃ synthesis and cracking systems for the reconversion of hydrogen, required for transportation in ammonia tanks, have been considered.

5.2.1. Synthesis (Haber-Bosch)

The synthesis of ammonia is a critical industrial process where nitrogen, extracted from the ambient air, is combined with hydrogen. The predominant method for this synthesis is the Haber-Bosch process.

For the purposes of this work the Ammonia synthesis process has been schematized in Figure 22 as:

Figure 22: Ammonia Synthesis archetype flowchart.

Main elements introduced are:

- **Nitrogen Unit:** Nitrogen Unit provides pure Nitrogen extracted from the air to the synthesis process at approx. 8 bara.
- **Compression:** Hydrogen and Nitrogen is mixed with a ratio of 3 to 1 required for the synthesis of Ammonia. Ammonia syngas is compressed to synthesis loop pressure of 130 to 200 bara.
- **Synthesis Loop:** According to the Haber-Bosch Synthesis, Ammonia syngas is routed through a multi bed reactor filled with Fe-based catalysts. Hydrogen and Nitrogen reacts to Ammonia. Heat of exothermic ammonia synthesis is used for steam generation. Ammonia is condensed from process gas. Unconverted syngas is recycled back to the process.
- **Refrigeration:** In an open Ammonia refrigeration cycle, produced Ammonia is further cooled down and purified. Dissolved inert gases, contained in the Nitrogen and Hydrogen feed, are removed from liquid ammonia and thermally treated.
- **NH₃ Storage:** Produced Ammonia is typically stored in liquid state at temperatures of approx. -33°C in atmospheric pressure storage tanks. Alternatively, pressure tanks could be utilized.

The main operational parameters required for the characterization of the ammonia synthesis process are:

Table 16: Main NH₃ synthesis operational parameters.

Parameter	Values	Notes
Operating temperatures of synthesis loop [°C]	400 – 520	In Synthesis Loop
Operating pressure of synthesis loop [bara]	130 – 200	In Synthesis Loop
Operating temperatures of ammonia tank [°C]	-33	Atm. storage
Operating pressure ammonia tank [bara]	Atm.	
NH ₃ Production [MTPD]	up to 3500	
H ₂ per NH ₃ [mol/mol]	1,5	H ₂ losses via purge are neglected
N ₂ per NH ₃ [mol/mol]	0.5	N ₂ losses via purge are neglected

Hydrogen emissions in the ammonia synthesis process can occur at several points, each with specific characteristics and mitigation strategies. Below is a detailed overview of the main hydrogen release elements/events related to the ammonia synthesis process, categorized by the type and category of the release:

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Start-Up:** For adjustment of the correct syngas mixture, syngas is temporarily routed to the flare prior to compression. This process approximately occurs for few hours every start-up. Usually, complete combustion is assumed. For baseload ammonia plants, this occurs at a low frequency.
- **Flare Scenario from Compressor:** Controlled or emergency depressurization of the compressor to the flare. Occurs with rare frequency.
- **Flare Scenario from Throttling:** Controlled or emergency depressurization of the NH₃ throttle section to the flare. Occurs with rare frequency.
- **Inert Purge from Refrigeration Unit:** Inert from the ammonia synthesis loop are purged together with traces of H₂ and NH₃ and routed to the flare. Occurs continuously during operation. Usually, complete combustion is assumed. For baseload ammonia plants, this occurs at a low frequency.
- **Compressor Seal Gas Losses:** Continuous seal gas losses of the compressor are routed to the flare. This type of losses occurs continuously during operation but for baseload ammonia plants, this occurs at a low frequency.

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Losses via Flanges/Valves:** Direct losses to the atmosphere difficult to quantify.

5.2.2. Cracking

Ammonia cracking is a chemical process in which ammonia (NH₃) is decomposed into nitrogen (N₂) and hydrogen (H₂) gases. This process is gaining interest as a means of hydrogen production, particularly in the context of using ammonia as a hydrogen carrier for energy applications.

Ammonia cracking involves the following reaction: $2NH_3 \rightarrow 3H_2 + N_2$

This reaction typically occurs at high temperatures (500-1000°C) and may require a catalyst, such as nickel, to enhance the reaction rate and efficiency operating at low pressures of about 30-40 bar.

For the purposes of this work the Ammonia cracking process has been schematized in Figure 23 as:

Figure 23: Ammonia cracking archetype flowchart.

Main elements introduced are:

- **Nitrogen Storage:** Imported green Ammonia can be stored either pressurized at ambient conditions or subcooled in liquid state at atmospheric conditions.
- **Vaporization and Pre-Heating:** Ammonia is pressurized by pump to operating pressure of the Ammonia Cracker, vaporized and superheated by recovering heat from the hot process gases leaving the cracker unit (flue gas & cracked process gas)
- **NH₃ Cracker:** In the Ammonia Cracker, NH₃ reacts to H₂ and N₂, supported by e.g. nickel catalysts. The heat required for the endothermic cracking reaction can be provided by burning natural gas, or by burning the PSA off gas plus Ammonia or Hydrogen. An electrical heated configuration is also possible. The process gas heat is recovered by cooling the gas to evaporate and superheat the Ammonia prior to be fed to the Cracker (in Vaporization and Pre-Heating Unit). Optionally a pre-cracker can be installed upstream of the main cracker unit.
- **PSA:** The PSA separates the Hydrogen from the Nitrogen and provides a pressurized pure Hydrogen stream. The PSA tail gas can be utilized for further Hydrogen recovery or for providing the heat for the endothermic cracking reaction.

Table 17: Main NH₃ cracking operational Parameter.

Parameter	Value Range	Notes
Operating temperatures pre-cracker [°C]	450 – 650	Lower temperature may require precious metal catalysts
Operating temperatures main cracker [°C]	600 – 850	
Operating pressure of main cracker [bara]	30 – 40	
Energy Efficiency [%]	80 – 90	HHV H ₂ Prod. to Utility consumption plus HHV NH ₃
Hydrogen Efficiency [%]	70 – 78	H ₂ Prod. to H ₂ in NH ₃ feed

Ton NH₃ [t]/ H₂ [t]	6,5 to 7,6	
Hydrogen Purity [%]	> 99,9 %	As required by PSA adjustment

The main hydrogen emissions related to the ammonia cracking step are reported below following the previously defined H_2 releases categorization.

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Tank:** Controlled or emergency depressurization of NH₃ tank to flare in which gasses are vented, of only very rare frequency.
- **Cracker Unit:** Controlled or emergency depressurization of ammonia or pre-cracked or completely cracked ammonia to flare in which the gasses are vented, of only very rare frequency.
- **PSA Unit in Cracker Unit:** Controlled or emergency depressurization of PSA Unit to flare in which the gasses are vented, of only very rare frequency.
- **Incomplete Combustion or Combustion Byproducts from Main Cracker Unit:** PSA off-gas, ammonia, and hydrogen can be used to provide heat for the endothermic cracking reaction. Final emissions depend on the installed flue gas treatment unit, the exhaust gasses are directly released in the atmosphere, happens continuously during operation of the plant

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Losses via Flanges/Valves:** Direct releases in the atmosphere, including both ammonia and hydrogen leakages.

5.3. H₂ liquefaction / regassification

Liquid hydrogen (LH₂) is highly regarded for its potential in energy storage and transportation due to its relatively high volumetric density—80% greater than compressed gaseous hydrogen at 700 bars. Unlike ammonia and methanol, LH₂ does not require energy for dehydrogenation when used in fuel cell applications. However, LH₂ presents significant technological challenges, such as the emission of greenhouse gases and other pollutants during direct combustion and related to safety (connected to the handling cryogenic liquid with such a high energy density), to the efficiency of the production/transport process and scalability of the process. Currently, LH₂ is primarily used for rocket propulsion and other specialized applications and is not yet developed to the scale needed for global hydrogen trade.

The investment costs and energy demand of the LH₂ supply chain are predominantly found in the liquefaction and storage for transport stages. Liquefying hydrogen requires substantial energy to reach temperatures as low as -260°C. Furthermore, specialized insulated vessels are necessary to maintain these low temperatures during storage and transport, which also consumes energy. Additionally, during transport and storage, there are inevitable losses due to the boil-off of part of the hydrogen.

5.3.1. Liquefaction

Hydrogen liquefaction involves three primary phases: compression, cooling, and expansion. Initially, gaseous hydrogen is compressed, and its excess heat is removed via a heat exchanger until it reaches ambient temperature (300 K). The compressed hydrogen is then cooled using other cold streams through additional heat exchangers to below its inversion temperature (80 K). These cold streams can be liquid nitrogen (Joule-Thomson process), helium (H₂-He cascade system), or hydrogen itself (Claude process and Linde-Hampson process). Finally, the cooled hydrogen stream is expanded through a throttling valve to reach its final temperature of 20 K, resulting in partial liquefaction.

Hydrogen liquefaction is more energy-intensive compared to processes like ammonia synthesis or LOHC hydrogenation, primarily due to the need for compressors and the production of cooling streams. The energy required to liquefy hydrogen ranges from 6.67 kWh/kg_{H₂} to 10 kWh/kg_{H₂}.

Despite the maturity of this technology, there is a shortage of large-scale plants. Economies of scale significantly influence specific energy consumption, with larger plants being more efficient. For example, energy consumption of liquefied hydrogen decreases from 12.5 kWh/kg_{H₂} for a 10 ton_{H₂}/day facility to 8.69 kWh/kg_{H₂} for a 200 ton_{H₂}/day facility. Projections indicate that by 2050, energy consumption for hydrogen liquefaction could decrease to between 5.5 and 6.1 kWh/kg_{H₂}.

The archetype for hydrogen liquefaction has been categorized as presented in Figure 24:

Figure 24: Archetype for hydrogen liquefaction system.

Main elements introduced are:

- **Compression:** Preferable pure and pressurized Hydrogen is provided to the Hydrogen liquefaction Unit. At inlet of liquefaction unit, the hydrogen is further compressed to pressures of typically 25 to 35 bara by a piston compressor, the details of this element are evaluated in the “[H₂ Compression](#)” archetype.
- **Pre-Cooling:** Optional pre-cooling cools down the compressed pure Hydrogen to temperatures of approx. 80 K.
- **Adsorption:** Via redundant adsorbers enabling continuous operation, impurities that would freeze out and block the cryogenic section are removed from Hydrogen.
- **Cryogenic Liquefaction:** The cryogenic liquefaction cycle cools Hydrogen down to approx. 30 K. The cryogenic section includes catalytic conversion of ortho- to parahydrogen. Via the recycle compressor (RC) flashed H₂ from downstream of the Expansion section is recycled back to the process.
- **Expansion:** Via either adiabatic expansion by valve or by expansion via expander, Hydrogen is throttled, and liquid Hydrogen is removed. The flash fraction is routed back to recycle compressor (RC) after cold recovery. Liquid Hydrogen is provided at approx. 2 bara and 21 K.
- **LH₂ loading bay:** Made of a stationary storage tank and a dispenser line for the loading procedures of tanks.

Table 18: Main LH₂ liquefaction operational Parameters.

Parameter	Value
Operating temperatures liq. Hydrogen [K]	Down to 20
Operating pressure of liquefaction [bara]	20 – 60
Specific energy consumption [kWh/kg LH ₂]	12 to 15 starting from atmospheric H ₂ 10 to 13 starting from pressurized H ₂
Liquefaction Capacity [t/d]	5 to 30 today available, 50 to 200 near future

Focus on loading procedure of LH₂ tanks

Transferring liquid hydrogen from the production or storage facilities to a tanker or from a trailer to an on-site storage tank, involves two primary methods:

1. **Pressure Accumulation:** This method involves increasing the pressure in the "mother" storage tank so that it becomes higher than the pressure in the "daughter" tank. This can be achieved either naturally or by intentionally vaporizing a small amount of LH₂ using an external heat exchanger.
2. **Cryogenic Pump Transfer:** This method uses a specialized cryogenic centrifugal pump to transfer LH₂ from the "mother" tank to the "daughter" tank.

Hydrogen liquefaction units involve several potential points of hydrogen emissions, each with distinct characteristics and mitigation strategies. Below is a detailed breakdown of these release points, categorized by the type and category of the emission:

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Flare Scenario from Liquefaction Unit:** Controlled (e.g., maintenance) or emergency depressurization of the compressor to the flare that causes hydrogen venting. If Controlled maintenance (approximately once per year) is correctly done, emergency depressurization is rare.
- **Inventory Adjustment for Load Control:** At part load, the inventory of the liquefaction unit needs to be reduced. The inventory can either be directly re-liquefied or routed to the flare through venting.
- **Adsorber Regeneration:** Adsorbers upstream of the cryogenic liquefaction section are regenerated with heat and purified hydrogen. Contaminated regeneration hydrogen is routed to the flare. Losses from adsorber to flare are up to 0.5% of feed.
- **Tanks loading procedure:** if pressure accumulation method is used and there is no boil-off hydrogen management system, there will be potential hydrogen releases during pressure relief.

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Fugitive Losses via Flanges/Valves (Warm Hydrogen Feed Supply):** Potential fugitive losses in warm hydrogen feed supply via compressor and at control valve shaft connections. These are minor losses, below the detection limit of the system.

5.3.2. Regasification

After the liquid hydrogen is transported via ships or trucks to its destination, it undergoes regasification to be converted into gaseous form. When compared to the liquefaction and transport steps, regasification is both less costly and less energy intensive. The thermal energy needed for regasification can be provided by the environment and the only additional energy required are for pumping the liquid hydrogen.

For typical on-site supply of Hydrogen, liquid Hydrogen from storage tank is routed via ambient air fin tube evaporators to be vaporized. In gaseous state. Hydrogen is routed to the process. If elevated hydrogen pressure is required, liquid hydrogen is pumped with a piston pump up the required pressure upstream of the fin tube evaporator. Large scale hydrogen re-gasification concepts, with integrated cold utilization concepts, are not yet commercialized.

Due to the presence of one main plant component only, the archetype has been just defined as the vaporization element. Before the vaporization process there will be a Liquid hydrogen storage unit, detailed in the “Liquid hydrogen tanks (LH₂)” chapter, for the final processing of regasified hydrogen, the plant will be connected to a demand-related hydrogen loading bay detailed in the “H₂ Compression” chapter.

Figure 24: hydrogen storage for liquified hydrogen and the compression element

The operational parameters that have been considered for the characterization of the archetype are:

Table 14: Main LH₂ regasification operational Parameters.

Parameter	Value
Operating temperatures liq. Hydrogen [K]	Down to 20 K to ambient
Operating pressure of air fin tube evaporators [bara]	1 – 40

The theoretical hydrogen emissions should be:

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Flare Scenario from Ambient Air Vaporizer:** Controlled (e.g., maintenance) or emergency depressurization of the ambient air vaporizer that requires to vent the residual hydrogen in the atmosphere. It happens with very rare frequency
- **Boil-Off Gas from Cryogenic Storage Tanks:** Hydrogen boil-off due to heat input into cryogenic storage tanks., Hydrogen can be vented or partially recovered, depending on Boil-off rate and storage tank insulation quality.

Fugitives’ emissions are mainly related to:

- **Fugitive Losses via Flanges/Valves:** Potential fugitive losses in the warm hydrogen feed supply via compressor and at control valve shaft connections as detailed in the “TYPICAL BOP ELEMENTS” chapter.

- **Pressure Relief Devices (PRDs):** Overpressure protection through controlled venting, related to the set pressure, venting frequency.

5.4. LOHC hydrogenation / dehydrogenation

LOHCs (Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers) are organic liquids designed as hydrogen carriers, meaning they are used for its storage and transport. The principle behind this method is the reversible hydrogenation, and then de-hydrogenation, of the LOHC. The hydrogenation reaction is exothermic and occurs at mid-high temperatures and pressures, while the release of hydrogen through the reverse reaction is endothermic, occurring at mid-high temperatures but at pressures close to ambient. Several molecules considered potential carriers for hydrogen transport and storage are categorized based on their molecular structure into three main groups:

- Cyclic hydrocarbons
- N-heterocyclic compounds (carbazole derivatives: N-ethyl carbazole; pyridines and quinolines, pyrroles and indoles)
- Circular hydrogen carriers (involving the formation of methanol, formic acid and hydrocarbons; ammonia and its derivatives)

Figure 25 illustrates the general LOHC process.

Figure 25: Exemplary LOHC process⁵⁸.

For the specific hydrogenation/dehydrogenation archetype characterization, the most promising LOHC with the specific storage capacities and operating pressure and temperatures for the reactions have been considered in the Table 19:

Table 19: Key parameters for most promising LOHC⁵⁹.

Parameter	Values		
Type	Dibenzyl toluene – perhydro dibenzyl toluene	N-Ethyl-Carbazole-dodecahydro–N-ethylcarbazole	Toluene–Methylcyclohexane
Storage capacity [wt%]	6.2	5.8	6.2
Hydrogenation			
Temperature [°C]	150	170	95-125
Pressure [bar]	50	70	20-40
Dehydrogenation			
Temperature [°C]	270-310	180-270	250-450
Pressure [bar]	Atm.	Atm.	3

5.4.1. Hydrogenation

In the hydrogenation process, the LOHC is pre-heated, as the reaction, although exothermic, must occur at specific temperatures for the catalyst to function correctly. Then, hydrogen is stored in the organic liquid within the hydrogenation reactor. Following this, there is a cooling and conditioning step for the hydrogenated organic liquid downstream of the reactor.

Depending on H₂ source, it may contain impurities and a purification step is required before being fed into the reactor. Purification can be carried out in various ways, depending on the state of the impurities (for example, catalytic dryers can be used to separate impurities present as vapours such as volatile amines, water vapor, carbon monoxide, and/or molecular oxygen, Desulfurization). Thanks to this step, hydrogenation doesn't depend on the source of the hydrogen.

For the characterization of the LCOH technology, mainly dibenzyl toluene/perhydro-dibenzyltoluene (H₀-DBTeH₁₈-DBT), toluene/methylcyclohexane (TOLeMCH) and N-ethyl-carbazole/dodecahydro-N-ethylcarbazole (NECeH₁₂-NEC) systems are considered.

The hydrogenation process is characterized by a catalytic reactor in which the two reactants (hydrogen and LOHC) are introduced, and from which the hydrogenated organic liquid is extracted as the product. Typically, the hydrogenation occurs at temperatures between 95 and 170°C and pressures between 20 and 70 bar as shown in Table 20.

The archetype has been defined as:

- **H₂ pre:** H₂ pretreatment and preheating unit
- **Reactor:** organic hydrogen storage liquid is mixed with raw hydrogen, heated to specific temperature under the influence of the catalyst to form the corresponding saturated hydride
- **LOHC treat:** a cooling and conditioning step for the hydrogenated organic liquid

Figure 26: General LOHC hydrogenation process

Considering the main operational parameters related to the hydrogenation process, summarized considering the main LOHC reported above:

Table 20: Main operational parameters for LOHC hydrogenation process.

Parameter	Value Range
Capacity [wt%]	5.8-6.2 wt%
Pressure [bar]	20-70 bar
Temperature [°C]	95-170 °C

The main losses related to the hydrogenation process are related to the pre-treatment system that is required if the hydrogen delivered to the LOHC plant is not pure enough. The specific parameters and losses are detailed in the “[Hydrogen Treatment Unit](#)” paragraph.

5.4.2. Dehydrogenation

Hydrogen-rich LCOH is loaded in the dehydrogenation reactor, after that it has been heated to the temperature of the dehydrogenation reaction in the oil bath. Then, hydrogen removed in the catalyst reactor is cooled, separated by a serpentine condenser, and eventually collected.

Main losses are related to the dehydrogenation phase required to reconvert the stored or transported hydrogen in LOHC form, specifically related to incomplete combustion.

Thermal energy required for dehydrogenation can be produced by burning part of the released hydrogen. This process involves a controlled combustion of a portion of the released hydrogen to generate the necessary thermal energy for dehydrogenation. The exact losses can vary and are estimated based on operational parameters and process efficiency. Estimated loss ranges between 0.1% and 1%⁶⁰.

Table 21: Main operational parameters for LOHC dehydrogenation process^{59,60}.

Parameters	Values
Pressure [bar]	Ambient – 3
Temperature [°C]	180 - 450
Compressor	Accord. To storage pressure
Pressure (H ₂ storage) [bar]	~200

5.5. e-MeOH synthesis / cracking

Methanol today plays a fundamental role in the chemical and pharmaceutical sector and in the production of synthetic hydrocarbons. Even if today the production of methanol is done mainly from steam methane reforming and coal gasification, methanol production from renewable hydrogen and other renewable sources as biomass gasification or solid waste accounts only for 0.2 Mt/year but will be a fundamental element for the production of sustainable fuels⁶¹.

5.5.1. Methanol Synthesis

The production of e-methanol from hydrogen is done through the Fischer-Tropsch process, in which CO₂ hydrogenation is typically done in fixed-bed catalytic Cu/Zn/Al-based reactor at 250–300 °C and 50–100 bar. Taking as example the CRI's George Olah Renewable Methanol Plant in Iceland, today the e-methanol plants produce around 500 kgH₂/h.

The main elements considered for the Fischer-Tropsch based e-methanol production are:

- **Feedstock unit:** union of storage, compression and mixing of hydrogen, CO₂ and unconverted gas. The mixture is compressed up to 60-70 bar and heated for the hydrogenation reactor⁶¹.
- **Hydrogenation reactor:** Chamber for the reaction, the process catalytically converts pre-heated hydrogen and CO₂ into methanol. Operates in temperature range between 250 and 300 °C and a pressure between 50 and 100 bar, typically using Cu/Zn/Al-based catalysts⁶².

$$\text{CO} + 2 \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3\text{OH}; \text{CO}_2 + 3 \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3 \text{OH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$$
- **Pipes:** Transport of the feedstocks
- **Methanol Treatment unit:** Purifies raw methanol by separating it from water and residual gases

Figure 27: Major steps of e-methanol/FT fuel production.

The main parameters that characterize the operation of these specific plants that could affect the hydrogen releases are schematized in the Table below, for all the main plant elements introduced before:

Table 22: Operational parameters of e-methanol production plant^{61,62}.

Parameters	Value Range
Feedstock Unit	
Pressure [bar]	60-70
Hydrogenation Reactor	
Reaction temperature [°C]	250-300
Reaction pressure [bar]	50-100
H ₂ /CO input molar ratio $\frac{[H_2] - [CO_2]}{[CO] + [CO_2]}$	2
General Parameters	
CH ₃ OH prod [kg/h]	Approx. 500
Lifetime [years]	4-8

The main hydrogen emissions for the specific archetype are:

- Fugitives' emissions related to the compression and storage units of H₂ and all the process BOP as pipes and valves already detailed in the "TYPICAL BOP ELEMENTS" chapter.
- Venting emissions related to about 1 % of unreacted gasses is purged and flared to reduce the accumulation of inert and undesired gas in the circuit. This purge flow slightly increases the CO₂ emissions, but its contribution (about 20 kg/h) can be assumed almost negligible, since it is around 3 % of the overall CO₂ captured from the flue gas⁶¹.

5.5.2. Methanol cracking

Methanol (CH₃OH) is a hydrogen carrier which can be processed via cracking/reforming steps to debond the hydrogen. This MeOH cracking has the advantage of lower process temperatures ranging from 200-300°C compared to methane (500°C) or thermo-catalytic water splitting⁶³, and an operating pressure of 7-30 bars.

The main chemical reaction follows

and the total reaction

The principal process includes four process steps:

- Mixing of demi-water and methanol, which is preheated and fed into the heat exchanger,

- ii) The reformer vaporizes the mixture and with help of a catalyst the water-methanol gaseous mixture reacts to the CO₂ and H₂
- iii) in the absorber including condenser, the synthetic gas is cooled (and recycled) and the hydrogen transferred to the next step
- iv) the hydrogen is optionally purified in a PSA-unit, for instance as during the steam reforming carbon monoxide can cause impurities in the final product⁶⁴. The co-product CO₂ can be either stored or used in other industrial processes (e.g. steel treatment).

Recent research focuses on improving the catalysts which enables lower reaction temperatures. Cu-based catalysts are the best economic and technical trade-off material for reforming methanol. Other catalysts include other noble or transition metals or Cu-alloys⁶⁵.

Figure 29: Process flow chart of a typical methanol cracking plant²⁵.

The selected macro elements for the archetype definition are:

- **Feedstock:** Contains a mixture of demi-water and methanol
- **Pump:** Transfers mixture to the next process unit
- **Heater/heat exchanger:** Vaporizing water/methanol mixture
- **Reformer:** Consists of a catalyst (e.g. copper) that facilitate the separation of CO₂ and H₂ at lower temperatures
- **Cooling unit:** Reduces the temperature to the operational condition for the purification, the condensate will be recycled and transferred to the water/methanol mixture storage.
- **Purification (optional):** Depending on the required purity, several purification steps are required.
- **CCS:** Excessive CO₂ can be stored

No specific releases from the methanol cracking process were highlighted, otherwise the standard releases from flanges, connections and the purification unit could be used.

6. STORAGE

Stationary hydrogen storage represents a key element in the hydrogen supply chain, enabling the balancing of geographical and temporal discrepancies between production and demand. Unlike conventional batteries, which suffer from self-discharge and capacity degradation over time and through cycles, hydrogen can store energy for extended periods while maintaining high energy density. However, hydrogen's primary challenge is its limited volumetric energy density. At standard conditions (25 °C, 1 bar), it is 0.01 MJ/L (LHV) in the gaseous phase and 8.5 MJ/L in the liquid phase. Otherwise, methane and gasoline have volumetric energy contents of 0.04 MJ/L and 32 MJ/L, respectively.

Historically, most hydrogen storage systems have utilized compressed gaseous storage and liquefied hydrogen due to the maturity and commercial availability of these technologies. Recently, new promising technologies, such as metal hydride (MH) storage and liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs), have emerged, potentially overcoming the high energy requirements associated with compressed hydrogen storage and liquefaction. Additionally, there has been a significant increase in interest in using salt caverns and porous rock formations for large-scale underground hydrogen storage, as well as in reconvert hydrogen into ammonia and methanol.

Hydrogen storage technologies with a TRL above 6 have been selected, summed up in the following:

- H₂ Compressed Tank (CH₂): Compressing hydrogen at high pressures is the most common used method for storage, stored in cylindrical and spherical tanks. Five different types of tanks (I-V type) are used, made of different materials ranging from metallic to composite material, allowing to pressurize hydrogen until 700 bar.
- Liquid hydrogen tank (LH₂): hydrogen is liquified at -253 °C which increases its density to 70.8 kg/m³ and stored in stainless steel and aluminium alloy vessels with sufficient insulation.
- Geological Storage: for long term storage, geological storage could be a feasible option, precisely salt caverns and porous rock formations are the options that now are more taken into account, allowing to store billions of Sm³ of hydrogen
- H₂-derivatives tanks: Ammonia, LOHC, methanol
- Metal hydride storage: Allowing to store higher capacities compare to compressed or liquefied hydrogen tanks, keeping low-medium operating pressures, metal hydride storage will be a fundamental hydrogen storage technology.

For all the different technologies, the most important information are introduced.

6.1. Compressed hydrogen tanks (CH₂)

Commercial gaseous H₂ storage technologies allow to store H₂ up to 700 bar or even higher. Specifically, Type I-IV tanks are adopted for the purpose⁶⁶. Furthermore, the type “V” tank configuration for pressure up to 1000 bar is available for specific applications requiring high energy density due to the limited space available (i.e., aerospace or aviation). From a construction point of view, the pressure vessels typically feature a central cylindrical section, two spherical domes, and a polar opening. In composite vessels, configurations might include polymorph or toroidal shapes. The classification of these pressure vessels is based on their construction materials and design:

- **Type I:** These are all-metal cylinders, typically made of 4130 steel or 6061 aluminium. They are robust and cost-effective but are relatively heavy and less efficient for high-pressure storage.
- **Type II:** These cylinders have a metal liner (usually 4130 steel or 6061 aluminium) reinforced with a composite wrap, typically made of fiberglass. They offer a balance between weight and cost, providing better efficiency than Type I cylinders.
- **Type III:** These have a metal liner (usually 6061 aluminium) fully wrapped with a composite material (typically carbon fiber). They are lighter and can withstand higher pressures than Type II cylinders, making them more efficient for medium-pressure applications.
- **Type IV:** These are fully composite cylinders with a non-metallic liner (usually plastic) wrapped with carbon fiber. They are extremely lightweight and can store hydrogen at very high pressures, typically up to 700 bar. They are commonly used for onboard vehicle storage and high-pressure dispensing in refueling stations.
- **Type V:** These are the newest generation of hydrogen storage, made entirely of composite materials without any liner. They offer the highest efficiency in terms of weight and pressure capacity, although they are still under development and less commonly used.

A schematic representation of the five types is indicated in Figure 28, while the main characteristics for the five types are reported in Table 23.

Figure 28: Common types of pressure vessels⁶⁷.

Table 23: Main characteristics of tank's technologies.

Parameters	Values				
	Type I	Type II	Type III	Type IV	Type V
Materials	Metals (steel or Aluminium)	Metals like type 1 + carbon fibre/glass fibre filament wrapped	Metallic liner (AA6061 or AA7000), fully wrapped with composite	Polymeric liner fully wrapped with composite	Fully composite
Nominal pressure [bar]	Aluminium: 175 Steel: 200	Aluminium + glass: 263 Steel + carbon fibre: 300	Aluminium + glass: 305 Aluminium + aramid: 438 Aluminium + carbon: 700	700	About 1000
Tank capacity [m³]	35 barg: 25-200 ⁶⁸ 70 barg: 25-100 ⁶⁸ 200-250 barg: ≤ 2.5 ⁶⁹		≤ 700 bar: up to 0.27 L ⁷⁰	250 barg: up to 1.75 ⁷¹ 700 barg: up to 0.5 ^{71,72} 900 barg: up to 0.25 ⁷¹	Up to 0.3 ⁷³
Applications	Stationary Large scale storage	Stationary Large scale storage	Prevalently automotive sector	Prevalently automotive sector	Mainly Aerospace / Aviation
Development	Market stage				Under development

Different configurations can be adopted depending on the application as listed below:

- **Ground Storage Tanks.** They are large, stationary tanks. Types I, II, III or IV are used for this application.
- **Bundle Storage Systems.** This configuration involves a series of small cylinders (Type I to Type IV) bundled together to form a large storage unit. These bundles are flexible and can be tailored to the specific capacity needs.
- **Modular Storage Units.** These units are composed of multiple Type IV cylinders integrated into a single module. They can be easily scaled up or down to match the requirements.
- **Tube Trailers.** Although primarily used for transportation, tube trailers can also serve as temporary high-pressure storage solutions. They typically consist of several high-pressure cylinders (Type II or III) mounted on a trailer.

The archetype developed by this study for large H₂ storage systems is shown in Figure 29. Generally, it includes:

- **The tanks** containing gaseous pressurized H₂.
- **Manual, control and pressure relief valves.** Specifically, pressure relief valves allow the discharge of overpressure in case of anomalies.
- **Instrumentation** to perform monitoring and data acquisition of the operative conditions.
- **The interconnecting piping (if any) and fittings** between the above-mentioned components.

Figure 29: General scheme of the compressed gaseous stationary system archetype.

The main H₂ emissions considered for large storage systems are:

- **Overpressure venting through safety valves.** Safety valves intervene when the pressure exceeds the set pressure. The instantaneous discharged flowrate of the safety valve that is selected by the designer to protect the equipment in case of malfunction or emergency is calculated through ISO 4126-1, ISO 4126-2, and IEC 60179-10. However, the total released mass during a specific period of time depends on the frequency of intervention, and the duration of the discharge.
- **Emissions from connection fittings.** Continuous emissions could occur in the case of imperfect connection and loss of seal. The amount of emission can be firstly estimated by assuming the procedure indicated in IEC 60179-10 for ATEX zone classification.
- **Emission from moving stem and seat leakage of valves.** Fugitive emission due to imperfect closing can be firstly estimated from the class of the valve as defined in IEC 60534-4:2017.
- **Tanks' purging operation.** In case of maintenance and intervention on the tank, H₂ is purged for safety reasons. Depending on the complexity of the system, purging can be directed to a flare or directly vented to the atmosphere. In the first case, the emission is equal to the amount of unburned while in the second case to the internal volume of the tank.
- **H₂ embrittlement.** H₂ embrittlement could be responsible for fugitive losses. The magnitude of the phenomenon depends on the operative conditions and tank's material.
- **H₂ permeation through tank walls.** H₂ permeation continuously occurs during service. The operative conditions (i.e., the pressure and temperature) such as the design of the tank (i.e., the material, and the surface) have to be considered when estimating the total amount of emission.

6.2. Liquid hydrogen tanks (LH₂)

The main characteristic of liquid H₂ (LH₂) storage is the high energy density compared to gaseous phase. An energy content equal to 8 MJ/L can be stored at -253 C and atmospheric pressure⁷⁴. However, dealing with LH₂ necessitates special equipment able to withstand extremely low temperatures to prevent material failure and minimize the flux of heat entering the system.

While LH₂ is non-corrosive and does not require special anti-corrosion materials, a significant challenge is the boil-off phenomenon, i.e., LH₂ evaporation, caused by heat flow from outside. The boil-off is usually declared as the percentage of LH₂ contained in the vessel that evaporates daily. To mitigate boil-off, storage vessels typically feature double walls with vacuum insulation and additional materials such as alumina-coated polyester sheets. Effective insulation and design can reduce boil-off rates to below 0.1% per day, making large LH₂ vessels more economical than compressed H₂ storage for those applications requiring a large amount of storage⁷⁵. Also, the shape of the vessel influences the boil-off magnitude. Typically, spherical tanks are preferred since they are characterized by the lowest surface area per unit volume. The Kobe LH₂ terminal consisting in 2.250 m³ of stored LH₂ designed and operated by Kawasaki is the biggest example of such storage in the world declaring to reduce the boil-off below the 0.1%/day⁷⁶.

Figure 30: Conceptual diagram of a vacuum thermal insulation structure (Left), Kawasaki operating liquefied hydrogen storage system (Right).

Also, cylindrical shape-based storage configurations are adopted. That is, different configurations can be realized depending on the specific applications in which they have to be implemented.

Also, for this type of tanks the archetype has been defined following the generic liquid/cryogenic storage vessels layout for liquid gasses^{77,78}. The archetype includes:

- **LH₂ tanks** that are generally of three types:
 - Double-jacketed tanks with liquid nitrogen on the outer jacket.
 - Super-insulated tanks with reflective powder or multi-layer insulation (Figure 31), the tanks are realized by two concentric vessels^{79,80}. To minimize heat transfer and convection phenomena, vacuum is created between the two vessels. Austenitic stainless steel is used for the inner tank while carbon steel is used for the external jacket with an anticorrosion primer and a topcoat. In the space between the internal and the external jackets,

insulating powder (perlite) is inserted. Furthermore, an adsorbent is also added to maintain the vacuum in the interspace.

- Vapor-cooled shielded (VCS) tanks employing super-insulation⁸¹.

Figure 31: super-insulated tank detail⁸⁰.

- **Shut-off device** that intervenes in the case of anomalies.
- **A boil-off system,**
- **Thermal-activated Pressure Relief Devices (TPRDs)**
- **The interconnecting piping (if any) and fittings** between the above-mentioned components.

The schematic of the archetype is shown in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata..**

Figure 32: Generic cryogenic storage vessels for liquid process gasses

The main operative parameters of LH₂ systems are shown in Table 24:

Table 24: Main LH₂ liquefaction operational parameters.

Parameter	Value	Notes
Shape	Cylindrical or spherical for very large volume ⁸⁰	-
Volume [m³]	Commercially available: up to 2.500 m ³ Designed and under development: up to 10.000 m ³	-
Typical Boil of Rate upper range [%/day]	Bulk storage ⁸¹ : ≥ 1000 m ³ (i.e., 70 ton): < 0.1 ≤100 m ³ (7 ton): < 0.9 (average value) For other capacities: < 0.3 (average value)	Boil off depends on several factors including: the shape, the installation position (horizontal vs vertical), the type of application, the type of insulation, etc. Therefore, the boil off of the specific case could result lower than that indicated as typical value.

The main H₂ emission events in LH₂ systems are represented by the boil-off. An effective management can significantly mitigate its impact. Depending on the application and plant complexity, several technological solutions are available to manage the boil off including:

- **Re-liquefaction.** When huge amount of boil off are present in the plant (e.g., on a ship or a liquefaction plant), the evaporated H₂ could be converted back to liquid. In this case, no emission theoretically occurs.
- **Used as fuel.** In industrial applications, boil-off can substitute natural gas, limiting emissions to a minimal amount of unburned combustible H₂ that is emitted into the atmosphere with the flue gases.
- **Released and burned in a flare:** boil-off can be released and burned in a flare, resulting in emissions of H₂ and some unburned gases as the previous case.
- **Released to the atmosphere:** all the boil-off will be directly released. This situation could verify in small plants where no techno-economic convenience is obtained by installing a flare or by recovering the boil off.

In addition to the boil off, similar types of emissions as for CH₄ can be considered as potentially sources of H₂.

6.3. Salt caverns/ porous rock formations

Salt caverns have been identified as potential sites for large-scale underground hydrogen storage (UHSs). UHSs are based on the same principles of the underground gas storage systems (UGSs), i.e., in the recovery of oil or gas depleted fields, aquifers and salt caverns for storage purpose⁸².

The principle of UHSs is based on the utilization of a porous underground formation covered by a proof layer (depleted field or aquifer) or to create an underground cavern (in a salt layer) for storing the gas under pressure. In UGS or UHS, usually a distinction is made between the sub-surface equipment which is the injection and withdrawal well and all its accessories, and the above-ground equipment, including wellhead, purification sections, compressors, quality and fiscal metrology plants, etc.

The general archetype of this type of storage is schematized as shown in Figure 33. As shown, the archetype includes the following blocks:

- **Wellhead:** Battery limit between the underground equipment and the sub-surface assets
- **Gas-Liquid separator:** This component ensures the separation between gas and liquid phases based on their density difference.
- **Desulphurization. Adsorption and selective oxidation**
- **TEG (Tri Ethylene Glycol) dehydration:** Dryers where first, the humid gas passes through an absorption column (tray column) where the water is absorbed by the TEG and the gas is dehydrated, secondly the TEG is recovered through a distillation step.
- **Compressors:** The compression section is installed downstream the drying section to compress the gas up to the final pressure as needed for the injection into the network. Reciprocating piston compressors are usually preferred for the purpose.
- **Pressure reducing station:** Standard equipment for the pressure control of gases.

Figure 33: General scheme of Salt caverns/ porous rock formations archetype

The gas is either injected, stored or withdrawn, so three phases could be considered in the process. However, since when the gas is stored the sub-surface assets are not in operation, only the injection and the withdrawal phases will be described.

- **Injection:** The gas coming from the network is generally compressed before being injected into storage. However, for shallow storage, the network pressure can sometimes be sufficient for gas injection without additional compression. In such cases, depending on the network pressure and storage depth, the gas can be injected directly into the subsurface using network pressure and later reintroduced into the network using a compressor.
- **Withdrawal:** The H₂ is humidified by the water vapour in the storage, ideally up to saturation conditions. This gas is dried by removing the water firstly through the gas liquid separator and secondly the dryer. The gas liquid separator is based on a difference of density process, while the dryer is based on continuous absorption / desorption process of water in TEG (TriEthylene Glycol). If the pressure of the storage is lower or close to the network pressure, the dried gas can be compressed for being injected in the network.

The parameters indicated in Table 25 are considered relevant for the archetype:

Table 25: Operational parameters for the specific geological formations.

Parameter	Min	Max
Raw volume [m³]	100 000	1 000 000
Pressure range [bar]	81 - 125	210 – 220
Salt cavern storage [x 1 000 000 Nm³]	0.8 – 1.8	60 - 100
Aquifer storage [x 1 000 000 Nm³]	475	3 000
Flow of injection [x 1 000 000 Nm³/d]	\\	2
Flow of withdrawal (if different) [Nm³/h]	storage pressure dependent	storage pressure dependent

While few demonstrators are in operation, experts agree that other operational factors could affect H₂ emissions in the atmosphere including, for example:

- Start & stop of the compressors per year (Stop&Start/y).
- Withdrawal flow (Tonm³/h).
- Frequency of tests inducing some gas releases (Number/y).
- Frequency of desulphurization adsorbent replacement (Number/y).

6.4. Metal hydride

H₂ absorption in Metal hydride (MH) is a promising solution for storage, offering several key advantages as high volumetric energy densities and improved safety thanks to low pressure chemical bond of H₂. This makes MH storage systems highly scalable and suitable for a variety of applications, ranging from residential use to large-scale seasonal storage. An additional benefit is the absence of H₂ emission during storage. However, one significant issue of the technology is their slower response time compared to batteries, making them less ideal for applications requiring immediate backup.

The fundamental reaction for transforming a metal or metal alloy into a metal hydride is expressed as:

Where Me represents the metal sorbent, MeH_x the corresponding metal hydride, and Q the heat exchanged during the reaction. This reaction is exothermic (Q > 0) during H₂ absorption and endothermic (Q < 0) during desorption.

Metal hydride storage capacity is evaluated through the gravimetric storage capacity, that is the quotient of the maximum absorbed H₂ mass and the mass of the hydride material. Therefore, the unit of measure is weight percent (wt%). The storage capacity depends on the metal hydride. In Table 26, the most promising ones at the state of the art are shown with the specific operational pressures and temperatures^{83,84}:

Table 26: Main parameters for state of the art Metal Hydrides

Parameter	Value					
Material	MgH ₂	TiFe	TiMn ₂	LaNi ₅	LiBH ₄	NaAlH ₄
Pressure [bar]	0.15 - 10	4.1	8.4	1.8	1	1
Gravimetric Storage Capacity [wt%]	7.6	1.86	1.86	1.49	18.5	7.5
Vol. energy density [kWh/dm ³]	3.67	4.03	4.09	4.12	4.08	3.20
Temperature [°C]	200 - 300	-8 – Amb.	-21	10 - 25	270 - 300	200

Metal hydrides operate exploiting the theoretical pressure plateau of the biphasic region of the mixture, precisely the steps are, following Figure 34:

- **Initial Dissolution (α Phase):** At low H₂-to-metal ratios (H/Me < 0.1), H₂ dissolves in the metal, releasing heat (an exothermic reaction)
- **Formation of Metal Hydride (β Phase):** As the concentration of H₂ and pressure increase, the formation of metal hydride becomes thermodynamically favourable. This results in the nucleation and growth of the β phase within the metallic phase. An intermediate region with coexistence of both α and β phases (α + β) is established, allowing reversible H₂ storage with minimal pressure variation

- **Completion of Transition:** With further H₂ dissolution, the transition from the mixed ($\alpha + \beta$) phase to the pure hydride (β) phase completes. Additional H₂ absorption requires progressively higher pressures.

Figure 34: Ideal Pressure-Concentration-Isotherm (PCI) (left), Van't Hoff plot (mid), Real PCI (right)⁸⁴

The archetype designed for the NHyRA project is shown in Figure 35. Despite the low TRL of the technology, the following main components are considered:

- **Tank:** Stainless steel, aluminium, or copper-based alloys.
- **H₂ absorption and desorption circuit:** It consists of a line for H₂ withdrawal (in the case of absorption), with auxiliary elements including valves, pressure transducers, thermocouples, pressure indicators, pressure reducers, flow meters, and regulators.
- **Purge and inerting circuit:** The supply and return lines must have appropriate tubing and fittings for cleaning the lines with inert gas before use, such as nitrogen or argon. Additional components connected by the tubing through the use of appropriate fittings include inert gas cylinders (nitrogen or argon), check valves, manual valves, and pressure reducers.
- **Heat management circuit:** Presence of a primary heating/cooling system for the absorption and desorption phases. Specific elements include heating/cooling systems, manual intercept valves, check valves, automatic valves, safety valves, heat exchangers, pumps, and pressure and temperature sensors.

Figure 35: General Layout of a MH storage system.

While the few examples of applications mostly refer to laboratory scale, only reasonable assumptions can be performed at the state of the art about real emissions expected in real industrial cases. H₂ emissions in metal hydride systems are assumed to be influenced by:

- **Incomplete absorption or desorption.** H₂ losses can occur due to incomplete absorption or desorption within the metal hydride tanks. Typically, a small amount of H₂ remains in the metal hydride material, potentially resulting in a minor emission source.
- **Activation process.** The activation process of metal hydrides, which is necessary to bring the metal to its maximum H₂ capacity and improve hydriding/dehydriding kinetics, can also lead to H₂ losses. Activation involves the penetration of H₂ into the metal, which depends on the surface structures and barriers like dissociation catalytic species and oxide films. A second stage of activation includes internal cracking of metal particles to increase the reaction surface area. This process usually requires H₂ fluxes at higher temperatures and pressures compared to operational conditions, consisting of cooling and heating cycles under a H₂ atmosphere.
- **Hydrogen purging and inerting.** During the purging and inerting process, incomplete purging of H₂ lines with inert gas (such as nitrogen or argon) before use can lead to H₂ mixing with the inert gas and subsequent emissions from the storage. However, the total emission into the atmosphere, as for LH₂, depends on how the mixture is treated

Fugitive emissions are another source of hydrogen loss and are mainly related to:

- **Fugitive losses via flanges/valves.** Potential fugitive emissions can occur in the fittings and in the components that connect the main components of the storage system, as evaluated in the “Balance of Plant Process Elements” paragraph.
- **Pressure Relief Devices (PRDs).** The same considerations indicated for safety valve in the CH₂ section apply.

6.5. LOHC

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs) present an emerging alternative for stationary storage, offering a solution for storing surplus energy, although they are not competitive compared to traditional technologies for seasonal storage from an economic point of view yet.

Once the LOHC is hydrogenated, the H₂-rich liquid can be stored in established crude-oil infrastructures. Due to the relatively high heat required for debonding the H₂ from its carrier, NHyRA project assumes that during storage and transport no H₂ emissions occur⁸⁵. The most crucial steps in the supply chain are the interfaces between conventional hydrogen storage - hydrogenation – transportation –dehydrogenation – conventional hydrogen storage/use, particularly those steps in which hydrogen is available in its free form already evaluated in the “LOHC hydrogenation / dehydrogenation” paragraph.

Due to lack of projects and activities on LOHC carrier for storage applications, has been decided that will be considered chemical and product tankers as storage solutions, specifically product tankers, which are a type of oil tanker, carry refined oil and are often designed to carry chemical cargoes as well, and may be capable of transporting LOHCs. Chemical tankers typically range in size from 5 000 to 35 000 deadweight tonnage (dwt), while product tankers range in size from 35 000 to 120 000 dwt⁸⁶.

Focusing on the specific storage and transport archetype the main technical parameters are reported in Table 27:

Table 27: LOHC storage, mineral oil-like.

Parameters	Values	
Type of tanks	Chemical Tankers	Product tankers
Capacity [Deadweight ton.]	5'000-35'000 ⁸⁶	35'000-120'000 ⁸⁶
Pressure [bar]	1 ^{60,85} bar	1 ^{60,85} bar
Temperature [C]	25 ⁶⁰ °C	25 ⁶⁰ °C

The main emission sources expected for this archetype are assumed to be in the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes, already evaluated in the “5.4. LOHC hydrogenation / dehydrogenation” paragraph.

6.6. Others

In addition to the evaluated storage methods, H₂ can also be stored by converting it into other mature energy vectors such as ammonia and e-methanol. These substances are already widely used in specific sectors and offer alternative methods for H₂ storage and transport.

Ammonia and methanol storage solutions are simply introduced in this report because of no emissions of pure H₂ is expected during their storage period. Otherwise, the main losses related to the specific H₂ supply chains have been evaluated in the “NH₃ synthesis/cracking” and “

e-MeOH synthesis / cracking” paragraphs in which the conversion and reconversion steps could be responsible for specific emissions.

6.6.1. Ammonia

Ammonia storage benefits from the extensive experience and technological maturity gained through decades of use in the fertilizer industry. Ammonia is a viable H₂ carrier due to its high energy density (i.e., 124 kg_{H₂}/m³ NH₃) in its liquid phase. Furthermore, conversion and reconversion processes (Haber-Bosch synthesis and ammonia cracking) are well established industrial processes. There are two primary methods for storing liquid ammonia⁸⁷:

1. Compression to 8 bars and storage at ambient temperature: This method is suitable for small (<270 ton_{NH₃}) and intermediate-scale (450-2,700 ton_{NH₃}) storage. The upper range is usually limited due to the cost referred to the compression of ammonia.
2. Refrigeration to -33°C: This approach is used for larger capacities where the cost of the refrigeration system is justified by the size of the plant. The process is performed at around atmospheric pressure, avoiding the need for expensive pressurization. Refrigerated tanks typically employ one or two layers of insulation materials to maintain low temperatures efficiently minimizing heat transfer from the environment.

These methods are chosen based on the quantity of ammonia to be stored. While compression is more suitable for smaller volumes, refrigeration becomes more economical for larger storage capacities.

6.6.2. e-Methanol

Methanol (CH₃OH) is a liquid organic-chemical substance commonly used as a raw material in various industrial sectors, such as the chemical, plastics, and rubber industries (CAS 67-56-1)⁸⁸. It is characterized by its flammability and acute toxicity upon exposure, although it is biodegradable in the environment. Methanol's low flashpoint of approximately 11°C at atmospheric pressure necessitates stringent safety standards for its storage.

Standard storage methods for methanol are similar to those used for gasoline, kerosene, and other easily flammable substances. Methanol is typically stored in tank farms with above-ground, floating roof tanks, and smaller, internally baffled floating baffle tanks.

7. TRANSPORTATION

To achieve the decarbonization targets of Europe's energy system by 2050 and support the transition across various sectors, including industry, heating, and mobility, hydrogen must be delivered in the most efficient manner tailored to specific production-consumption supply chains. Effective delivery of hydrogen is crucial for ensuring its widespread production and utilization.

For this reason, multiple hydrogen transportation solutions related to the ways of transporting hydrogen (truck, ship, rails and pipelines) are considered in correlation with the specific quantities and distances required to connect producers and consumers. Indeed, the latest two parameters significantly influence the preferred transportation method due to the need to minimize the levelized cost of transport (LCOT) of hydrogen. Figure 36 from IRENA's report "Global Hydrogen Trade to Meet the 1.5°C Climate Goal: Part II"⁸⁷, illustrates the optimal transport solutions based on distances and volumes.

Figure 36: hydrogen transport technologies overview⁸⁷

For the purposes of this work the main widespread transport solutions have been selected:

- **Transmission & Distribution hydrogen grid:** Hydrogen pipelines are a cost-effective method for transporting large volumes of hydrogen over long distances. These pipelines can either be dedicated hydrogen pipelines or repurposed natural gas pipelines. This method is particularly efficient for connecting hydrogen production facilities with industrial hubs or large-scale users.
- **Compressed hydrogen tank (Tank I-IV) (CH₂):** widely used for short to medium-distance transportation. They operate at high pressures (up to 700 bar) to maximize the hydrogen storage capacity. These tanks are typically transported by trucks and can be an effective solution for distributing hydrogen to fuelling stations or industrial sites.
- **Liquid hydrogen tank (LH₂):** involve cryogenic cooling of hydrogen to -253°C. This method significantly increases the volumetric energy density of hydrogen, making it suitable for long-distance transportation. Liquid hydrogen tanks are used in trucks, ships, and railcars designed to handle cryogenic temperatures.

- **Hydrogen carriers (Ammonia, LOHC, methanol):** Hydrogen carriers such as ammonia, LOHCs, and methanol provide alternative methods for hydrogen transport. These carriers can be transported using conventional shipping and trucking infrastructure. Upon reaching their destination, the hydrogen is released from the carrier through chemical processes.

The listed technologies have been chosen for their relevance and potential in different contexts of hydrogen transportation. While some of these technologies are also used for storage, this chapter focuses on their transportation aspects. When possible, these technologies will be evaluated in terms of their main utilization distances and specific information necessary for defining hydrogen emissions.

7.1. Transmission & Distribution Grid

Gaseous hydrogen can be transported through pipelines in a manner similar to that of natural gas. The first hydrogen pipeline was reportedly built in the 1930s in Germany. According to the global gas report 2020, there are about 1.4 million km of natural gas pipeline worldwide, and only 4'542 km of hydrogen pipelines, primarily in the US and Europe, with most being small pipelines operated by industrial hydrogen producers⁸⁹. The big advantage of hydrogen transportation through pipelines is the possibility to deliver high quantity of hydrogen for long distances. Thus, pipelines appear the most attractive⁸⁷ transport solutions for distances of 3'000-7'000 km by land,. Interesting new projects of hydrogen European backbones as for example, "H2Med", or "HyPerLink" with a capacity of 10 GW confirm the intent to establish an extensive hydrogen transport and distribution network in Europe.

The possibility of exploiting existing gas infrastructure, both repurposing it or blending H₂ with natural gas, could allow to spread easily and rapidly the use of hydrogen. Nevertheless, there are some technical challenges to overcome for the use of hydrogen in transmission and distribution, such as:

- Lower volumetric energy density of hydrogen compared to methane/natural gas, implying a third of energy transported for the same volume amount
- Hydrogen embrittlement of steel and welds used in pipeline fabrication, generating faster growth of cracks
- The need to control hydrogen permeation and prevent leaks, mainly for polymeric pipelines

The gas network consists of interconnected objects that transport and distribute gases, including pipelines with equipment to transfer gas to consumers. There are different classifications based on gas overpressure, gas speed, and pipe material, with pipelines made of polyethylene or steel. Gas stations within the network serve functions like pressure reduction, stream measurement, and gas division. Compressor stations increase gas pressure to compensate for frictional losses, and gas storage is used for inter-seasonal demand fluctuations.

On average the diameters of the distribution and transmission grid range from 50 to 250 mm. Pipelines are made in low X-grades API 5L materials, with an operating pressure ranging from 30 up to 150 bars. Nevertheless, greater pipeline diameters, up to 1000 mm, are foreseen as decarbonization process move forward with high X-grades API 5L materials.

In general, a complete hydrogen/natural gas transmission line is made of:

- **Gathering line:** pipelines for collection and transport of hydrogen from production plants to treatment and high-pressure grid injection plants, characterized by short length and small diameter with variable pressure ranges.
- **Transmission line:** consisting of compressor stations that include multiple reciprocating or centrifugal compressors (usually placed at 100-200 km intervals along the pipeline) and pipeline characterize by high pressure operation (from 25 up to 150 bars) and high diameters (reaching over 1000 mm diameters) for natural gas distribution, allowing the blending from 5 to 15%⁹⁰ of hydrogen. They connect the gathering line to large consumers or to the pressure and metering

station for final distribution. Eventually, gas storage facilities to balance supply-demand discrepancies can be present.

- **Pressure reduction and metering stations:** Pressure reduction and metering stations in a gas grid ensure the safe and efficient delivery of natural gas by lowering its pressure to suitable levels for distribution and accurately measuring gas flow for billing and operational purposes.
- **Distribution line:** key objective of this line is to deliver gas to small consumers; the operational parameters for pressure and diameter usually space between 5 - 0.05 bar and 400 – 40 mm.

Figure 37: General Hydrogen transmission pipeline.

For the definition of the archetype, the following items are separately considered:

- High pressure transmission pipeline: Operates at high pressure, transporting gas over long distances. Characterized of large diameter pipes, compression stations and Block valve station sites.
- Pressure station and metering station (city gate stations): installations for final distribution and use of hydrogen.
- Gas Distribution system: Mains and service lines including piping above and below ground and all other equipment necessary to supply the gas to the consumer

7.1.1. High pressure transmission pipeline

Transmission pipelines are the large lines that move natural gas over long distances across the country. They typically have diameters ranging from 6 to 48 inches. These pipelines operate at high pressures (Italian network controlled by SNAM spa work around 70 bar(a)), although there is uncertainty about what the operational pressure of the future H_2 lines will be. In Spain future hydrogen transmission pipeline will

operate with a pressure of the future transmission network at 80-100 bar, with pipeline DN of 30". Higher pressures will be used only for offshore pipelines.

Transport line has some building blocks as:

- **Block valve station:** where the main Line valves are located. The main purpose of these facilities is to block the pipeline in case of an incident and blowdown, in safety conditions, the inventory of gas trapped in the pipeline section between two stations. In these stations there are several valves, a vent, and instrumentation to monitor the status of the pipeline. Normally the main valves are remotely operated, while the auxiliary valves are manually operated. There are several types of actuators, including: pneumatic, electric and pneumo-hydraulic actuators.
- **Pipeline:** diameters of the distribution and transmission grid pipeline range on average from 50 to 250 mm. they are made in low X-grades API 5L materials, with an operating pressure ranging from 30 up to 150 bars. Nevertheless, pipeline in high X-grades API 5L material with greater diameters, up to 1000 mm, are foreseen as the decarbonization process move forward
- **Compression station:** required to compress the gas to allow it flowing downstream to its destination. The main components of the compression station are shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38: General compression station layout

They include:

- 1) centrifugal or reciprocating compressors in a single or multiple configurations, depending on the pipeline needs. These compressors can be driven by either electric motors or gas turbines, depending on the specific requirements and infrastructure of the gas grid.;
 - 2) scrubbers and filters to knock out water and impurities from the gas stream,
 - 3) yard piping for the gas to enter and exit the station. Emergency Shutdown Valve (ESD): Used to shut down the system in emergencies or overpressure situations.
- **Slug Catcher:** adopted to handle the large volume of fluid pushed into the station by devices like "pigs" used for cleaning pipelines.

7.1.2. Pressure reducing and metering station (city gates)

Pressure reducing and metering station (city gates) represented in Figure 39 consist of a facility that receives high-pressure H₂ from the transportation system and reduces it to an appropriate pressure for local distribution. It is also responsible for measuring the quantity of gas supplied to end users.

The main operations that characterize this element are:

- High-pressure natural gas/H₂ enters the Energy Recovery Module (ERM).
- The filter removes impurities.
- The regulator reduces the pressure to a safe level for local distribution.
- The meter measures consumption.
- Odorized gas is sent to the distribution network.

Flowrate and operational pressures are currently unknown.

Figure 39: Pressure reducing and metering stations (city gates).

The main elements of in the pressure reducing and metering station are shown in Figure 39. They include:

- Inlet/outlet valves: to control the flow of gas to and from the station.
- Filter: to remove particles and contaminants from the gas before distribution
- Pressure regulator: to decrease the pressure, as required to supply the gas to the distribution grid.
- Meter: to measure the amount of gas supplied.
- Odorization system (if applicable): to add a characteristic odour to the gas to detect leaks.
- Safety valve: to interrupt the gas flow in case of emergency.

7.1.3. Distribution grid

Gas distribution systems are defined as systems operating below 25 bars. It is worth pointing out that the actual pressure differs depending on the country, but generally do not exceed 16 bar. Typically, pipes have diameters ranging from 0.75 to 24 inches.

The system boundaries are highlighted in Figure 40. The main element which characterizes the distribution grid is the gate station, a distribution facility located adjacent to a transmission facility where pressure reduction first occurs and the hydrogen flows through a splitter system for distribution to different districts or areas. The gas is often metered, heated, and odourised at this point. These stations may have multiple metering and pressure regulating runs. Gate stations are also typically the custody transfer point between transmission and distribution.

Figure 40: System Boundaries of the Distribution Grid

Evaluating the main Hydrogen emissions in transmission and distribution grids that can occur.

Fugitives' emission are mainly related to:

- Leaks due to connections / loss of tightness: they could be present at above ground equipment (city gates, compressor stations, block valves etc.). Fugitives occur if permeation/steel degradation is happening or there are problems at the welded points of the pipe or at the different equipment involved in the infrastructure. KiWA study recommends assuming that hydrogen leaks are twice the rate of natural gas (in mass). Since it is difficult to establish data for methane grids, emission levels for fugitives are mostly confidential. For an initial approximation, data reported in table 3 of the IPPCC report with TIER 1 emission factors⁹¹ could be adopted.

Vented emissions are mainly related to:

- Purging / venting: they are present for works, process, commissioning and decommissioning including works, maintenance, renewal.
- Regular emissions of devices: pneumatic emission actuators, flow control valves, measurement equipment, compressors, seals
- Starts & stops: emissions from start and stops of equipment. They are present at compressor stations.
- Incidents: they could happen, e.g. when a pipe is accidentally broken.

Generic emission factors for natural gas transmission are 72 000 - 133 000 kg CH₄/PJ. Similar values can be used for the moment for H₂ as similar processes are involved⁹²

Incomplete combustion emissions are mainly related to:

Unburned hydrogen in exhaust gases from combustion devices related to the turbines of the compressor stations. For NG, IPCC recommends to use 1 kg/TJ (LHV)⁹³. Similar values can be used as initial values for hydrogen, to be adapted based in the results in WP3 measurements.

7.2. Compressed hydrogen tank (Tank III-IV) (GH₂)

Compressed hydrogen can be transported by both pipelines and mobile storage tanks. The latter has the advantage of delivering hydrogen into areas where pipelines are not applicable due to economic or technical reasons. Currently, for short/medium distances and reduced hydrogen demand (<10 ton/day)⁸⁷, compressed gaseous storage transport is still a standard.. The typical transport mode is primarily via road and can be also extended to rail or sea if the infrastructure allows the handling of hydrogen⁹⁴.

Generally, five types of tanks exists, as already detailed in the “Compressed hydrogen tanks (CH₂” paragraph^{95,96}. They basically differ in the technical setup and material selection. Moving from type I to type V, higher gas pressures are allowed, increasing the gravimetric density of hydrogen and reducing the transport weight⁹⁵. Indeed, for lorry transport the overall weight is a crucial parameter, which is why certain storage types can be more beneficial than others depending on the transport distance, total cost of the storage tank and the maximal load capacity⁹⁷. In lorry transport, the type III is the standard technology, whereas type IV can store hydrogen under higher pressure, which in turn is expressed in comparably higher costs for compression and tank itself but higher density. The type I and II storage tanks are used in stationary application storage⁹⁷ Type V still is in an early technological development stage and thus it is omitted in this analysis. Consequently, this section will focus only on the type III and IV, whose main parameters are summarized in Table 28

Table 28: Main Parameters describing type III and type IV tanks for compressed hydrogen transport

Parameters	Values	
	Type III	Type IV
Technology	Type III	Type IV
Typical Pressure [bar]	200	500-700
Temperature [°C]	273	273
H₂ quantity [kg]	300-500	Up to 1000

Road transport in tube trailer (where each tube has a maximal loading of 300 or 1000 kg of hydrogen, respectively for type III and type IV) is the state of the art for compressed hydrogen transport⁹⁴..Two examples are reported in the Figure 41, These solutions have the following characteristics:

- $\Phi = 559$ mm (for each tube)
- Capacity (total): 22879 liters, i.e., 1.9 m³/bottle
- Pressure: up to 300 bar
- Estimated H₂ content: 535 kg (assuming to work at 300 bar and 40 C)

Figure 41: State of the art vehicle for transport of compressed hydrogen (Linde & Air Liquide).

The archetype for compressed hydrogen tank transport is schematized in Figure 42 and includes the following elements:

- **Thermally activated pressure relieve device (TRPD):** it opens the valve if critical pressure/temperature is surpassed
- **Valves:** for charging / discharging operations
- **Boss:** connection of storage vessel and external valve (type IV and V)
- **Storage Container:** Series of cylindrical tanks

Figure 42: General Hydrogen transportable tank layout, made of multiples cylinders⁹⁸

Hydrogen release causes re mostly the same as for the stationary storage case. However, higher releases related to the loading and unloading phases are present because of the more frequent number of charge/discharge cycles compared to stationary ones.

emissions during specific operations are:

- **Loading:** once the loading is completed, all the valves on the bottles are closed and the fluid is discharged until the pressure is down to 0 barg to depressurize the system. The leaks amount is related to the Volume of the auxiliary tubing of the tanks system.
- **Unloading:** the pressure of the fluid in the tubing should be 0 barg before to disconnect the connection. Therefore, it seems that no losses occur during the unloading.
- In case of over temperature or pressure, the tube trailers vessels are equipped with safety equipment's that will purge the entire amount of hydrogen contained inside of the vessel (Pressure Relief Valve and/or rupture discs)

7.3. Liquid hydrogen tank (LH₂)

LH₂ tanks are used for inter-city and inter-continental distances (>1000 km) and volumes from few tons per day up to thousands of tons per day through shipping transport, which in turn is accompanied with higher technical efforts to maintain hydrogen in liquid state.

In this section, only the transportable storage tanks (trailer for road and rail, ships) are described. Additional processes such the liquefaction and regasification are not included here since they are part of the related liquefaction/regasification archetype description.

The full LH₂transport process includes the following 4 steps⁹⁹:

- Step 1 - At liquification plant: trailer vents the remaining load in the trailer, which can be recirculated to the liquification plant until trailer pressure is at 2-4 psig (0.14 - 0.28 bar)
- Step 2 – Filling of trailer: filling takes 3-6 hours potential hydrogen releases are recirculated to the plant
- Step 3 – Transport: boil off losses occurs. As already said for stationary applications in LH₂ paragraph, boil off is the most important characteristic phenomenon of this technology to take into account. There are some approaches to minimize the amount of boil off, but at the end some emission will occur.
- Step 4 – unloading at the HRS: trailer is firstly pressurized with vaporizer (minimal 20 psi, i.e. 1.38 bar). If the pressure in the trailer is too high at the HRS, hydrogen is vented away, which is considered as losses. Some hydrogen is used to purge and precool the pipes/valves. The filling is started at the bottom of the receiving vessel. The stationary storage is filled by up to 90% and the refill process is monitored either by mass check (balance) or meter. The purging/precooling can be estimated by comparing the trailer weight at the beginning and the end of filling the stationary station. Emission during the connection of the plug-sockets in the station can be present.

The loading and unloading procedures are schematized in Figure 43

Figure 43: General trailer loading and unloading terminals¹⁰⁰

The archetype for liquified hydrogen transport has been categorized with the following main elements¹⁰¹, shown in Figure 44:

- **Insulated liquefied hydrogen storage container:** Storage consists of double layer with high vacuum limiting the heat exchange
- **Shut off devices**
- **Boil-off system:** Managing and enabling the boil off
- **Pressure Relief Devices:** Risk mitigation
- **Level gauge:** Quantifying the filling level
- **Electric or heat exchanger:** enabling faster extractions
- **Interconnecting piping**

Figure 44: Liquid Hydrogen Storage System¹⁰¹.

The technical parameters for LH₂ transport depend on the different transport vector (trailer ship, or rail) and are summarized in Table 29.

Table 29: Operating parameter for liquified hydrogen related to the different transport vectors

Parameters	unit	Trailer	Ship	Rail	Notes
Temperature	°C	-253 ^{101,102}	-253 ^{101,102}	-253 ^{101,102}	Ship transport in experimental stage
Density	kg H ₂ /m ³	~70 ¹⁰²		~70 ¹⁰²	
Cycling	Days-weeks				Preferable short due to boil off losses ¹⁰²
Maximal filling capacity	[%]	90 ⁹⁹	90 ⁹⁹	90 ⁹⁹	
Pressure	bar	<=12		Like trailer	Ship transport only one prototype worldwide

					available (SUISO)
Quantity	kg @ 0.14 barg	<= 4'500 (large) <= 2'100 (urban)	1'250 kL – SUISO frontier by Kawasaki In the future up to 10000 ton H ₂ ¹⁰¹		
Normal evaporation rate (NER)	%	< 0.5-0.8	0.3%/day for the smaller ¹⁰³		
Filling time	h	3-6			
Discharging time (depending on size)	h	0.75-2			
Trailer, pressure during transport	bar	1.4-4.1			Depending on duration, temperature,
Trailer, pressure during filling at Liq plant	bar	0.14 - 0.28			
Trailer, pressure during unloading at HRS plant	bar	Min 2.0			
HRS/receiving vessel, initial pressure during delivery		2.0			

The main hydrogen losses and releases identified for the transportation of hydrogen through liquid hydrogen tanks are listed in the following.

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Boil-Off Gas from Tanks:** Hydrogen boil-off due to heat ingress into tanks. That can be vented or partially recovered. These losses are related to Boil-off rate, storage tank insulation quality, ambient temperature. Approximately 0.5%/day (trailer) and approximately 0.3%/day (ship), in shipping case, the BOG will be used to power the ship⁷⁴. Hydrogen boil-off up to roughly 5% also occurs when unloading the liquid hydrogen on delivery⁷⁸

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Fugitive losses via Flanges/Valves:** Potential fugitive losses in the hydrogen feed line.
- **Fugitive losses related to sloshing phenomenon:** Potential damage of the tank wall and additional boil off by heating (dissipated kinetic energy).
- **Fugitive losses related to flashing phenomenon:** Occurs during transfer from high to low pressure tank
- **Fugitive losses related to thermal stratification and overfilled:** Replaced gas losses during filling

7.4. LOHC

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHC) provide an effective method for hydrogen storage and transportation, minimizing potential losses. Unlike traditional storage methods like compressed hydrogen (CH₂) or liquid hydrogen (LH₂), LOHCs chemically bind hydrogen to various carriers. This approach offers several benefits due to the favourable physical properties of LOHCs, making them easier to handle during both storage and transport. With low melting points (< 30°C) and high boiling points (> 300°C), LOHCs can be stored and transported at room temperature^{85,104}.

In the “LOHC hydrogenation / dehydrogenation” paragraph, the most promising LOHC have been listed, detailing the specific storage capacities and operating pressure and temperatures for the reactions⁵⁹. They are:

- Dibenzyl toluene – perhydro dibenzyl toluene
- N-Ethyl-Carbazole-dodecahydro–N-ethylcarbazole
- Toluene–Methylcyclohexane

LCOH allows hydrogen transportation for both long and short distances, respectively by truck and by ship:

- **Road Transport:** Road tankers approved for transporting liquids and flammable substances (class 3, GHS), can be used for LOHC transport. These tankers usually have multiple compartments, allowing them to carry both loaded and unloaded LOHC material simultaneously, if needed. The maximum cargo for these tankers is limited by the gross vehicle weight, with a net load capacity of 28.5 tons. With a storage density of 5.3 wt%, an LOHC trailer can carry about 1,500 kg of hydrogen⁸⁶.
- **Sea Transport:** LOHC transportation by sea can utilize existing ships and port infrastructure, making it a feasible option. Tankers are classified by their size in deadweight tonnage (dwt), from small tankers (10,000 dwt) to ultra-large crude carriers (up to 550,000 dwt). Product tankers, which are a type of oil tanker, carry refined oil and are often designed to carry chemical cargoes as well, and may be capable of transporting LOHCs. Chemical tankers typically range in size from 5 000 to 35 000 dwt, while product tankers range in size from 35 000 to 120 000 dwt. Considering transportation distances, 'Handysize' (10,000-30,000 dwt) and 'Handymax' (30,000-45,000 dwt) tankers are practical options⁸⁶.

Parameters that characterising LOHC road and sea transport are summarized in Table 30^{60,86}:

Table 30: Characteristic parameters for LOHC transport

Parameters	Road Transport	Sea Transport
Tanks	class 3, GHS tanks	Product Tanks (crude oil)
H₂ quantity	Up to 1500 kg	10000-45000 dwt
Pressure [bar]	1	1
Temperature [°C]	25	25

Thanks to the stable chemical bond with the LOHC, negligible losses during the transportation and storage phases are expected. The main losses are in the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes, already evaluated in the “LOHC hydrogenation / dehydrogenation” paragraph.

7.5. Others (Ammonia & Methanol)

There are others forms of transporting hydrogen, mainly converting it in others mature energy vectors already utilized in specific sectors. Two of them are in ammonia and methanol (MeOH).

Ammonia and methanol transport solutions have not been evaluated in detail because, being other elements than hydrogen, they do not create hydrogen emission/losses during storing and transport. The main losses related to the specific hydrogen supply chains have been evaluated in the “NH₃ synthesis/cracking” and “

e-MeOH synthesis / cracking” paragraphs in which the conversion and reconversion of hydrogen could generate specific losses.

7.5.1. Ammonia

As for the storage cases, ammonia tanks benefit from the maturity of the technology conferred by the extensive trade that this carrier has witnessed in the past decades mainly for the fertilizers sector. Ammonia is a feasible way of storing hydrogen thanks to the mature conversion and reconversion process (described in “NH₃ synthesis / cracking” chapter). Additionally, ammonia presents high energy density of 124 kg_{H₂}/m³_{NH₃} in its liquid form.

There are two main adopted solutions to transport liquid ammonia⁸⁷

1. The compression of the ammonia to 8 bar
2. The refrigeration of ammonia to -33°C, around atmospheric pressure

The adoption of the two solutions is straightly related to the amount of stored ammonia in tanks. Compression is used for small (< 270 tonNH₃) and intermediate scale (450-2,700 tonNH₃). Limited by the cost of pressurizing ammonia for bigger capacities. For higher capacities, refrigerated tanks avoid the use of steel by employing either one or two layers of insulation materials.

7.5.2. e-Methanol

Methanol (CH₃OH) is a liquid organic-chemical substance with the formula at ambient temperature. It is used in several industrial sectors for example as a chemistry raw material, plastics and rubber (CAS 67-56-1)⁸⁸. It is characterized as easily flammable, acute toxic when exposed to, but biodegradable in the environment. Due to its low flashpoint of approximately 11°C, the transport of methanol has to fulfil certain safety standards. In Europe the ADR, RID, ADN and IMDG standards regulate the transport of methanol on road, rail, inland transport via water and sea, respectively. Generally, standard tanks and trailers can be used for transport similarly to gasoline, kerosene or other easily flammable substances.

For ship transport¹⁰⁵, the loading of the tanker ships is done by using pumped pipes/hose transferring the methanol from dockside storage to the ship tanks. The dockside storage is filled by means like pipelines, barge, rail or truck tanks. Also, the sea transport of methanol is similar to other hydrocarbon liquids. The vessels are double hulled, which have to be clean to avoid contamination of methanol. Furthermore, devices for methanol leak detection, firefighting equipment as well as equipment for loading and unloading the vessel at the destination port. Both rail and road transport of methanol are similar. The tanks have to be equipped with pressure relieve devices, top and bottom valves.

8. END-USERS & APPLICATIONS

H₂ is already a key element in various industrial processes. Between 2020 and 2022, H₂ usage was estimated to be in the range of 80-100 Mton/year¹⁷.

Figure 45: H₂ use by sector¹⁷.

As shown in Figure 45, the greatest amount of H₂ is currently used in the following sectors:

1. **Refining sector.** Approximately 80% of the total consumption is produced onsite through SMR, while the remaining part is produced as a by-product from other processes such as hydrocracking and hydrotreating. Hydrocracking converts heavy, low-quality gas oils into more valuable fuels like diesel, gasoline, and jet fuel. Hydrotreating process reduces sulphur and other contaminants' content.
2. **Ammonia production.** The second-largest use of H₂ is in the production of ammonia via the Haber-Bosch process for fertilizer production.
3. **Chemical and steel sectors.** H₂ is also used for methanol and Direct Reduced Iron (DRI) production respectively in the chemical and in the steel sectors.

To decarbonize the industrial sector, there will be an increased focus on utilizing low-emission H₂ and expanding its applications, particularly in hard-to-abate sectors. Precisely, H₂ is expected to replace traditional fossil fuels as a source of high/mid temperature processes, including also those in the cement and glass sectors.

In accordance with published H₂ strategies, the archetypes for other final end-uses including heating and cooling and power generation are included in the deliverable¹⁰⁶. Since they have been already indicated in other sections, other potential final uses including the production of hydrogen-based fuels are not repeated in this section.

The archetypes for the following end-uses are reported in the next sections of the report:

1. Industrial Processes

- Refinery sector: Hydrogen used in hydrodesulphurization, hydrocracking processes for the production of fuels.
- Nitrogen-based fertilizers production: Hydrogen is used for ammonia production.
- Steel industry: Used mainly in the Direct reduced iron (DRI) based steel production.

2. Transport

- Hydrogen Refuelling stations (HRS)
- E-fuels: hydrogen coupled with CO₂ from Carbon capture, utilization and storage technology can be used for the synthesis of natural gas and methanol and methane
- Vehicles: For hydrogen-based vehicles will be both considered Fuel cell-based vehicles and internal combustion engines ones, both powered by hydrogen

3. Electricity generation:

- Fuel Cells (FCs)
- Gas turbines

4. Thermal

- High temperature heating for industry
- Low enthalpy distributed heating (es. Residential Boilers)

8.1. Industrial Process

In this paragraph, the main sectors and associated technologies where H₂ is used as a chemical agent are introduced.

8.1.1. Refining Sector

H₂ use in refining reached over 41 million tons (Mt) in 2022¹⁷. Under the Net Zero Emissions (NZE) Scenario, this demand is expected to decrease, aiming for less than 35 Mt by 2030, due to a shift away from increasing demand for oil products. In refineries, H₂ serves crucial roles, functioning as a catalyst to stimulate chemical reactions and as a process by-product, indicating the need for critical actions based on its concentration.

In Figure 46, a simplified flow diagram of the primary H₂ involved processes in refineries is shown. In Table 31, instead, the key operating parameters describing the general archetype are indicated. That is, the following processes can be identified in a typical refinery¹⁰⁷:

Figure 46: General Hydrogen-involved processes in a refinery plant.

- **Hydrotreating (HDT).** This process removes contaminants like sulphur, nitrogen, oxygen, and metals from petroleum products to produce cleaner fuels like low-sulphur gasoline and diesel, naphtha, and kerosene.
- **Hydrocracking (HCK).** It breaks down heavy hydrocarbon molecules into lighter, more valuable fractions like gasoline and diesel producing high-quality gasoline, jet fuel, and diesel.
- **Hydrodesulfurization (HDS).** The process targets the removal of sulphur from diesel and gasoline fractions to meet ultra-low sulphur fuel standards producing ultra-low-sulphur diesel (ULSD) and gasoline.

- **Catalytic Reforming (CR).** It increases the octane number of naphtha to produce high-octane reformat for gasoline blending producing high-octane gasoline components. H₂ is also produced as by-product for other refinery processes.
- **Isomerization (IS).** It converts linear hydrocarbons to their higher-octane branched isomers to enhance gasoline quality to produce high-octane gasoline blending components.

Table 31: Operational Parameters of the hydrogen processes in refineries¹⁰⁷⁻¹⁰⁹

Element	HDT	HCK	HDS	CR	IS
Temperature [°C]	300-400	340-480	300-400	500-535	150-200
Pressure [bar]	20-150	60-200r	20-150	7-50	10-35
H ₂ Flow [Sm ³ /ton _{fuel}]	50 to 700	1000 to 2000	100 to 600	20 to 50 (produced)	Negligible

In Figure 47, a block flow diagram of a H₂ network that feed the processes within a general refinery plant is shown. The H₂ that is produced in the reforming section and in the SMR plant are usually treated with a PSA system to reach required the desired purity before to feed in the downstream processes. Since H₂ is usually produced at relatively moderate pressures (<50 bar), a compression section is needed to supply H₂ at the operative pressure of the downstream processes (up to 200 bar) through a dedicated pipeline.

Figure 47: Conventional refinery hydrogen network¹⁰⁸.

Due to the complexity of the plant, to identify and estimate the H₂ emissions in refinery plant is a hard task. In fact, several sources can be listed including, for example, emissions from the H₂ conveying

networks within the plant, from compressors section, tanks etc. Since these emissions' sources are the same of those already indicated in previous sections, they are not repeated in this section since the reader can refer to what it has been already indicated. However, the incomplete combustion of the unreacted H₂ in the hydrotreating and hydrocracking processes is a specific source of emission from refineries. Specifically, H₂ is mixed with the off-gasses (ROG) and feed in the combustion sections to produce the heat required by the refinery¹⁰⁸. Because of its economic value, recover H₂ is an alternative option even if losses through the permeated side would occur. That is, the separation technologies indicated in Table 32 can be adopted for the purpose.

Table 32: Summary of gas separation technologies in refinery plants¹⁰⁹

Summary of gas separation technologies				
Features	Adsorption	Cryogenics	Legacy membranes	Divi-H
H ₂ purity	99.9%+	90-96%	90-98%	90-99.95%
H ₂ recovery	75-92%	90-98%	85-95%	90-95%
Feed pressure	10-40 barg	>5-75 barg	20-160 barg	20-160 barg
Feed temperature	50-80C	<0C	20-80C	20-150C
Feed H ₂ content	>40%	>10%	>25-50%	>25-80%
H ₂ product pressure	Feed pressure	Feed/low pressure	<< Feed pressure	< Feed pressure
H ₂ capacity	1-225 K Nm ³ /hr	10-75+ K Nm ³ /hr	Modular	Modular
Pretreatment requirements	Depends on adsorbent	CO ₂ , H ₂ O removal	CO ₂ , H ₂ S, acid gas removal	Minimal (liquid separation only)
Multiple products	No	Liquid HCs	No	No
Capital cost	Medium	High	Low	Low
Scale economics	Moderate	Good	Modular	Modular

8.1.2. Nitrogen-based fertilizers production

Two main categories of fertilizers exist. Synthetic (chemical) fertilizers are manufactured through chemical processes and produced in large-scale industrial facilities. Organic fertilizers, instead, are derived from natural sources including typically compost and manure through biological processes such as composting or fermentation.

Nitrogen-based fertilizers, which are synthetic fertilizers derived from ammonia (NH_3), represent the largest product group of fertilizers typically used by end-users¹¹⁰. H_2 is a key element for the production of such fertilizers: the synthesis of ammonia is basically done by mixing nitrogen separated from the air with H_2 at high temperature and pressure in accordance with the Haber-Bosch process. Ammonia can be used to make nitric acid (HNO_3), and then to produce nitrate fertilizers such as ammonium nitrate (AN) in a dedicated reaction.

The following reactions apply:

Ammonia may also be mixed with liquid carbon dioxide to produce urea. Both these products can be further mixed with water to form urea ammonium nitrate (UAN) solution.

The ammonia is used to make nitric acid, with which it is then mixed to produce nitrate fertilizers such as ammonium nitrate (AN). Ammonia may also be mixed with liquid carbon dioxide to create urea. Both these products can be further mixed with water to form UAN (urea ammonium nitrate) solution.

The process for the production of ammonia can be schematized in the three main blocks as shown in Figure 48:

- **Ammonia synthesis element (HB).** The Haber-Bosch process is the most implemented method to produce ammonia at industrial scale. the readers can refer to paragraph “NH3 synthesis/cracking” for the definition of the archetype.
- **Nitric Acid Production element (NA):** Nitric acid is produced by oxidation of ammonia in the Ostwald process. The liquid ammonia is evaporated, superheated and sent with compressed air to a convertor, containing platinum and rhodium catalyst. In the convertor ammonia is converted into nitric oxide which is then converted into nitrogen dioxide in the oxidation vessel by adding secondary air. Then, the water absorbs nitrogen dioxide to form nitric acid in the absorption column.
- **Ammonia nitrate production and fertilizer production (AN & Fer):** The industrial production of ammonium nitrate entails the acid-base reaction of ammonia with nitric acid than are produced Urea and UAN solution for the final use.

Figure 48: Production process of Ammonia (UAN) for fertilizers

H₂ emissions are expected to occur only in the Haber Bosch block. In fact, no H₂ is expected to be present in the other section. In fact, 0.178 kg of H₂ have to be fed into the reactor to produce 1 kg of ammonia. That is the following emissions are expected:

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Start-Up.** For adjustment of the correct syngas mixture, syngas is temporarily routed to the flare prior to compression. This process approximately occurs for few hours every start-up. Usually, complete combustion is assumed. For baseload ammonia plants, this occurs at a low frequency.
- **Flare Scenario from Compressor.** Controlled or emergency depressurization of the compressor to the flare. Occurs with rare frequency.
- **Flare Scenario from Throttling.** Controlled or emergency depressurization of the NH₃ throttle section to the flare. Occurs with rare frequency.
- **Inert Purge from Refrigeration Unit.** Inert from the ammonia synthesis loop are purged together with traces of H₂ and NH₃ and routed to the flare. Occurs continuously during operation. Usually, complete combustion is assumed. For baseload ammonia plants, this occurs at a low frequency.
- **Compressor Seal Gas Losses.** Continuous seal gas losses of the compressor are routed to the flare. This type of losses occurs continuously during operation but for baseload ammonia plants, this occurs at a low frequency.

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- Fugitive Losses through fittings, and the components in the balance of plants.

8.1.3. Steel sector

The steel industry is one of the most carbon-intensive sectors, contributing to 8% of Europe's CO₂ emissions. Traditional steel production relies heavily on coal and natural gas. However, potential decarbonization opportunities through alternative technologies are under investigation. These new pathways for the decarbonization of steel production include H₂ plasma smelting reduction (HPSR), H₂ flash ironmaking, H₂ enriched blast furnace ironmaking, and H₂ based Direct Reduction Iron (DRI) paired with Electric Arc Furnaces (EAF)¹¹¹. Furthermore, H₂ could be used in the steel industry for heat treating cold-heading material and cold-extrusion steel grades. Historically, a mix of H₂ and methane was used for economic reasons, but there is a trend towards using pure gas due to its better performances such as, for example, heat transfer properties.

To date, industrial demonstrators are limited to the use of H₂ in the DRI furnace as reducing agent, or as a fuel in substitution of traditional fossil fuels to produce the thermal energy required by the process.

Regarding DRI production, MIDREX, and ENERGIRON® have been considered as typical process in this phase of NHyRA project progress. These processes use a gas reducing mixture with H₂ contents ranging from 55%vol. to 85%vol. However, the implementation of pure H₂ is also assumed to be technical feasible in the future¹¹¹.

Regarding MIDREX¹¹² technology, the first commercial plant is scheduled to begin production in 2025 in Boden, north Sweden. The revamping aims to reduce the emissions from 2.0 to less than 0.5 tons CO₂ per ton of steel. Specifically, the traditional blast furnace-basic oxygen furnace (BF-BOF) process will be replaced by the DRI-EAF process in the MIDREX FLEX configuration as shown in Figure 49.

Figure 49: The MIDREX FLEX configuration¹¹²

Despite the use of H₂, a small amount of natural gas is often required to maintain the proper operative conditions (e.g., temperature and carbon content in the produced DRI). From a technical point of view, different configurations of the MIDREX process have been developed based on the H₂ content in the mixture entering the shaft furnace. For a content up to 20-30% vol., no significant modifications are needed. However, higher percentages require more extensive revamping, including the removal of the NG reformer and the introduction of a pre-heater in the plant layout.

ENERGIRON® is the other industrial process considered. The manufacturer declare almost 18,400 kg/h of H₂ is required to annually produce 2 million tons of DRI. As for MIDREX, modifications to the existing plant layout can be necessary based on the H₂ concentration. In Figure 50, a schematic of the plant layout by ENERGIRON® is shown.

Figure 50: The ENERGIRON® plant schematic for use with H₂

The main parameters of the two process technologies are shown in Table 33. As shown, some data are not available in the literature, or they have been assumed.

Table 33: Operational parameters of main H₂ based iron production processes¹¹²

Parameter	MIDREX	ENERGIRON®	Notes
Hydrogen [Nm ³ /ton of crude steel] [Nm ³ / ton of DRI]	556	-	For process purposes and for heating the pre-heater. In MIDREX, almost 150 Nm ³ are required for heat supply.
	650	≈800	ENERGIRON® has been calculated by assuming 8000 h/year
Natural gas [%mol]	> 3.5	Not indicated	
Inlet temperature to reactor [°C]	> 950	950-1080	
Operative pressure [barg]	2	≥ 5	
Hydrogen purity [%]	99.8	Not indicated	

Figure 51 can be also used as a reference for the estimation of H₂ demand as a function of the composition of the entering mixture.

Figure 51: NG and H₂ demand for different percentage of injection¹¹³.

Other steelmaking processes use H₂. Among these, annealing involves heating the material up to temperatures higher than 500 °C and allowing it to cool at a specified rate. Annealing process require the

use of H₂ and N₂ mixtures or pure H₂, around 10 Nm³/ton_{steel} of hydrogen. Specifically, pure H₂ allows faster production and higher final quality. Since heat is required to maintain the operative temperature in the chamber, and because of new gas has to be continuously circulated to ensure high quality standard, H₂ is usually supplied to the burner substituting traditional fossil fuels.

In Figure 52, the general archetype for a steel making plant is shown. As depicted, since different processes can be implemented in the plant, the block includes data about the estimated demand of H₂ by typical processes that can be present. Based on the definition of different scenarios, the users will select the most relevant for their analysis.

Evaluating generally the process: The production process begins in the pelletizer unit (**PU**), where iron ore is converted into iron pellets by heating. These pellets are then forwarded to the Direct Reduction Iron Furnace (**DRI**), where hydrogen serves as the reducing gas to eliminate oxygen from the iron pellets, an endothermic reaction. Additionally, thermal energy preheats the hydrogen stream entering the furnace¹¹⁴.

An additional step is necessary to remove most of the remaining oxygen, which is where the Electric Arc Furnace (**EAF**) comes into play. In the EAF, two main processes occur: the hot Direct Reduced Iron is completely melted at approximately 1700 °C and further reduced. It's important to note that reduction in the EAF does not involve hydrogen but rather carbon monoxide, produced from the reaction between oxygen and carbon. In the process, it is estimated that 10 kg of carbon coke are added per ton of liquid steel (tIs), indicating that even the hydrogen-based DRI combined with EAF cannot be considered entirely carbon-free¹¹⁴.

Optionally, in the final stage of steel production, the hot rolling procedure (**HR**) is conducted to make the produced steel commercially viable. In this process, hydrogen could be utilized as a heat source. It's estimated that around 0.06 tons of hydrogen are needed to produce 1 ton of steel.

Figure 52: General Steel making plant archetype

Regarding H₂ expected emissions in steelmaking plant, since no demonstrators are in operation yet, only estimations based on the literature and partners experience can be performed. That is, since H₂ is

consumed to reduce ferric oxide (Fe_2O_3) and black iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) to iron (Fe), emissions are expected to be limited along the distribution system and to unburned H_2 .

Therefore, H_2 emissions are expected to be the following:

- **Incomplete Combustion.** Unburned H_2 in the exhaust flue gases can be present depending on the combustion efficiency and the H_2 -natural gas mixture composition.
- **Fugitives:** Fugitive Losses through fittings, and the components in the balance of plants.

8.2. Transport

8.2.1. E-fuels

E-fuels are promising substitutes of carbon-rich fossil fuels and are therefore required to fulfil the climate goals of the European Commission. There are many potential synthesis routes to produce e-fuels, requiring both H₂ and a carbon source. The “e” refers to the electricity used for producing H₂. The use of electricity generated with renewable energy sources is preferred since it allow reducing the emissions throughout the life cycle, The carbon source can either be retrieved by carbon capture and utilization technologies through direct air capturing, or by flue gas treatments in industrial processes.

The most promising e-fuels are e-methanol and e-ammonia, respectively synthesized by Fischer-Tropsch and by Haber-Bosch routes.

It is evaluating also a promising future application of hydrogen in e-fuels production is CO₂ methanation using renewable hydrogen, based on the Sabatier reaction

This archetype will focus on the production of e-methanol and CH₄, due to the already detailed Haber-Bosch process.

The main elements considered for the Fischer-Tropsch based e-methanol production are:

- Reverse water gas shift reactor (RWGS): Chamber for the reaction
- Pipes: Transport of the feedstocks
- Catalyst: Supports the reaction of CO and H₂ ($\text{CO} + 2 \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$; $\text{CO}_2 + 3 \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3 \text{OH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$)
- CO₂ Separator

Figure 53: Major step of e-methanol/FT fuel production.

The main parameters that characterize the operation of these specific plants that could affect the hydrogen releases are schematized in the Table 34, for all the main plant elements introduced before

Table 34: Operational parameters of e-methanol production plant.

Parameters	Values
RWGS	
Reaction pressure [bar]	24.5
Reaction temperature (RWGS) [°C]	600
CO ₂ separator, absorber pressure [bar]	30
Flash pressure [bar]	3.4/1.0/0.3
FT synthesis	
Reaction temperature [°C]	220
Reaction pressure [bar]	24.3
H ₂ /CO input molar ratio	2.2
Methanol synthesis	
Reaction temperature [°C]	300
Reaction pressure [bar]	52/51/50
H ₂ /CO input molar ratio	2.1
H₂-separation	
H ₂ recovery ratio	85%
H ₂ absorber pressure [bar]	23.2

Due to the lack of information related to specific losses of e-methanol production, the general losses related to compression line (when the hydrogen is delivered at low pressure), valves and fitting and an optional loss related to the hydrogen storage system are considered.

Another promising future application of hydrogen in e-fuels production is CO₂ methanation using renewable hydrogen, based on the Sabatier reaction, which chemically transforms sources into CH₄, also known as BioSNG. In the future, BioSNG could be utilized in the transportation sector or injected into the natural gas grid. However, the production of methane from alternative sources should increasingly focus on processes already in use today. The production of methane from biogenic sources is on the rise. Anaerobic digestion, which typically uses wet feedstocks, is well-established, and many plants are operational worldwide.

The methanation technology is mentioned in this document for completeness, but it will not be detailed extensively due to its limited current use.

Figure 54: Simplified methanation flowchart.

For the archetype characterization, introduced in the Figure 54, the main plant elements are:

- **H₂ production** : Water treatment and electrolysis if Hydrogen is produced on site
- **Methanation Rector**: Catalytic reactor. Sabatier reaction (exothermic, T^a 150-500°C). Pressure 10-50 bar.
- **Gas treatment unit**: Depending on needs downstream. Cooling, gas drying, purification, compression might be needed. Grid injection is a possibility (normal use of the SNG produced).
- **Balance of Plan (BOP)**: Water treatment, heat exchanger, air injection. To support main processes.

For the hydrogen losses or releases, no specific information has been provided in addition to the traditional releases/emissions evaluated in the “[3.1 Balance of Plant Process Elements](#)” paragraph.

8.2.2. Hydrogen refuelling stations

Projections indicate that one out of twelve vehicles sold in Germany, Japan, California, and South Korea will be powered by hydrogen by 2030. Additionally, it is expected that over 350,000 hydrogen trucks will be operational, alongside thousands of trains and ships that will transport passengers without releasing carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. As recorded at the end of 2020, there were 540 hydrogen refuelling stations in operation globally¹¹⁵, highlighting the pivotal role of the utilization of hydrogen in the transport sector in the next and far future.

Hydrogen refuelling stations are governed by the ISO 19880 standards, which provide comprehensive guidelines on the design, construction, operation, and maintenance. Different kinds of Hydrogen stations exist. In NHARA project, we focus only on external hydrogen supply stations with gaseous hydrogen delivery, which is the most common HRS worldwide.

Following the ISO 19880-1 guidelines for the definition of a HRS general layout, the archetype has been described as:

- Connection cabinet for tank unloading (C.C.)
- Low pressure hydrogen storage (LP Storage)
- Compressor unit (Comp): typically, mechanical booster of diaphragm compressors usually they operate in the 70-95 MPa range, under 135 °C^{54,116}.
- High pressure storage (cascades): in the 70-95 MPa range
- Precooling unit: fundamental to pre-cool the compressed hydrogen, decreasing its temperature of -20 to -40 °C to respect the 85 °C operating temperature limits for vehicles hydrogen storage system.
- Hydrogen dispenser

HRS solutions that directly connect the HP compressor unit to the vehicle also exist. They have been presented in the compression archetype in “5.1.1 H2 Compression” paragraph.

The simplified design of an HRS is reported in Figure 55

Figure 55: Simplified Schematic of an HRS.

An HRS is always composed (at minimum) of the components shown in Figure 56. However, the listed components can be arranged in a different way depending on the size of the station from one to 4 compression units installed, from one to 4 sources of H₂ put in parallel, HP/MP storages configuration is extremely variable and/or dispenser with one, two or multiple distribution lines) and the manufacturer (specific approaches on the equipment disposal and layout).

Figure 56: Simplified process flow chart of an HRS.

For H₂ release/leakage estimation, the sources are identified for each component. Then, when more than one unit is present for a given component, the total release should simply be computed by multiplying the number of installed units by the release of a single unit. For example, if a compressor unit has X sources of release and the station has 2 compressor units, then the total sources of release would be 2X.

The two main sources of emissions are from the high-pressure compressed hydrogen tanks and during the compression process itself:

- Emissions from hydrogen compression is estimated to be between 0.05 – 0.25%. All hydrogen handled by the refuelling station is assumed to go through one compression cycle. Hydrogen emissions are computed assuming a daily output of a single hydrogen refuelling station between 80 kg and 1300 kg.
- Emissions from the high-pressure storage is estimated to be between 0.12 – 0.24% per day. Hydrogen emissions are computed assuming an amount of stored hydrogen between 100 kg and 500 kg.

Other sources of H₂ losses like purging during regular operations (following each vehicle refuelling, the flexible hose is purged to eliminate any residual hydrogen), fugitive emissions through pipes and emergency venting are deemed negligible.

Each item of the HRS presented in Figure 56 is further detailed in the following to better understand the different sources of H₂ release.

Source of Hydrogen (Tube trailer)

Tube trailers are a common method for delivering hydrogen from production facilities to refuelling stations or industrial sites, ensuring a reliable supply of hydrogen gas where pipeline infrastructure is not available. It is fundamental to characterize the connection elements between the trailer and the HRS, in which not negligible losses could occur. The archetype is shown in Figure 57:

Figure 57: Detailed representation of H₂ sourcing (Tube trailer).

The hydrogen possible emissions related to the IN/out connection block of the trailer and HRS connection cabinet are:

1. Probable fugitive releases due to leakages on the connection between the tube trailer and the HRS. These releases are controlled and mitigated by bubble test inspection after any Tube trailer connection.
2. Fugitive releases could appear on equipment connections (valves, sensors, any other element on the H₂ line going from the vessels to the IN/out connection) due to leakages on the connection. This could be due to vibrations or lack of maintenance.
3. For each connection/disconnection of tube trailer a venting event:
 - During connection: It is used to flush the line to ensure the right purity of the H₂ before getting inside the HRS process.
 - During Disconnection: It is necessary to depressurize the line to be able to disconnect it in a safe way. Thus, a purge should be done.

Connection cabinet for tank unloading (Low pressure)

The hydrogen connection cabinet is the interface between the hydrogen source and the station's storage and dispensing system. This cabinet houses the necessary equipment and safety mechanisms to facilitate the safe transfer of hydrogen gas from the high-pressure cylinders of the tube trailer to the station's infrastructure. It includes pressure regulators, valves, and monitoring systems to ensure that the hydrogen is transferred efficiently and securely, maintaining the required pressure and flow rates while preventing leaks and ensuring compliance with safety standards. The connection cabinet components are shown in Figure 58.

Figure 58: Detailed representation of connection cabinet.

The losses are mainly related to possible fugitives and incident that could occur during the operation of the plant, precisely:

- **Pressure regulator + Piping:** Fugitive releases due to leakages on the connection between piping and the pressure regulator. These releases are controlled and mitigated by maintenance plan.
- **H₂ valves + piping and safety overpressure device:** Fugitive releases due to leakages on the connection between piping and valves or PSV (pressure safety valve). These releases are controlled and mitigated by inspection and adapted maintenance plan.
- **Pressure safety valve:** In case of overpressure (for example tube trailer with a higher pressure compared to maximum admissible pressure of the station), a safety valve will lead to a purging of the hydrogen into the atmosphere to protect the station

Compression unit (Medium and/or High pressure)

The objective of the compression unit is to reach the required H₂ distribution pressure safely and efficiently. The adopted compressors include Diaphragm Compressors, Piston Compressors, Hydraulic Compressors, Centrifugal Compressors. These systems have been detailed and analysed in the “Compression unit” paragraph, therefore they will be not treated in the paragraph.

The configurations of compressors in a hydrogen refuelling station can vary based on the station's design and capacity requirements:

- Single Medium-Pressure Compressor: used in small stations or those with low hydrogen throughput. It compresses hydrogen to medium pressures (500 bar). Hydrogen is then further managed by the storage and dispensing system.
- Dual Compressors (Medium and High Pressure): one compressor is used to compress hydrogen to a medium pressure. Hydrogen is then fed into a second compressor to achieve the high pressure required for vehicle refuelling (typically 350 bar or 700 bar). This configuration ensures a more efficient and reliable compression process, balancing the load between two compressors.
- Multiple Compressors in Parallel: used for high capacity stations to handle large volumes of hydrogen. This setup provides redundancy and ensures continuous operation even if one compressor is offline for maintenance.
- Cascade Compression Systems: hydrogen is compressed in stages using multiple compressors. Each stage progressively increases the pressure, which can be more efficient and reduce the strain on individual compressors.

These compressor types and configurations ensure that hydrogen is delivered at the correct pressures required for safe and efficient vehicle refuelling, adapting to the specific demands and capacities of different HRS.

A schematic of the compression unit is shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59: Detailed representation of compression unit (MP and/or HP).

The main releases of the general compression unit, without going in the details for each specific compressor type already evaluated, are related to fugitives and incidental releases from the main BOP components as valves, fitting, piping etc.:

- Fittings from all equipment's inside H₂ compressor (Safety valve, filter, manual valves, metrology): fugitive releases due to leakages on the connection between piping and the equipment's. These releases are controlled and mitigated by rigorous maintenance plan.
- safety overpressure device (PRD on compressor unit): fugitive releases due to leakages on the connection between piping and valves or PSV (pressure safety valve). These releases are controlled and mitigated by inspection and adapted maintenance plan. In case of overpressure (for example failure on compressor shaft), a safety valve will lead to a purging of the hydrogen into the atmosphere to protect the station.

Medium and/or high-pressure hydrogen storage:

In hydrogen mobility stations, different types of storage systems are employed to safely and efficiently store hydrogen at medium and high pressures. These storage systems can be categorized as follows:

- Medium-Pressure Storage: Type I, II, III cylinders as already described in the Compressed hydrogen tanks (CH₂) paragraph
- High-Pressure Storage: Type IV and Type V cylinders

Different configurations are possible depending on the station site specificity. Possible configurations are the same detailed in the “Compressed hydrogen tanks (CH₂)” paragraph for stationary applications.

Concerning the pressure ranges, we can categorize them as follow:

- Medium Pressure: Typically ranges from 200 to 350 bar. This storage is used for intermediate steps in the hydrogen refuelling process, often before final compression to high pressures.
- High Pressure: Typically ranges from 350 to 700 bar, depending on the final destination (light vehicle or heavy vehicles). This storage is used for direct dispensing into hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, ensuring they receive hydrogen at the necessary pressure for efficient operation.

These storage systems and configurations are critical for the safe and efficient operation of hydrogen refuelling stations, ensuring a reliable supply of hydrogen at the required pressures for various applications.

A schematic of the hydrogen storage is shown in Figure 60, including the hydrogen HP and/or MP storage as well as the manual valves and piping, which are connected to the compression unit and to the dispenser.

Figure 60: Detailed representation of HP and/or MP storage.

The generalized losses for a storage system of an HRS are also mainly related to fugitives and incident emissions that could occur in all of the auxiliary elements required for the storage-. While the specific emissions related to the tank has been widely evaluated in the “Compressed hydrogen tanks (CH₂)” paragraph, the general ones are:

- Fugitive emissions due to leakages on the connection between piping and valves. These releases are controlled and mitigated by inspection and adapted maintenance plan.
- Fugitive emissions due to leakages on the connection between piping and valves or On Tank Valve (OTV). These releases are controlled and mitigated by inspection and adapted maintenance plan.

- In case of over overpressure (for example failure of compressor unit, fire near the storage unit creating an overpressure, etc..), a safety valve will lead to a purging of the hydrogen into the atmosphere to protect the station and avoid explosion.

Hydrogen Dispenser (HP and/or MP, single or double line)

A hydrogen dispenser is a crucial component of a HRS, designed to safely and efficiently transfer hydrogen from the station's storage system to the fuel cell vehicle's tank. It functions similarly to a traditional gasoline pump, but it is specifically engineered to handle hydrogen gas at various pressures. The dispenser ensures that hydrogen is delivered at the correct pressure and temperature, providing a seamless and safe refuelling experience for users.

Hydrogen dispensers play an essential role in the hydrogen refuelling infrastructure, enabling the widespread adoption of hydrogen fuel cell vehicles by providing reliable and safe refuelling options.

The specific component has been detailed in the “Hydrogen Dispenser ” section in the “5.1 H₂ Compression” paragraph and is no further evaluated here. Figure 61 schematize the components of the hydrogen dispenser in a HRS, helping in the definition of the relative hydrogen losses/releases.

Figure 61: Detailed representation of dispenser.

For the main releases that could occur in the dispenser, the reader is addressed to the “Hydrogen Dispenser ” section in the “5.1 H₂ Compression” paragraph.

The main difference in the specific case of a dispenser in HRS are related to the frequent refuelling procedures compared to dispenser in a loading bay. Main losses are:

Furthers losses related to the specific section are:

- The venting required to decrease the pressure in the dispensing line after each refuelling, as required to disconnect the nozzle from the vehicle.
- In case of rupture of the break-away, we could have, during highly short time (under second range), hydrogen release at very high pressure (Up to 700 barg).
- In case of over pressure on the distribution line, the overpressure is evacuated from the dispensing line by an PRD (Pressure relief Device).

Summing up the main hydrogen emissions for the H₂ refuelling station archetype:

The two main sources of leakage are from the high-pressure compressed hydrogen tanks and during the compression process itself:

- Both vented and fugitives emissions from hydrogen compression is estimated to be between 0.05 – 0.25%. All hydrogen handled by the refuelling station is assumed to go through one compression cycle. Hydrogen emissions are computed assuming a daily output of a single hydrogen refuelling station between 80 kg and 1300 kg.
- Both vented and fugitives emissions from the high-pressures storage is estimated to be between 0.12 – 0.24% per day. Hydrogen emissions are computed assuming an amount of stored hydrogen between 100 kg and 500 kg.

Other sources of H₂ losses like purging during regular operations (following each vehicle refuelling, the flexible hose is purged to eliminate any residual hydrogen), fugitive leakage through pipes and emergency venting are deemed negligible, for completeness can be defined in the “3.1 Balance of Plant Process Elements” chapter..

8.2.3. FC Electric Vehicles

Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) represent a promising technology in the quest for sustainable transportation. Utilizing hydrogen as a fuel, FCEVs generate electricity through a chemical reaction between hydrogen and oxygen in a fuel cell, producing only water and heat as byproducts. This clean energy process provides a viable alternative to conventional internal combustion engines, offering significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions and other pollutants.

This technology allows to overcome some limits of Battery Electrified Vehicles (BEVs) that are related to limited range and long recharging times, coupled with high peak power requested for fast charge, that today has reached 350 kW for 800 Volts based BEVs.

By 2030, FCEVs could account for 1 in 22 passenger vehicles and 1 in 12 of light commercial vehicles (LCVs) sold, leading to a fleet of 3.7 million fuel cell passenger vehicles and 500,000 fuel cell LCVs. In addition, about 45,000 fuel cell trucks and buses could be on the road by 2030. Fuel cell trains could also replace roughly 570 diesel trains by 2030¹¹⁷.

For this reason, we will focus on:

- Forklifts: already used for industrial applications, hydrogen based forklifts are based on a hybrid solution between Li-ion battery electrical storage and a 25 litres 200 bar tank coupled with a 2-5 kW PEM FC¹¹⁸.
- FC passenger/light commercial Vehicles: typically use high-pressure storage tanks that can hold hydrogen at around 700 bar. The Hyundai Nexo SUV, the Honda Clarity Fuel Cell sedan and the Toyota Mirai sedan are three recent commercial examples. All of the cars are powered by a 100-120 kW FC and around 5 kg of hydrogen tank operating at 700 bars¹¹⁹.
- FC Truck/ Busses: often use storage tanks with service pressures of around 350 bar (5,000 psi) with a total tank capacity in the 40-70 kg_{H_2} range¹²⁰ powered by FC (200- 300 kW) and BESS hybrid configuration.
- FC small trains: newly designed and diesel retrofitting solutions are both existing now, considering some already commercialized solutions and prototypes ones. They are characterized by PEM FC over a 1 MW peak power, and both compressed (>350 bars) and liquified hydrogen storage solutions^{121,122}.

For all different types of vehicles, a unique archetype has been defined and schematized in Figure 62. Precisely the archetype components are:

- Air line: characterized by an air measurement and filtration unit, coupled with a compression and humidification unit, to operate in every real word cases. Approximately 50 to 70 per cent of the oxygen supplied to the fuel cell stack is consumed within the cells. The remainder is exhausted from the system.
- Fuel cell Unit: PEM fuel + Purge/safety vales (only adopted option thanks to their rangeability and durability). Most of the hydrogen that is supplied to the fuel cell system is consumed within the cells, but a small excess is required to ensure that the fuel cells will not be damaged. The excess

hydrogen is either mixed with the exhaust to produce a non-flammable exhaust from the vehicle or catalytically reacted.

- Hydrogen storage Unit: Type IV-V tanks operating in the 350-700 bars range and the auxiliary valves, the most delicate component made of all the required auxiliaries as on-Tank Valve (OTV) that controls the flow of hydrogen into and out of the storage tank, the manifold system of pipes and valves that distributes hydrogen from the storage tanks to the fuel cell system, Pressure Relief Devices (PRD) that release hydrogen gas if the tank pressure exceeds safe limits, Temperature and Pressure Sensors for the tank and check valves
- Waste water and temperature management system: the fuel cell system also includes auxiliary components to remove waste heat. Most fuel cell systems are cooled by a mixture of glycol and water. Pumps circulate the coolant between the fuel cells and the radiator
- Power Train: made of the electric-drive motor, controller and the complete energy power management system to manage the flows coming from FC and BESS.
- Battery system: usually small Li-ion Battery + BMS to flatten the energy request for the fuel cell.

Figure 62: General flowchart of FC based vehicles.

In terms of hydrogen releases and losses, the major losses come from the H₂ tank system and the outlet side of the Fuel cell, due to the not complete fuel utilization of the Fuel cell. Even if the outlet hydrogen line is normally blocked, it is periodically purged to evacuate the nitrogen which diffuses from the cathode (air side) towards the anode (hydrogen side) diluting the hydrogen., The purged hydrogen in the process is considered 1% of the exploited one¹¹⁹.

The main H₂ releases are however expected to come from the vehicle tank system, which is therefore further detailed.

Vehicle tanks system

Two typical configurations for vehicles tanks systems exists: a single high pressure storage system is used for light duty vehicle (shown in Figure 63), while multiple tank lines with dedicated valves systems are used for heavy-duty vehicles (shown in Figure 64). Precisely the two configurations are characterized by:

- SINGLE TANK CONFIGURATION: Typical for vehicles – up to 5-6 kg of H₂ as storage at 700 barg (almost 130 lt) per 500 km of driving¹²³
- MULTI TANK CONFIGURATION: Typical for busses (up to 25 kg H₂ at 350 barg) or some vehicles (Toyota Mirai) - same amount of H₂ content of the single tank configuration at 700 barg¹²⁴.

Figure 63: Single Tank configuration¹²³

Figure 64: Multiple Tank configuration¹²⁴

The key elements of the H₂ tanks systems have been already described in the “Compressed hydrogen tanks (CH2)” paragraph, recapping them:

- Interface with the station fueling dispenser (receptacle)

- Filter
- Integrated in tank valve (it is like a manifold block): Check valve, Auto solenoid valve, Pressure transducers, Excess flow valve, Filter, Relief valve, Temperature transducers, Manual override
- Integrated pressure regulator block: Pressure regulator, Manual defuel valve, Pressure transmitter, Automated shutoff valve, Pressure relief valve.

The main hydrogen release elements/events related to the hydrogen compressed tanks storage are reported in the table below following the previously defined H_2 releases categorization:

- **Tank Surface - Hydrogen Embrittlement:** Hydrogen embrittlement of the tank material that causes fugitive losses of hydrogen. The phenomenon is related to operative pressure and temperature of the tank and occurs mainly in steel; some evidence of H_2 embrittlement in aluminium has been found in the case of high storage pressure. Hydrogen embrittlement can lead to material failure, especially in steel tanks under high pressure.
- **Tank Surface - Hydrogen Permeation:** Hydrogen permeation through the tank material. Operative pressure and temperature influence the permeation through the material, tank area.
- **Safety Valve:** Safety valves intervene when the operative pressure in equipment exceeds the valve set pressure. Venting the elaborated hydrogen. Related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area, fluid characteristics. Theoretical calculation using ISO 4126-1 and 4126-2, IEC 60179-10. The total released mass depends on the frequency of intervention and the duration of discharge before operator intervention.
- **Connection Fittings:** Emission due to not ideal connection that could create fugitives' hydrogen releases, as detailed in the "[3.1 Balance of Plant Process Elements](#)" chapter.
- **Valves - Emission from Moving Stem:** Fugitive Emission from a moving stem. Related to operative conditions (temperature, pressure).
- **Valves - Emission Due to Imperfect Closing:** Fugitive emission due to imperfect closing. Related to the leakage class of the valve. Permissible leakages can be calculated according to IEC 60534-4:2017 "Industrial-process control valves. Part 4: Inspection and routine testing" based on the class.
- **Purging:** In case of maintenance and intervention on the tank, H_2 is purged. The effected quantity vented is related to the hydrogen content in the tank, maintenance frequency.
- **Thermal Pressure Relief Device (TPRD):** Overpressure due to the increase of temperature above 108-110°C. related to the volume of H_2 content. The TPRD is designed not to close again after activation. After its activation, the storage has to be removed and substituted.
- **Leakage on the OTV** could occurs but these releases are mitigated by periodic maintenance and leak tests.

8.2.4. ICE vehicles

In the transport sector, which has limited near-zero emission energy options like electricity and advanced biofuels, hydrogen presents a promising solution for addressing significant emission reduction challenges, particularly when integrated with internal combustion engine (ICE) technologies. Hydrogen-fueled internal combustion engines (H2ICE) offer a unique alternative to electrified vehicles by retaining the traditional ICE powerplant while eliminating tank-to-wheel CO₂ emissions at the tailpipe. This is similar to internal combustion engines powered by ammonia, which are more suited for maritime applications¹²⁵.

Unlike fuel cell powertrain systems, H2ICEs can operate using non-purified hydrogen, which significantly reduces the production cost of hydrogen fuel. The impurity limits for H2ICE fuel are 20,000 µmol/mol for non-hydrogen gases, 1 µmol/mol for carbon monoxide, and 2 µmol/mol for sulfur compounds¹²⁶. These engines can also leverage advanced combustion and engine control technologies, such as direct injection, the Miller cycle, lean or diluted combustion, and pre-chamber ignition.

Leading car manufacturers as Ford, BMW, Mazda, Chevrolet and Toyota produced hydrogen-based ICE vehicles, both light vehicles and heavy vehicles¹²⁶, with the characteristics summarized in Table 36.

Table 35: Main operational parameters of H₂-based ICE vehicle¹²⁶

Parameters	Values	
Vehicle Type	Cars	Bus/Pick-up
Engine displacement [L]	1.3-2.0	6.0-6.8
Tank Capacity [kgH ₂]	1.5-2.5	10-29.6
Pressure [bar]	200-350	350
Range [km]	100-130	230-260
Efficiency [%]	40-50	40-50

the general archetype for hydrogen-based hydrogen vehicles has been simplified considering the main components interested of hydrogen flow in Figure 65, precisely:

- Hydrogen storage Unit: tanks operating in the 200-350 bars range with all the auxiliaries components as detailed in the specific section of “8.3.1 Fuel cells” paragraph.
- Internal combustion engine unit (ICE): made of the hydrogen-based engine and fuel supply system, precisely the prevailing systems are gas mixer, port injection, and direct injection¹²⁷
- Power train: mechanical part made of the transmission, wheels, etc.. to transfer mechanical power to the wheels.

Figure 65: Flowchart of simplified H₂-based ICE vehicle

Hydrogen emissions related to ICE vehicles are mainly related to the H₂ storage unit and the ICE unit, precisely:

The Fugitives and vented emission of the H₂ storage unit have been considered the same type of the storage unit of FCs vehicles, evaluated in “[8.3.1 Fuel cells](#)” paragraph.

Relate to the ICE unit the main hydrogen emissions are related to the unburned hydrogen content in the exhaust gasses, even if it difficult to quantify them due to the fact that are related to the specific operating conditions of the engine and limited availability of exhaust hydrogen measurement instruments in traditional engine experimental facilities¹²⁷.

8.3. Electricity generation

The generation of electricity from hydrogen can be achieved through distinct processes: direct combustion in gas turbines or in internal combustion engines, and electrochemical oxidation in fuel cells. The former methods involve the burning of hydrogen in a controlled manner, whereas the latter employs the oxidation of hydrogen in a fuel cell.

8.3.1. Fuel cells

Fuel cells (FCs) convert hydrogen gas into water, electrical energy, and heat through an electrochemical reaction, essentially the reverse of electrolysis. Different types of fuel cells exist, using different materials (electrodes and electrolytes), operating temperatures, and the types of gases.

The main advantage of FCs is their high efficiency in electricity production without emitting pollutants. According to Si et al.¹²⁸, PEMFCs and SOFCs are suitable for cogeneration-based reactors. They also reviewed other FCs technologies like alkaline fuel cells (AFCs), phosphoric acid fuel cells (PAFCs), molten salt fuel cells (MSFCs), photoelectrochemical cells (PECs), multiple membrane fuel cells (MMFCs), and flow fuel cells (FFCs), noting their high efficiency (40-60%) compared to traditional internal combustion engines. FCs integrated into combined heat and power (CHP) systems can achieve up to 80% efficiency.

FCs can process not only pure hydrogen but also other hydrogen-bearing gases, which are reformed at high temperatures. However, this work focuses on FCs operating with hydrogen. Despite their advantages, FCs face challenges like high initial costs, lack of fuel supply infrastructure, and network.¹²⁹

This archetype focuses on fuel cell stationary applications, that are non-movable systems designed as primary power units and backup power units, e.g. uninterruptible power systems (UPS), or for the combined heat and power production (CHP). In terms of the number of units deployed, the most common types are PEMFCs and SOFCs¹³⁰.

A 2015 study from the Fuel Cell and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking outlined a potential analysis for several stationary fuel cell sizes and applications in Europe¹³¹. The fuel cells sizes have been categorized based on the specific application:

- **Residential:** micro-CHP used in 1 or 2-family dwellings or single flats. The used technologies are PEM or SOFC, fed by natural gas, biogas or pure hydrogen. The installed capacity is usually 1 kW_{el}, cotemporally producing 1.45 kW_{th} of thermal power.
- **Commercial:** mini-CHP (5 kW_{el} and 4 kW_{th}) used in apartment buildings, and CHP used in commercial buildings with capacity > 50 kW_{el} and >40 kW_{th}, usually utilizing SOFC systems.
- **Industrial:** prime power large scale for data centres > 1 MW_{el}, CHP for natural gas industrial applications ~ 1.4 MW_{el}, CHP for biogas industrial applications ~ 0.4 MW_{el}.

PEMFCs hold the largest market share globally, especially in transport applications (about 70% of capacity). For stationary applications, also MCFC and PAFC are starting to be evaluated for capacities above 200 kW. In 2018, the stationary fuel cell market saw around 240 MW capacity sold, dominated by the US and Asia¹³². This work focuses on PEMFCs and SOFCs, which have higher technology readiness levels (TRL 9)¹.

Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC)

PEMFCs are widely used in building applications and micro-cogeneration due to their maturity and high efficiency in converting hydrogen into electricity. They achieve electrical efficiencies of 30-40% and combined heat and power (CHP) efficiencies of up to 90%. For stationary applications, PEMFCs typically range from 0.3 to 5 kW in size¹³³. They are also used in backup power systems and small-scale commercial applications.

Based on the range of the operating temperatures, two types of PEMFCs are identified:

- Low temperature (LT-PEMFC): They operate at relatively low temperatures (60-80°C) and low pressures (1-3 bar), making them suitable for quick start-up and shut-down cycles. This, alongside the high-power density, is beneficial for residential and small-scale commercial applications. Nevertheless, the low temperatures necessitate the utilisation of expensive platinum-based catalysts to enhance reaction rates. The system is also highly sensitive to the presence of carbon impurities, which are typically found in reformed fuels, results in a typical system lifetime of 5,000-10,000 operating hours¹³⁴. In LT, water is essential as a proton conductor inside the membrane, therefore, a water management system must be designed in a manner that ensures optimal performance. Nevertheless, the operation of this system affects the power performance, and therefore it is necessary to control it accurately in order to maintain the required moisture level¹³⁵.
- High temperature (HT-PEMFC): They operate at higher temperatures (120-180°C) with improved performance thanks to lower voltage losses, faster reaction rates, better tolerance to carbon poisoning and a simplified version of the water management system and of the fuel processing system, lowering the operating costs. The main challenges are in durability and costs¹³⁵. In fact, Nafion is replaced with the less expensive polybenzimidazole (PBI) based membranes, which is more strong mechanically, but in this case the load of platinum required increase (almost 2.5 times) due to enhanced catalyst degradation mechanisms at high temperatures¹³⁰.

The PEMFC system design for stationary applications must be able to produce power efficiently while keeping process variables constant, to limit degradation and failure. Therefore, a highly efficient control loop system must be carefully designed in at least five different subsystem levels^{136,137}:

- Fuel cell
- Fuel processor: Feed hydrogen and air at a certain stoichiometric ratio and avoid fuel starvation.
- Thermal subsystem: Almost half of the energy produced by the PEMFCs is heat; the system is used to keep the stack temperature in the optimal range.
- Water management subsystem: Keep the membrane hydrated and ensure proton conductivity and stability.
- Power electronics subsystem: Filter the electrical unsteady power signals and deliver AC current smoothly.

Figure 66 shows a complete PFD of a general PEM FC plant configuration with all the main components:

Figure 66: Schematic diagram of an LT-PEMFC system¹³⁵

Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC)

Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC) are highly efficient energy conversion devices capable of cogeneration, achieving nearly 60% electrical efficiency and low emissions. Unlike other fuel cells, SOFCs operate at high temperatures (600-1000°C), enabling the use of various fuels, including natural gas and biogas, without an external reformer. This high-temperature operation allows internal reforming of hydrocarbons, leading to higher electrical efficiencies and combined heat and power (CHP) efficiencies up to 85-90%. When hydrogen is used as fuel, water is the only byproduct, resulting in an almost zero-emission power generation process.

SOFCs are commonly used in large industrial CHP systems (100-1000 kW) and residential heating systems (1-3 kW), and they accounted for 10% of global fuel cell sales in 2022¹³⁸. However, their implementation in small-scale residential applications is limited due to their less dynamic operation compared to PEMFCs. SOFCs require prolonged start-up and shut-down times (12 hours or more), often necessitating continuous operation at reduced output during low demand periods.

The high operating temperatures of SOFCs provide several advantages, such as the ability to generate high-grade waste heat, making them suitable for space heating and domestic hot water production while generating electricity. Additionally, SOFCs can be integrated into hybrid power generation systems paired with gas turbines. Studies have shown configurations with Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) and micro-gas turbines achieving gross system efficiencies of 55% and 57%, respectively¹³⁹.

Key components of an SOFC system include thermal management, which uses part of the heat generated in the stack for endothermic reformation reactions, reducing the air flow rate needed to maintain the desired stack temperature gradient, thereby increasing process efficiency. Heat exchangers on both the

anode and cathode sides are designed to maintain the temperature gradient across the stack. The heat from burning the electrochemically unutilized fuel can be further utilized.

The specific layout for SOFC based CHP systems is shown in Figure 67:

Figure 67: System block flow diagram of general SOFC plant¹⁴⁰.

In SOFC systems, hydrogen losses are minimal due to the high efficiency of the electrochemical processes and the robust sealing of the system components. Potential sources of hydrogen losses include:

1. **Anode Off-Gas:** Hydrogen that is not utilized in the electrochemical reaction is recycled back into the system or combusted in the combustor.
2. **Unburned Hydrogen in Exhaust Gases:** Hydrogen that escapes combustion in the combustor. Optimizing combustion processes to ensure complete utilization of hydrogen.

The Fuel Cell archetype (including heat and power cogeneration possibility) includes the following components:

- **Fuel cell stack:** operating parameters (temperature, pressure, ...) are reported in Table 36 for SOFC and PEMFC technologies.
- **Feed line:** including all components required to feed fuel (H_2 or others) and air/oxygen to the stack.
- **Thermal management unit:** an efficient heat management is essential in order to improve the total efficiency and durability of the fuel cell system. Thermal management options for PEMFC and SOFC vary due to their operating temperatures and exhaust air temperatures. In LT- and HT-PEMFC, heat is removed by circulating liquid coolant through a cooling system. The heat recovered from PEMFC stack can be used for space heating and hot water heating. In a PEMFC system an after-burner (used to burn unreacted fuel) can also be employed to create a higher heat output and to increase the overall efficiency. Heat removal from a SOFC is more complex. It is realized by supplying excess air to the cathode. The excess air and unconsumed fuel in the stack are combusted in a burner and the produced heat is used for preheating the reactants supplied to the reformer or the fuel cell stack.
- **Other BOP:** include components such as pumps, blowers, control valves, sensors, pipes and heat exchangers.

It's schematized here the flow diagram for CHP Fuel cells:

Figure 68: General flow chart of FCs plant

Table 36: Main operational parameters for SOFC and PEMFC technologies

FC Types	SOFC	PEMFC
Electrolytes	Solid YSZ, perovskite	PEM polymer
Temperatures [°C]	600-1000 °C	40-100 °C
Pressure [bar]	Amb-2	1-3
Fuel used	Natural gas, coal gas, biogas, H ₂ , NH ₃	H ₂
Power output	>10 kW	<100 kW
Efficiencies	50-60 %	40-45 %
Advantages	Low cost catalyst, no need for an external reformer, cogeneration.	High power density and quick start up, vast power range.
Challenges	Low power density, slow startup, susceptible to corrosion.	Expensive catalysts, slow oxygen kinetics, sensitive to CO poisoning.
Applications	Distributed power generation at large scale, auxiliary power, aerospace.	Small distributed generation, automotive, portable power.

Evaluating the main hydrogen emissions:

In SOFC systems, hydrogen losses are minimal due to the high efficiency of the electrochemical processes and the robust sealing of the system components. Potential sources of hydrogen losses include:

1. **Anode Off-Gas:** Hydrogen that is not utilized in the electrochemical reaction is recycled back into the system or combusted in the combustor.
2. **Unburned Hydrogen in Exhaust Gases:** Hydrogen that escapes combustion in the combustor. Optimizing combustion processes to ensure complete utilization of hydrogen.

Other general emissions are related to the BOP for the generalized Fuel cell system

Vented hydrogen emissions are mainly related to:

- **Safety Valves:** Overpressure events related to set pressure, back pressure, orifice area. The total released mass depends on the frequency and duration of discharge, these specific elements have been detailed in the “Valves” subparagraph of “Balance of Plant Process Elements”.
- **H₂ treatment unit losses:** In systems with PSA, some dry hydrogen is used to dry the inactive desiccant bed, which is then used as thermal source for the burners or vented off to the atmosphere. The details of the specific procedure are contained in the “Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA)” paragraph.

- **Anode Off-Gases:** in specific cases is required to vent partially the anode off gasses that contain traces of unreacted hydrogen, mainly the anode off-gasses are recirculated to recover the unreacted hydrogen.

Fugitives' emissions are mainly related to:

- **Leaks in Pipes, Flanges, or Other Equipment:** Occasional releases or occasional equipment failures, operational errors (faulty components, corrosion, improper maintenance, or accidental damage). Further details of the losses are detailed in the "3.1 Balance of Plant Process Elements" chapter.

In some cases, the pipelines are purged before shutdown: hydrogen emissions from purging the lines could occur.

8.3.2. Gas turbines

To achieve a zero-emission energy system by 2050, increasing the share of variable renewable electricity (VRE) generation is essential. This necessitates flexible and dispatchable power-generation technologies to ensure supply and demand balance. Gas turbines currently offer the required flexibility, but they must transition from natural gas to low- or zero-carbon fuels to meet carbon neutrality goals by mid-century. The European Investment Bank's climate strategy highlight this need, ceasing funding for projects involving unabated fossil fuels exceeding 250 gCO₂/kWhel¹⁴¹.

In this framework, hydrogen-fuelled gas turbines help reducing the while providing the flexibility required for a deeper integration of VRE in the power grid.

Hydrogen fuelled gas turbines operate by combusting hydrogen with air to produce high-temperature, high-pressure gases that drive a turbine to generate electricity. The use of hydrogen in gas turbines is advantageous due to its zero carbon emissions. However, it presents challenges such as managing high combustion temperatures and ensuring flame stability.

In gas turbines, natural gas enriched with different quantity of hydrogen can be used, providing a flexible approach to decarbonizing power generation. Indeed, different studies and industrial tests have explored the effects of hydrogen-enriched combustion with promising results:

- Research funded by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, particularly the EPSRC Flex-E-Plant project (EP/K021095/1), has examined blending hydrogen into the natural gas grid. This included pressurized burner tests with up to 15% vol. H₂ in CH₄ and atmospheric burner tests with up to 40% vol. H₂ in CH₄.
- Tests have demonstrated stable combustion with hydrogen mixing ratios up to 60 vol.-% without significant derating of power output. Magnusson et al. successfully tested a gas turbine with 60 vol.-% hydrogen, maintaining NO_x emissions below 25 ppm¹⁴².
- Ciani et al. and Bothien et al. showed that staged combustion can maintain stable operations with up to 70 vol.-% hydrogen. Beyond 70 vol.-%, minor reductions in power output are expected, but stable combustion is achievable¹⁴³.
- Higher TRL-level testing in the EU FP7 H2IGCC project (EU Grant 239349) included blending hydrogen and nitrogen at Cardiff University (UK) with mixtures up to 85% vol. H₂ in 15% vol. N₂ in a modified Ansaldo Energia lean premixed burner up to 2 MW and 4 bar. This research focused on the influence on flashback, NO_x emissions, and thermoacoustic.
- Full engine scale combustion trials with up to 83% vol. H₂ in 17% vol. N₂ were conducted at Sesta Lab (Italy), and turbulent flame speed measurements for hydrogen-containing fuel blends (70-30% vol. H₂-N₂, 85-15% vol. H₂-N₂, and 100% H₂) were developed at PSI (Switzerland).

Meanwhile, manufacturers are striving to develop turbines capable of running on 100% hydrogen, but long-term operation at these levels is still limited. Challenges include managing flame stability, mitigating flashback risks, and controlling NO_x emissions.

The hydrogen-based gas turbines archetype considers both co-fired and 100% hydrogen-based plants. Gas turbine integration in a combined cycle is not analysed since the integration would not affect the emissions.

The hydrogen ready gas turbine archetype is shown in Figure 69 and includes the following components:

- **Compressor:** The pressure ratio, similarly, to natural gas-fuelled turbines, ranges from 15-25 for heavy-duty turbined and exceeds 30 for aeroderivative turbines.
- **Combustion system:** Currently, for 100% hydrogen operation, combustion systems need to be equipped with diffusion flames and nitrogen or steam dilution systems. For large gas turbines configurations, steam dilution is preferred for efficiency and emissions reduction. Lean-premixed combustor technology has higher potential for the future but is less mature and not yet sufficiently developed for high hydrogen content fuels. Hydrogen content currently tolerated by different gas turbine is up to 30-50% vol. for heavy-duty engines, 50-70% vol. for smaller engines, and 20% vol. for micro gas turbines. Average turbine inlet temperature ranges from 1200 to 1650 °C for multi-cluster technologies^{144,145}.
- **Turbine:** Hydrogen-natural gas blends are currently used both in aeroderivative and heavy-duty units. For larger turbines co-fire up to 30%vol of hydrogen is possible, while the use of 100% hydrogen is expected in 10 to 20 years¹⁴⁶ in 20 MW up to GW-size turbines. For larger turbines co-fire up to 30%vol of hydrogen is possible, while the use of 100% hydrogen is expected in 10 to 20 years¹⁴⁶ in 20 MW up to GW-size turbines. The pressure ratio, similarly, to natural gas-fuelled turbines, ranges from 15-25 for heavy-duty turbined and exceeds 30 for aeroderivative turbines.
- **BOP/auxiliary elements:** includes all additional the components required for the effective operation of a generalized power plant (venting/blow-down valves, shutoff/control valves, metering valves, piping system, etc.)

Figure 69: General layout of gas turbine power plant.

The main operational parameters for the characterization of the gas turbine archetype for electricity production have been collected from partners experience, state of the art reports and multiple producers' datasheets as Baker Huges, Ansaldo, Siemens, General electric, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, MAN, Caterpillar. Key values are reported in Table 37¹⁴⁴⁻¹⁴⁶.

Table 37: Operational parameters for Aero-derivative and Heavy-Duty hydrogen ready gas turbines.

Parameters	Values	
	Aero-derivative	Heavy Duty
Type	Aero-derivative	Heavy Duty
Power [MW]	15-120	50-600
Hydrogen share	50-70 (today)	30-50 (today)
Efficiency [% LHV]	34-39	38-45
Pressure Ratio	15-40	15-25
Turbine inlet temperature TIT [C°]	1200-1650	1200-1650
Exhaust temperature [°C] (no CHP)	450-550	600-700
Speed [rpm]	3000-3600	3000-3600

The main hydrogen releases related to hydrogen based and co-fired gas turbines are related to the valves/fitting losses and hydrogen unburned residues at the outlet of the turbine:

- Fuel Gas valve Isolating Interstage Vent: It is typically routed to atmosphere during different operating conditions, related to the Gas line volume between isolating and vent valves.
- Fuel Gas Valve Isolating Packing vent: It is typically routed to atmosphere during normal operation, related to fuel gas valves size and operating conditions
- Unburned Gas to Exhaust: Presence of Unburned gas during different operating conditions
- Control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings: Control valves, safety valves, venting/blow-down valves, manual valves, fittings can be considered sources of leakages or losses during normal operation or due to some process events (i.e. Depressurization after shut-down, PSV opening for pressure protection, etc.), as detailed in the “3.1 Balance of Plant Process Elements” chapter.

8.4. Heat thermal use

Manufacturing is responsible for 81% of energy consumption within the industrial sector, with the remainder attributed to mining, construction, and agriculture. The predominant energy sources for these processes are natural gas and petroleum, which together constitute over 80% of the total energy usage.

Industrial heat is utilized in a variety of processes that occur at different temperatures, including metal smelting, driving endothermic chemical reactions, and the distillation of fuel ethanol. Hydrogen is emerging as a promising option for providing high-temperature process heat with the added benefit of being carbon-free¹⁴⁷

In 2018, five major sectors in the United States—chemical production, oil refining, iron and steel, pulp and paper, and cement—accounted for 70% of the industrial heat demand¹⁴⁸.

Green hydrogen is expected to encounter competition as a low-carbon heat solution, particularly for high-temperature applications. Most applications requiring temperatures above 500°C remain beyond the reach of current electrification technologies, whereas hydrogen, with a combustion temperature reaching up to 2100°C, is capable of meeting the heat requirements across this spectrum¹⁴⁹

Today for industrial heat, up to 50% mix of hydrogen and natural gas could be used without significant increases in NO_x emissions¹⁵⁰, with gas burners efficiencies higher than 90%¹⁵¹.

Also, the thermal use of energy in buildings constitutes a significant portion of total energy consumption and global carbon emissions, primarily due to the combustion of natural gas. To mitigate the emissions associated with this application, various strategies have been proposed, such as the electrification of heating (through the deployment of heat pumps) and the injection of H₂ into gas grids. The former strategy would necessitate a substantial expansion of the electricity infrastructure and retrofitting homes for electric heating technologies, while the latter can leverage existing gas grids. H₂ based boilers for residential buildings present a viable alternative solution for heating and hot sanitary water production, offering a complementary solution to heat pumps. Pure H₂ gas boiler for heating purposes has been developed by several companies, including Remeha and Bekaert Heating. While these boilers are technically similar to traditional ones, some technical adjustments are expected to accommodate H₂. Key modifications include the flame detector and the burner. H₂ has a significantly higher flame speed than natural gas, which raises the local flame temperature and can result in elevated NO_x levels. Therefore, a burner redesign is expected to minimize the NO_x emissions.

The archetype developed for future NH₂RA analysis is shown in Figure 70. As shown, boilers are considered when the heat demand is supplied by hot, pressurized water or steam while burners are adopted when heat is transferred to another fluid like, for example, drying air in ceramic industry.

Figure 70: General Archetype for hydrogen utilization for thermal uses

The main operative parameters of the archetype depend on the specific performances of the burners/boilers. Specifically, H₂ demand can be calculated as a function of the heat demand, the efficiency of the boiler/burner and the composition of the entering gas mixture.

The main H₂ releases for this archetype are assumed to be limited to:

- **Incomplete Combustion.** Unburned H₂ in the exhaust flue gases can be present depending on the combustion efficiency and the H₂-natural gas mixture composition.
- **Fugitives:** Fugitive Losses through fittings, and the components in the balance of plants, as detailed in the “3.1 Balance of Plant Process Elements” chapter.

9. CONCLUSIONS

This report provides a comprehensive analysis of the main technologies across the hydrogen supply chain, focusing on those at advanced stages of development. The analysis aligns with European development scenarios for 2030 and 2050, as outlined in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), to project the growth and integration of these technologies in the energy market.

The NHyRA project is central to this analysis, aiming to evaluate hydrogen emissions across the value chain, with a specific focus on anthropogenic emissions. By developing an emissions inventory and conducting experimental tests, NHyRA seeks to provide valuable data for the scientific and industrial communities. This project will also generate emissions scenarios for the current period, as well as for 2030 and 2050, aiding decision-makers in implementing effective mitigation strategies.

This report identifies key technologies and equipment, termed "archetypes," that are crucial in the supply chain and potential sources of hydrogen emissions. These archetypes encompass various stages of the supply chain, including production, compression, storage, liquefaction, conversion, and utilization.

The methodology section of the report outlines the creation of "archetypes" to facilitate scenario analysis in future work packages. These archetypes are characterized by key operational parameters that influence hydrogen emissions, such as operating pressure, temperature, flow rates, and others.

Hydrogen emissions are categorized into three main types: fugitives, vented, and incidents. This categorization aligns with procedures from the natural gas sector, enabling a standardized approach to evaluating emissions. Effective management of hydrogen emissions is crucial, as research indicates that these emissions can impact the environment by affecting the lifetime of other greenhouse gases.

By summarizing, this report underscores the importance of advancing hydrogen technology, strategic planning, and effective emission management to support the transition towards a sustainable hydrogen economy. The findings and methodologies outlined in this report will provide a robust foundation for future research and development in the hydrogen sector.

Despite the large amount of data reported, it is important to note that the present study shows some limitations. First, not all archetypes have been described in the same level of detail. Some of them are low TRL technologies. Therefore, the schematization of H₂ emission sources could be challenging. In fact, mature industrial plants emissions are expected to differ from those occurring at a laboratory scale or from a prototype. Second, also very complex industrial plants are described by archetypes. These plants are usually custom designed per the specific requests of a client. Therefore, the same type of plant can show different configurations. However, it has to be mentioned that the NHyRA project doesn't aim to investigate every possible plant's configuration.

Contacting plants' manufacturers/owners/operators is believed to be the best way to face the issue effectively and avoid emissions overestimation or underestimation. For this purpose, surveys, questionnaires, or interviews will be developed and performed in the future NHyRA project plan.

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